

Synthesis, characterization, theoretical investigation and biological

Screening of metal-II complexes of derived from (E)-4-(((3-aminopyrazin-2-yl)methylene)amino)benzoic acid

A Thesis

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for
Award of the Degree of **Doctor of Philosophy**

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this thesis are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This thesis is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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This is to certify that the thesis entitled **“Synthesis, characterization, theoretical investigation and biological Screening of metal-II complexes of derived from (E)-4-(((3-aminopyrazin-2-yl)methylene)amino)benzoic acid ”** submitted by **Dr.N. Kotilingaiah** to SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy is a Bonafede record of the research work carried out by him under my/our supervision and guidance. The content of the thesis, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In this study, the impact of aldehyde on anilin was investigated. Two residues of bases were found to be isomers with the bases, which formed when anilin was applied to fatty acids and its hydroxyl group. Two diamides were also found to be isomers with the bases, which formed when anilin was applied to fatty acids and its hydroxyl group. The first two residues were known as beta-hydroxy acids, the last as acyl-hydroxy acids. The study also investigated the effects of substituting aniline with aldehyde, revealing that a third series of diamides were formed after the reaction. These compounds rely on a series of diamides, which are isomers with aethylenamine and semen hydroxyl group. It is expected that other substituting aldehydes would produce new diamides. The results and findings from the study provide insight into the effects of aniline on aldehyde and its effects on fatty acids. The study also highlights the potential for further research on the effects of natriomamalgams on allantoin [1]. Chitosan, a naturally occurring amino-polysaccharide, has gained attention for its antifungal properties due to its unique physiochemical characteristics and biological activities. Studies have shown that chitosan can inhibit the growth of *Alternaria alternate*, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*, and *Rhizopus stolonifer*, with the inhibitory index affecting the concentration. Chitosan can completely inhibit fungi growth at a concentration of 3%. Researchers have focused on molecular weight and degree of deacetylation, but less on the antifungal activities of chitosan derivatives. The antifungal activity of chitosan is proposed to be due to its polycationic properties, with different amido groups in different chitosan derivatives. The study aimed to investigate the antifungal activity of other chitosan derivatives by synthesizing Schiff bases of chitosan, N-substituted chitosan, and quaternized chitosan and measuring their antifungal activities against *Botrytis cinerea* Pers. and *Colletotrichum lagenarium* (Pass) Ell.et halst[2]. Thiosemicarbazides are crucial in biology due to their high antitumor, antibacterial, antiviral, and antimalarial activities. They form neutral or anionic chelates with metal ions, affecting their biological behavior. Their mechanism of action is based on inhibition of ribonucleotide reductase, a key enzyme in DNA precursor biosynthesis. Unlike mono-thiosemicarbazides and their complexes, bis thiosemicarbazide cytotoxicity targets hypoxic tissue, making it widely used as radiopharmaceuticals. The structurally related anticancer drug elesclomol exhibited potent cytostatic activity[3]. Thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) are Schiff base ligands with significant medical applications in treating diseases like leprosy and tuberculosis. They have shown

beneficial biological activities in areas such as antiviral, antibacterial, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antimalarial, and anti-HIV. TSCs are synthesized via condensation reactions of an aldehyde or ketone with a thiosemicarbazide and coordinate with metals in a bidentate fashion via sulfur and azomethine nitrogen. Biological activities of TSC complexes are affected by the type of metal center and the group attached to the aldehyde moiety. Cisplatin has been used as the most potent metal-based anticancer drug, but it has challenges such as multidrug resistance and adverse side effects. To address these issues, palladium complexes are used as natural substitutes to platinum due to their similarity in complex forming processes and coordination geometry. Palladium thiosemicarbazone complexes are potent towards cancer cells due to their ability to form diverse structures, lipophilicity, and square planar geometry. Mono-palladium(II) chloride was active against lung and breast cancer cell lines, while aryl substituted thiosemicarbazone palladium complexes were found to be active against both murine and human cells resistant to cisplatin. The denticity also influences the biological activities of palladium and other metal complexes, with tridentate and tetradentate showing better anti-proliferative activities than mono/bi-dentate.

This work reports the anticancer activities of novel thiophene-substituted thiosemicarbazone palladium complexes, focusing on the synthesis of π -donor ligands and their respective palladium complexes and their anticancer activities using human cervical, human colon, colorectal, and non-cancerous cell lines [4]. The chemistry of transition metal complexes of thiosemicarbazone (TSC) ligands has been a subject of research interest for six decades due to their numerous pharmacological properties. TSCs are a class of N, S bidentate Schiff base ligands synthesized by the condensation of a ketone or an aldehyde with a thiosemicarbazide. They can coordinate to the metal center in neutral or anionic forms, depending on the presence of nitrogen and sulfur donor atoms. The biological activity of TSC derivatives and their metal complexes depends on the parent aldehyde and ketone, as well as the central metal ion of the complexes. Heterocyclic TSCs and their Pd(II) and Pt(II) complexes exhibit a variety of biological activities against various tumors, viruses, fungi, bacteria, protozoa, malaria, and convulsions. Cinnamaldehyde (CIN), a naturally occurring phytochemical compound, possesses significant properties such as anti-inflammatory, oxidative, and anti-oxidative properties, making it a suitable candidate for anticancer drugs. CIN has been shown to exert chemopreventive activity against various types of human cancer cells, inducing apoptosis and regulating cancer

cell invasion and metastasis. The coordination of ligands to metals gives them a three-dimensional orientation, improving their biological activity. This study aimed to prepare new TSCs-based thiophene derivatives and CIN, coordinated to Pd(II) ion, and determine their mode of coordination and anticancer activities[5]. Cancer is a major health concern worldwide, with lung cancer being the most common and affecting an average of 2.1 million women each year. Early diagnosis approaches emphasize the importance of effective and timely treatment for cancer patients. Transition metal complexes with chemotherapeutic properties have been synthesized due to the unmet clinical need for effective anticancer drugs. Cisplatin, a Pt-based drug, gained popularity for its cytotoxic property, leading to the development of new alternatives based on other metals and their corresponding complexes. Ruthenium(II/III) complexes have gained considerable interest due to their comparable ligand exchange kinetics to Pt. The in vivo mechanism of action of Ru complexes as anticancer agents differs from the conventional DNA-binding mechanism exhibited by cisplatin. Ru(III) complexes, such as indazolium trans-tetrachlorobis(1H-indazole)ruthenate(III) (KP1019) and sodium trans-tetrachlorobis(1H-indazole)ruthenate(III) (NKP-1339), have shown promise in chemical model systems both in vitro and in vivo. Indoles are considered privileged moieties in biological systems due to their valuable potential in human health care. Thiosemicarbazones (TSCs) are bidentate chelating ligands with a wide range of pharmacological properties, such as antifungal, antibacterial, antioxidant, and antitumor. Transition metal complexes have advantages over other small molecular drugs due to their wide spectrum of oxidation number, coordination states, and multi-target effect. Metal complexes may produce favorable multi-target effects on pathogens and viruses due to their unique metal centers. The rapid spread of SARS-CoV-2 has increased research towards developing potential COVID-19 antiviral drugs and vaccines. Solubility is an important factor for drugs to enter the systemic circulation for showing a pharmacological response. Therefore, the need for water-soluble drugs is significant. This study aimed to design and synthesize a water-soluble binuclear Ru(II)-p-cymene complex in a one-step reaction, characterized by analytical and spectroscopic tools[6]. Heterocyclic chemistry is crucial for designing and discovering new compounds, with thiosemicarbazones being used as intermediates. These compounds enhance biological activities and are used in organic synthesis. This study reports an efficient method for synthesizing 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiones using derived thiosemicarbazones. The structures of the products were characterized using infrared

spectroscopy, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, mass spectrometry, elemental analysis, and single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis[7].

Cancer is the second leading cause of death worldwide, with hepatocellular carcinomas (HCC) being the sixth most prevalent type and the third most frequent cause of cancer mortality. HCC is the second-greatest cause of cancer-related death in men, after carcinoma. Risk factors for HCC include hepatitis, alcoholic disease, and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis/non-alcoholic liver disease. Medical researchers have focused on 1,3-thiazole and 1,3,4-thiadiazole systems to develop effective anticancer drugs. Thiazole derivatives, generated from thiosemicarbazones, exhibit a broad range of pharmacological properties, including antiparasitic, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities. Acid hydrazides are widely used for synthesis of heterocyclic compounds, including inhibitors of myeloperoxidase, insecticides, glycogen phosphorylase, antituberculous medicines, and HIV. Recent studies have reported the synthesis of hydrazides directly from corresponding acids without hazardous solvents or support reagents, and their confirmation using green chemical principles. 1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives have antioxidant, antidepressant, anti-cancer, anticonvulsant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, anti-leishmanial, and radio-protective activities. A novel, simple method for producing functionalized 1,3,4-thiadiazoles derivatives with thiazole moiety as potent cytotoxic agents against liver cancer cell lines is presented[8]. Urease is a nickel-containing enzyme found in bacteria, algae, fungi, and plants that catalyzes the hydrolysis of urea to ammonia and carbamate, which quickly hydrolyzes to ammonia and carbonic acid. It is responsible for the pathogenesis of several bacteria and is immunogenic in humans, triggering the release of antibodies and inflammation. Urease enzyme is crucial for the survival and colonization of bacterial pathogens, increasing the concentration of ammonia in the microenvironment and protecting the colony from gastric acid. It also causes alkalization of urine, leading to precipitation of struvite and carbonate apatite, forming urinary stones. Combining antibiotic therapy with urease inhibitors has been beneficial for treating kidney stones and urease positive urinary tract infections[9]. Myeloid leukemia (ML) is a blood cancer caused by the uncontrolled generation of immature monocytes and granulocytes in the bone marrow. Chemotherapy and bone marrow transplantation are the main strategies for treating ML, but cure rates remain low. The aberrant vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) signaling induces the proliferation, survival, and resistance of ML cancer cells to chemotherapy. Anti-angiogenic therapies and apoptosis induction are considered valuable approaches for managing

this malignancy. Investigating biochemical changes in apoptotic and antiapoptotic markers is crucial to determine the perfect anticancer medication. Semicarbazone, thiosemicarbazone, urea, and thiourea fragments have been incorporated as privileged linkers in several potent anticancer molecules with VEGFR-2 inhibition and apoptosis induction potentials. To the best of our knowledge, none of the previously developed semicarbazones- and thiosemicarbazone-linked heterocycles have been evaluated for their cytotoxicity against myeloid leukemia. However, two trials have been adopted to evaluate profiles of anticancer candidates incorporating urea and thiourea fragments against myeloid leukemia over the last two decades.

The authors decided to design and synthesize a new set of novel derivatives by tethering the pharmacophoric privileged fragments semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone to the 1,2,3-triazole ring. Twelve novel derivatives were synthesized, their growth inhibition effects against a panel of sixty cancer cells, and their VEGFR-2 inhibitory potentials were reported. The VEGFR-2 inhibitory effect of sorafenib was reported to be mediated through the presence of a number of pharmacophoric fragments and four main interactions with VEGFR-2[10]. Transition metals, such as Cu(I), Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Pd(II), and Ag(I), play a significant role in biological redox reactions due to their comparative stability in different oxidation states. Transition metal catalysts are widely adopted in synthetic organic chemistry due to their diverse reactivity in enabling molecular transformations. The development of supporting ligands has significantly impacted the reactivity and stability of metal complexes in the primary coordination sphere. Thiosemicarbazones and thiocarbazones act as active ligands due to their better coordination tendencies, more stable complexes, better selectivity, and the possibility of forming macrocyclic ligands. The Schiff bases of thiosemicarbazone and thiocarbazones display a wide range of coordination modes with transition metals, influenced by the number and type of substituents[11]. Cancer is a major public health issue with malignant characteristics such as infinite proliferation, metastasis, and drug resistance. Medicinal chemists are developing anti-cancer drugs targeting DNA damage repair pathways, with PARP-1 being a crucial regulator. Several PARP inhibitors have been developed, with five approved for clinical use and several compounds entering clinical trials. Current PARP inhibitors show beneficial effects in refractory cancers like ovarian cancer, pancreatic cancer, triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC), and

prostate cancer with BRCA1/2 mutation. Recent clinical studies have also shown a high clinical response rate in TNBC patients who have not received chemotherapy treatment, indicating further expansion of PARP-1 inhibitors' clinical use.

However, existing PARP-1 inhibitors have drawbacks such as poor physicochemical properties, serious toxicity and side effects, narrow application range, and drug resistance. Therefore, it is necessary to search for new PARP-1 inhibitors to overcome these shortcomings. The structure-activity relationship (SAR) of present PARP-1 inhibitors includes an amide group, aromatic ring, and hydrophobic groups. Thiosemicarbazone and its derivatives are the main pharmacophores of many anti-cancer drugs, as they effectively inhibit the activity of ribonucleotide reductase, an enzyme involved in DNA synthesis. This work aims to synthesize novel PARP-1 inhibitors capable of inhibiting ribonucleotide reductase activity, revealing the anticancer activity of the resulting target compounds and their mechanism of action[12]. Isonicotinic hydrazide (INH) is a potent hydrazide with numerous biological properties, including antitubercular, antimicrobial, anticonvulsant, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-platelet, and anti-tumor properties. Its *in vivo* inhibitory activity against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv has led to the development of various INH derivatives, including Iproniazid, an antituberculosis and antidepressant drug. Hydrazones derived from INH and pyridinecarboxaldehydes show activity against Gram positive and negative bacteria and exhibit good cytotoxicity. Thiosemicarbazides have high biological and antitumor activities, with coordination with metal ions increasing their activity. They have wide applications in catalysis, non-linear optics, chemical analysis, and various industrial aspects. This work presents the synthesis and characterization of a new ligand, 2-isonicotinoyl-N-phenylhydrazine-1-carbothioamide, with strong cytotoxicity against HCT-116 and HEPG-2 cell lines[13]. Thiosemicarbazones are attractive due to their bonding modes, biological implications, structural diversity, and ion-sensing capabilities. They are effective chelating ligands for metal complexes, and their biological activities can be altered through complexation with transition metals like copper(II) ions. Thiosemicarbazone-metal complexes act as antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, and anti-inflammatory agents. They have potential applications in nonlinear optics, electrochemical sensing, and Langmuir film generation. 1,2,3-triazoles have a wide range of biological activities and can be synthesized through click chemistry, cycloaddition of substituted nitriles, or reactions of diazo compounds and amines or amides. The current work focuses on synthesizing a new

1,2,3-triazole derivative, continuing our interest in heterocycle synthesis. Both thiosemicarbazones and 1,2,3-triazoles have their applications in various fields[14]. The development of a novel Schiff's-base ligand has gained significant significance in coordination chemistry, as it is synthesized by the condensation of primary amines and aldehydes or ketones and forms complexes with transition metals via nitrogen lone pair electrons. These chelating agents have wide applications due to their strong electron-donating property. Schiff bases and their transition metal complexes have been extensively explored for their applications in various fields, including nonlinear optics, molecular/metal ion sensing, dye-sensitized solar cells, molecular magnetism, and photoluminescence. They also show a broad range of biological properties such as anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, herbicidal, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, and anti-tumor activities. The non-linear optics (NLO) of materials was started after the Kerr effect in 1875. Molecules with large optical non-linearities have become the center of recent research due to their potential applications in various photonic technologies, including all-optical switching and data processing. Drug-like compounds are molecules that contain functional groups and/or have physical properties consistent with the majority of known drugs, and can be inferred as compounds that might be biologically active or show therapeutic potential. To be effective as a drug, a potent molecule must reach its target in the body in sufficient concentration and stay there in a bioactive form long enough for the expected biological events to occur. In recent years, the inhibition of histone deacetylase- and ribonucleotide reductase- has emerged as an innovative and significant approach to the treatment of cancer. This inhibition is expressed in various types of cancers, including colon-, breast-, lung-, pancreatic tumor tissue, metastatic melanoma, acute myeloid leukemia, acute lymphocytic leukemia, and childhood tumors of the nervous system. Studies on the structural, theoretical, and molecular docking studies of a special class of Schiff's-bases have been conducted, resulting in single crystals of nickel(II) and manganese(II) complexes of this class of ligand[15]. treatment can help cure many types of cancers. Carbothioamide, a class of organic compounds with active sites N, O, and S, has numerous medicinal and biological applications, including anti-cancer activity. Carbothioamides have shown efficient cytotoxicity against MCF-7 and Hela cells, and metal ions can enhance their activity by forming coordination compounds. A ligand derived from pyrazole-4-carbothioamide and its coordination compounds showed good results against the Hela cell line. A new thiocarbamide derivative derived from triazol-3-amine and benzoyl isothiocyanate

showed strong cytotoxicity against liver cancer and breast carcinoma, in addition to antioxidant activities. N-methylantraniloyl(4-phenylthiosemicarbazide) and some of its metal complexes exhibited significant high cytotoxicity against MCF7 and HepG2 compared to cisplatin. Several papers have reported the applications of DFT in studying and characterization of organic compounds. This work synthesized a new ligand 2-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-N-phenyl-hydrazine-1-carbothioamide derived from carbothioamide and its metal complexes, showing strong cytotoxicity and potential as an anti-cancer drug[16]. The coordination chemistry of transition metals is a challenging and experimentally demanding field in modern inorganic chemistry. (thio)semicarbazones, a widely used ligand, have remarkable complexation properties towards various metal ions. These compounds, part of the Schiff bases family, can be obtained through condensation reactions with aldehydes or ketones. The ease of synthesis and complexation properties make them ideal for smart design of structures. (thio)semicarbazone moieties are N,O/S bidentate ligands, yielding five-membered chelate metalocycles upon coordination to a metal ion. However, incorporating additional donor functions, such as pyridine derivatives, can facilitate a tridentate coordination mode. These compounds have been studied extensively due to their diverse biological activity and are a focus in biomedicine. The study reports the solvent-induced synthesis and molecular and supramolecular structures of two nickel(II) complexes derived from the bis-thiosemicarbazone ligand H2LI, obtained by the condensation of 2,2'-(ethane-1,2-diylbis(oxy)dibenzaldehyde with 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide. To the best of our knowledge, neither the crystal structure of H2LI nor its metalocomplexes are known. Therefore, the chemistry of H2LI is of particular interest. Extensive theoretical studies are performed to identify physical factors contributing to the stability of the reported metal-based supramolecular architectures[17]. Thiourea derivatives, a group of thiourea derivatives, have gained significant attention due to their variable bonding modes and potential biological applications. These compounds have been used as drugs and have been evaluated for their antiviral, antioxidant, antibacterial, antitumor, anticancer, and antitubercular therapeutics over the last 50 years. Thiosemicarbazones are potent intermediates for synthesis of pharmaceutical and bioactive materials, making them widely used in medicinal chemistry. A number of N-substituted arylthiosemicarbazide derivatives have been prepared and evaluated for their antimicrobial and antitubercular activities. This work aims to synthesize -phenylhydrazine-1,2-bis(carbothioamide) and investigate its antibacterial, cytotoxic, and antioxidant activities[18]. hiosemicarbazide and

Schiff bases are extensively researched due to their antibacterial and anticorrosion properties. Schiff bases are crucial intermediates for synthesis of bioactive compounds like β -lactams and thiazolidone. They can be prepared using various methods, such as refluxing aldehydes or ketones with primary amines. Microwave-promoted organic synthesis has been used in the last decade, with 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazide being selected as a working compound. This study reports an efficient synthesis of new functionalized Schiff bases derived from 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazones. Quantum calculations of physical properties were performed using the Gaussian 09W set of programs[19]. Isatin, a compound known for 150 years, has been found to exhibit biological activity in mammals. Its Schiff bases and Mannich bases have various pharmacological properties, including antibacterial, anticonvulsant, anti-HIV, antifungal, antiviral, and anticancer activity. A variety of 3-substituted indolin-2-ones have been used as anticancer drugs or drug candidates. Sunitinib, a multi-targeting tyrosine kinase inhibitor, is a representative member of this class. 6-Methoxycarbonyl group-substituted indolin-2-ones are potent inhibitors of VEGFR-1/2/3, PDGFR α , and FGFR-1, with low cross-reactivity against other kinases. Indirubin was identified as the active ingredient in a traditional Chinese recipe for treating chronic myelogenous leukemia. Thiosemicarbazones, such as Isatin-3-thiosemicarbazones, have been studied extensively due to their important biological activities. Previous studies have revealed promising cytotoxic and anticonvulsant properties of various 2,3-dioxo-2,3-dihydroindole thiosemicarbazones. The synthesis of new N-4-aryl thiosemicarbazone derivatives of substituted 2,3-dioxo-2,3-dihydroindoles has been performed and evaluated for cytotoxic, antiviral, and antimicrobial activity[20]. Thiosemicarbazide and Schiff bases are extensively researched due to their antibacterial and anticorrosion properties. Schiff bases are crucial intermediates for synthesis of bioactive compounds like β -lactams and thiazolidone. They can be prepared using various methods, such as refluxing aldehydes or ketones with primary amines. Microwave-promoted organic synthesis has been used in the last decade, with 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazide being selected as a working compound. This study reports an efficient synthesis of new functionalized Schiff bases derived from 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazones. Quantum calculations of physical properties were performed using the Gaussian 09W set of programs[21]. It seems like you've provided information about the diverse biological activities of isoniazid (INH) and its derivatives, as well as the broader applications of thiosemicarbazide derivatives. Isoniazid's wide range of activities, including its use as an antitubercular,

antimicrobial, anticonvulsant, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-platelet, and anti-tumor agent, highlights its versatility. Furthermore, the synthesis of copper complexes of INH derivatives and their evaluation as antitumor agents, with attributed antitumor activity to the inhibition of ribonucleotide reductase enzyme, adds an interesting dimension to the potential medical applications of these compounds. The mention of iproniazid as an antituberculosis and antidepressant drug and the exploration of hydrazones derived from INH and pyridinecarboxaldehydes with activities against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, along with good cytotoxicity activities, underscores the diverse pharmaceutical potential of these compounds.

Additionally, the information on thiosemicarbazides and their coordination with metal ions to enhance biological and antitumor activities, as well as their applications in catalysis, non-linear optics, chemical analysis, and various industrial aspects, further emphasizes the multifaceted nature of these chemical compounds and their significance in both biological and industrial contexts. It appears that you're describing a research effort focused on synthesizing and studying the cytotoxicity of various isonicotinic thiosemicarbazide derivatives and their metal complexes. The compounds mentioned include N-ethyl-2-isonicotinoylhydrazine-1-carbothioamide, N-(2-isonicotinoyl hydrazine carbonothioyl)benzamide, 2-isonicotinoyl-N-phenylhydrazine-1-carboxamide, and N-benzoyl-2-isonicotinoylhydrazine-1-carboxamide. The goal of the work seems to be the exploration of new derivatives with potential anti-cancer activity. The focus is on the synthesis and characterization of a new ligand, 2-isonicotinoyl-N-phenylhydrazine-1-carbothioamide, and its metal complexes. The study includes testing the cytotoxicity against HCT-116 and HEPG-2 cell lines, indicating strong cytotoxicity of the ligand against these cancer cell lines.

Furthermore, the mention of the compounds being semi-conductors suggests that their electronic properties, specifically their optical band gap, were investigated. This aspect might have implications for potential applications in electronic or optoelectronic devices. Overall, this research reflects a comprehensive exploration of the biological and electronic properties of the synthesized compounds, aiming to contribute to the development of new compounds with anti-cancer potential and potentially interesting semiconductor properties[22].

2. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS & RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

All reactions were performed under nitrogen atmosphere in a fume-hood using Schlenk technique. The reaction progress was monitored using Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC). The reagents and solvents used were of analytical grade purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Chemicals purchased were used without further purifications while the solvents were dried before using standard procedures. Melting points were determined on capillary tubes using SMP-10 apparatus. UV-Vis spectra for ligands and complexes were.

PHYSICAL RESEARCH FOR SCHIFF BASE CO-ORDINATION BEHAVIOR

Coordination chemistry is a rapidly developing field, with substantial advances achieved in the last decade. Schiff base-based M compounds are one of the most important divisions, and they are used in a broad variety of biological processes. Nanotechnology may make use of inorganic nanoparticles. A broad range of chelating characteristics may be found in Schiff bases, which are the result of condensation reactions between aromatic aldehyde compounds and amines. After chelation, metal ion complexes produced from 'Schiff base ligands' have dramatically increased biological activity as well as other properties compared to free ligands. In terms of biological activity and other properties after chelation, metal complexes generated from Schiff base ligands outperform the free ligand. Researchers are increasingly focusing on Schiff bases that have been effectively synthesised from amines or aldehydes with heterocyclic rings because of their relevance in biological, therapeutic, medicinal, analytical, and pharmacological sectors. Compounds derived from 4-aminoantipyrine and related Schiff-base complexes have a wide range of pharmacological properties. To cool things down, it's a pyrazole derivative It's a substance that's employed in the production of azo dyes. It may be used to counteract the effects of oxidative stress. It is possible to alter the coordinating properties of 4-aminoantipyrine by reacting with different types of aldehyde and amines as well as ketones and thiocarbazides. As a consequence of interacting with DNA to cause DNA damage, antiviral, anticancer and antiseptic substances cause cell death. DNA and metal ion compound interactions have aroused a lot of attention because of their importance in cancer treatment and molecular research. Hydrazine is utilised to create Schiff base and its metal (II) complexes. The properties of the Schiff base as well as the biological efficacy of the Schiff base and its metal (II) complexes are reviewed."

2.1 Schiff Base

Hugo Schiff-named Schiff bases are produced when the primary amine interacts with aldehydes or ketones under certain circumstances" (Schiff in 1864). Aldehydes and ketones have carbonyl groups ($O=C-$) that are replaced by azomethine or imine sets in the N atom analogue of Sb, which is also known as $-C=NH_2$ or imine. It is a yellow, stable ligand soluble in DMS, DMF, and $CHCl_3$ that has been employed in this work. Copper, cobalt, and iron all have highly distinct chemical properties. Copper, a typical transition metal, has the electrical structure $[Ar] 4s^2 3d^9$. There are many different coordination compounds that can be made using this method. One to three oxidation states are possible. Few copper compounds at the +3-oxidation state have been reported. Hetero-metallic, multi-nuclear Schiff base complexes with metal alkali ions have been made using Schiff base complexes. An aromatic aldehyde and an amine molecule are combined to form "Schiff bases," which have a long history of use owing to their simple synthesis and large variety of complexes they may form. Inorganic chemistry's most significant advances may be traced back to the discovery of Schiff bases.

Chemistry students may find Schiff bases fascinating because of their simple preparation and ability to alter the chemical environment surrounding an $N=C$ group. Under carefully regulated conditions, M salts complexes with Sbl's are often combined to form "Schiff bases" with M. Using transition metal ions to build coordination complexes is frequent because they allow for the synthesis of a wide range of metal ion compounds. It exhibits an array of physical and chemical properties as well as a variety of oxidation states in the words of P.G. Cozzi

2.2 Bensity of Sbl's

Depending on the number of donor atoms, ligands are classified as quadridentate, tridentate, didentate, or monodentate. One, two, or more donor sites on the ligand may form a closed ring with the centre metal ion. This ring-formation process is known as chelation. Bi-dentate, tri-dentate, tetra-dentate, and poly-dentate Schiff base ligands all contain nitrogen as a donor atom, and they all have nitrogen as an electron donor. The kind of aromatic aldehyde & amine used determines the donor nature of the ligand. Tridentate and tetradentate "Schiff base metal complexes" have both been reported in large numbers.

2.3 Significance of Schiff Base Complexes

Schiff bases have played an essential role as chelating agents in major group & transition metal coordination chemistry owing to their easy synthesis, stability under different circumstances of oxidation and reduction, as well as the structural flexibility associated with their various uses. Literature suggests that a number of significant advances in inorganic chemistry may be traced back to this complicated ligand system. Modern coordination chemistry, inorganic biology, catalysts, optical and medical imaging, & thin films all owe a debt of gratitude to Schiff bases, which played a key role in the development of these fields. Researchers have been intrigued by t-M compounds containing "Schiff base ligands" for many years. Antibacterial, fungicidal, and cancer-fighting properties are among the many uses for transition metal Sb compounds. These chelating ligands are good for building Sb compounds with t-M ions and other metal ions because they include extra donor atoms such as O, S, and N. It is possible to synthesise several Sb M compounds with various structural properties as yields.

2.4 Schiff Base Metal Complexes

Complexes of Schiff bases and metal halides have been synthesised under proper experimental conditions. Chemicals have been synthesised using metal alkoxides, metal amides, metal alkyls, and metal acetates, all of which are metals. As far as Schiff base metal complexes go, they have been widely researched. A wide variety of co-ordination compounds with octahedron, tetrahedron, and square planar geometries may be synthesised using transition metal ions, notably first and second row transition metal ions. For the formation of compounds, copper (II) is an extremely frequent transition metal ion and non-transition metal ion. However, copper (II) is less common because of its refusal to conform to a standard hexagonal or quadricyclic crystal geometries. Cu (II) complex has a wider amplitude of separation of an electronic energy region than other first row transition metals due to the presence of considerable Jahn-Teller distortion. In all living organisms, copper (Cu) is a critical trace element. These enzymes include hemocyanins, superoxide dismutase, and blue copper proteins, all of which include copper atoms. The anti-ulcer properties of Cu (II) amino acid-based compounds have been discovered.

It was shown that the nuclease activity of Cobalt (II) compounds with pBR 322 DNA could be detected without the need of external reagents by the researchers Tian et al.

Figure 2.1 (A, B and C) Co (II) compounds of porphyrins, Sb'sand tetra aza structures

A Ni (II) co-ordination molecule, Ni (bpy) 2dppz²⁺, has been studied for its inter-calative DNA-binding properties. An aromatic molecule, 2-aminonicotinaldehyde has an amine and an aldehyde functional group and two nitrogen atoms in its ring. Because of the presence of nitrogen atoms, the heteroatom effect, which gives reactivity as well as chelating and other features, is induced by this effect. As a result, "the creation of imine (>C = N-) (or azomethine (-CH=N-) groups" from the reaction of the carbonyl group connected to aromatic aldehydes and ketones has

received a lot of attention." Catalysis, preparation, as well as other areas use a lot of these groups.

Figure 2.2 Generic structure of ANA

2-aminonicotinaldehyde (ANA) and its derivatives have only had a few studies done on their multiple denticity and chelate capability, and this is about to change. A number of scientists explored metal complexes and their physical and chemical features, such as their stability and selectivity. There are several applications for metal complexes generated from 2-aminonicotinadine (ANA) derivatives, which are used in a variety of fields including materials science, biology and catalysis. Fluorescence spectroscopy, colorimetric approaches, electrochemical, atomic absorption spectroscopy, inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy, mass spectroscopy, and others are among the methods used.

The development of new drugs with multi-target inhibitory abilities has lately been a major focus of study due to the multiple benefits it offers over conventional synergistic combination treatment using compounds with metabiological activity. Similar to traditional pharmaceuticals, Schiff base and its metal complexes may have a wide range of effects. Amaiakacin was his go-to antibiotic for bacteria, whereas Nystatin was his go-to fungicide. When Sb and M ion (II) compounds were examined, the latter demonstrated an increase in inhibitory effect when fused with metal (II) ions. The antibacterial activity of the chemicals formed is very high. Cooperatively formed complex structures are reduced in size, and donor parties are responsible for the distribution of positive ions and maybe electrons throughout their complex formation rings; this process is known as chelation. Bioorganic chemistry relies heavily on transition metal complexes because of their wide range of oxidation states, which may be used as models of active sites in biological systems.

Research efforts using Schiff bases include organic synthesis, catalyst and drug design, and models for metalloenzyme active sites. Schiff bases are a class of compounds. When it comes to producing metal-organic hybrid materials, single-molecule magnets, very porous materials,

optical devices, and sensors, they are the most versatile chelators in the industry. The synthesis of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde derivatives has aroused the attention of various research organizations' due to its possible biological effects. In light of the rising prevalence of antibiotic resistance, new compounds with antibacterial action against pathogenic bacteria and fungi are becoming more necessary. Medical chemistry made its most significant advances when heterocyclic compounds played a significant role in influencing biological processes. Bioactive 2-aminonicotinaldehyde versions and M material have been studied in this respect, and a range of physiologically active, including such anti-inflammatory and antibacterial and anticancer activities, have been observed in their broad spectral distributions. Cobalt(ii), vanadium(ii), copper(ii), and ruthenium(ii) t- metal ions are predicted to be synthesised in the present work because to the biological value of Sb obtained from the condensed reaction of 2-aminonicotinaldehydes with different substitutions and its applicability in diverse domains. When it comes to investigating how ligand environments might influence the activity of metal complexes, as well as their spectrum properties, cytotoxic studies are of interest.

It is when an amino molecule reacts with an aromatic aldehyde compound that the Sb's are broken down. This class of chemical ligands, known as Schiff bases, has several biological uses. The C=N linkages in azomethines derivatives are necessary for biological activity, and various azomethines have been shown to have outstanding antibacterial and antifungal characteristics. Sb's and M compounds have recently been identified to have physiologically relevant action. A class of amino acid-based metal chelators, known as M compounds, is particularly successful in binding to a wide range of biologically relevant targets. It is well accepted in the scientific literature that Schiff base complexes are good co-ordinating ligands because of their high stability, considerable solubility in common solvents, and flexibility in altering their surroundings. The chemistry of multinuclear metal complexes has recently gotten increasing attention due to their importance in the multi-metal active sites of various metalloproteins and metalloenzymes. Polynuclear copper (II) compounds have caught the attention of academics in recent decades because of the relevance of knowing their structure and function. The easiest way to explain it is as an open cage in the cubane manner. Surprisingly, there are just two reports in the literature on open cage cubane geometries of Cu (II) compounds with Schiff base ligands in the related tetra nuclear copper (II) clusters with cubane structures. Salen-type Schiff bases are used as tetradentate chelating Ls with two N and two O atoms for donor sites to produce

mononuclear molecules. Although these metal compounds may be used as ligands to coordinate a second metal ion using the fascinating bridging capacity of the phenoxo O atoms, the outcome is multinuclear complexes. Since these dipositive transition elements are found in mononuclear compounds, they are useful as "ligand molecules" for synthesising heterometallic compounds. When Cu (II) chelates are used to include sodium (I), a plethora of heterometallic compounds is formed.

Rational ligand design, metal selection, and carefully controlled experimental conditions have produced several polynuclear compounds with fascinating structural and physico-chemical properties. For their intriguing hierarchical and magnetic characteristics, mixed-metal aggregates involving close connections between Na⁺ions and transition metal clusters have recently attracted a lot of attention. However, their contribution to understanding molecular recognition in biological systems has been overlooked. The earliest alkali metal complexing agents to be used were the crown ether, cryptand, and related ligands. However, there are numerous simpler and more affordable ligands that are just as effective. For alkali metal complexing, transition metal Schiff base complexes have recently emerged as an important tool. Supramolecular networks and highly dimensional molecular systems with customisable topologies have been the subject of several investigations. The composition and manufacture of transition metal co-ordination polymers spanned by small conjugated ligands (such as cyanide, azide, oxalate, thiocyanate, and nitrite) are presently actively being researched because of their structural diversity and in the context of molecule-based magnets. It is important to choose the right bridge ligands because they may convey magnetic couplings between paramagnetic metal ions, enabling the magnetic strength and nature of the system to be identified.

Tumors are formed when a certain kind of tissue grows abnormally in the human body. In contrast to healthy cells, cancer cells grow and replicate differently and continue to divide and proliferate unchecked. It's no secret that the management of malignant tumours has long been a topic of debate among doctors. Cancer cell growth and death have been successfully inhibited and even induced by chemical therapies, but treatment outcomes for most malignant tumour diseases remain poor. Development of new drugs with increased biological high selectivity is a goal for the future. Research into the anticancer properties of organic ligands and metal compounds has led to the discovery of a large number of anticancer ligands. Among these are

Schiff bases, which are easy to synthesise. It's easy to mix with metal ions since it has an active imino group. Biopharmaceutical research is also focusing on their antibacterial, antiviral, and tumour cell growth-inhibiting characteristics. Various cancer cells may use a variety of techniques to inhibit the reproduction of aberrant DNA. DNA is impacted by the cleavage or binding methods used by metal complexes. Non-covalently bind metal complexes to DNA through intercalation and electrostatic bonding. DNA may be cleaved by a wide variety of metal complexes in three distinct ways: hydrolytically, oxidatively, and photolytically. Although Cisplatin is a frequent treatment for cancer, it has problems such as resistance, toxicity, and other side effects, which limit its usefulness. Pharmacologically, Schiff bases are widely studied because of their broad spectrum of activities, including antibacterial, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-tuberculosis, antioxidative, and anticonvulsant properties. Colors, catalysts, organic synthesis intermediates, and stabilisers of polymers are all examples of Schiff bases. There's also the well-known structural active ingredient 2-aminonicotinaldehyde that has a wide range of beneficial properties for the treatment of cancer, bacterial and viral infections as well as malaria. Analytical, biological, inorganic, medicinal, and pharmaceutical research all benefit from the Schiff base made from 2-aminonicotinaldehyde. 2-aminonicotinaldehyde Schiff bases are particularly useful for pharmacological study because of their specific biological features, which include antifungal, antibacterial, anticancer, and cytotoxic activity. Dimeric and polymeric chemicals may be made using bis-bidentate.

A lot of attention has recently been paid to Schiff base ligands, particularly in terms of structural diagnostics. Because of their appealing physical and chemical properties, Schiff bases have become important ligands in the field of co-ordination chemistry. One of the most promising chelating agents is "Schiff bases with imine or azomethine ($-RC=N-$)" because they can generate complexes with an extensive spectrum of inner transition and inner transition metals. There are ligands in Schiff bases that are bidentate, tetradentate, and multidentate, as well as others. Due to its increased biological activity over non-Schiff base complexes, the biological activity of transition metal complexes produced from Schiff base ligands is one of the most intensively investigated subjects in coordination chemistry. Copper (ii) ion complexes containing Schiff bases have attracted increasing attention as prospective therapeutic therapies for a wide spectrum of disorders because of their extraordinary bioactive characteristics in vitro and in vivo. 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde Schiff bases have two ligands of type hydrogen bonding between the

enamine and enolimine forms of keto-enamine. Biological applications for Schiff base metal compounds include olefin hydrogenation catalysis and photocatalysis.

Schiff bases may be used to break down chemical molecules and produce radioactive isotopes. 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and its complexes have several uses in medicine, biology, and technological advancement. This has resulted in the utilisation of metal complexes of Schiff base in the creation of antibiotics. N complexes are a small but rapidly developing family of flame retardants that have spurred public concern regarding ecologically friendly FRS, since nitrogen-based flame retardants having high breakdown temperatures, they are perfect for recycling. For flexible polyurethane foams, melamines are one of the most often used materials. The antibacterial, flame retardant, & corrosion inhibitory properties of coumarin derivatives containing a thiazole ring have been explored as environmentally safe PU coating additives. It has recently been discovered that a DOPO-containing imidazole curing agent may be employed in a reactive and flame retardant epoxy glue that has been synthesised. Chemical linkage was used to introduce "phosphaphenanthrene, piperidine, and triazine-trione" groups to the epoxy matrix, resulting in an unique in tumescent reactive flame retardant epoxy system. This article overview of recent breakthroughs in surface-coating techniques for manufacturing flame retardant FPUFs. Finally, the advantages and disadvantages of in tumescent and non-in tumescent coatings for FR FPUFs, as well as future research potential, are discussed. Based on Schiff's chemistry, alkyd colour object compositions have been made. The limiting oxygen index was used to assess the FR properties of various additions (LOI). For the first time, chemotherapeutic medications were successfully utilised on a broad scale in people to prevent and cure bacterial infections. Sulphonamides and their metal complexes were investigated for their antibacterial properties since they limit the development and multiplication of harmful microorganisms. Findings from the study show that metal ion compounds have higher activity than their derived ligand. We employed a new sulphonamide L and its Cu metal combination to produce the coated film antibacterial and flame retardant. The limiting oxygen index (LOI) test was used to assess the flame retardant properties of the additives. Against "gram-negative, gram-positive, and fungal pathogens," the antimicrobial coatings were tested. It was also tested to determine whether the coatings' mechanical and physical properties were adversely affected by the additions.

Schiff base compounds containing an imine group ($-RC=N-$) are generated when a primary amine interacts with an active carbonyl. In the past, Schiff bases have played an important role as complexing ligands in the chemistry of main group and transition metal coordination because of their stability under various oxidative and reductive circumstances and because imine ligands were borderline between hard and soft Lewis bases. It is becoming more popular to include Sb ligands into transition metal ion materials owing to their well-known biological, chemical and physical characteristics, as well as their catalytic and therapeutic uses, as the area of Sb compounds grows. Metal-based antibiotics are being studied to find out if complexation changes the ligand's pharmacological properties and how antibiotics function.

Metal-based complexes are a fast-growing field of study, with innovative design and synthesis, structural explanation, & pharmacological assessment all contributing to their rapid growth. According to published study, many scientists have looked at transition metal ions chelate due to its wide range of applications. Human malignancies may be treated with a chemotherapeutic medication called Cis-platin. Cis-platin and its second-generation medications (carbo platin and Oxali platin) have been shown to be poisonous and have harmful effects. Schiff base complexes rather than Pt metal ions should be used to build medications with less adverse effects, higher curative characteristics and cheaper prices in order to address these negative impacts. Compounds comprising flavonoids of medium concentration and Schiff base Schiff base have shown antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer, antioxidant, and herbicidal properties. O, N, and S-based ligands have been used as donors for chelation, which has resulted in medical applications. Key to life biology and the development of novel pharmacological therapeutics, the development of DNA molecular probes and transition metal complexes that can bind to DNA in a physiological environment is being explored.

Antifungal, antibiotic, and anticancer characteristics are only a few of the uses of Schiff bases in the pharmaceutical sector. It has long been known that transition metal Schiff base compounds have biological action. A major role for aromatic amine Schiff bases in biological and pharmacological processes is played by these compounds. Sb ligands with O or N donor atoms are a good class of organics that may bind to different metal ions, and aromatic aldehydes have a superior conjugation mechanism than aliphatic aldehydes. In nature, the ligands around core metal ions are thus not symmetrical, and the coordination chemistry of transition metal

complexes with asymmetrical Schiff base ligands has received considerable interest. Transition metal complexes have several advantages over their symmetrical counterparts in terms of composition and shape. The steric and electronic features of asymmetric Schiff base compounds have been widely studied in connection to catalysis of numerous processes. They might be used in optoelectronics and as models for important biological species.

Schiff base metal complexes have shown potential in photo electrochemical energy conversion systems. Ligands have been incorporated into Schiff's base Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} + M materials, and they show outstanding properties Photoelectric properties. The inorganic semiconductor n-Si and the metal complex devices were created. An investigation was carried out using current-voltage measurements. There has been a rise in electrical conductivity with increasing temperature, activation energies below two eV, and an inherent conduction mechanism discovered via electrical studies of the Schiff base Nickel (II) complex. For use in semiconductors, dithiocarbazate metal compounds also demonstrated promising properties. The hydrogen generation catalytic activity of the Ni-complex with a bis-dithiocarbazate base was noteworthy. Due to their vast variety of applications, metal compounds have lately attracted a lot of attention. For semiconductor applications, the ions Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} is particularly intriguing.

Research and attention on Schiff bases ligands has increased in recent years. When aromatic aldehydes and compounds with an amine group are combined, Schiff bases are formed, which are distinguished by the presence of an azomethine group ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}$). As a ligand, Schiff bases have found broad use in coordination research because they may be synthesised via a simple condensation procedure. Reactions between aldehyde compounds and amino acids that include an amine group may also produce Schiff base ligands (Sb's). Synthesis of Sb's from amino acids and aldehyde groups relies heavily on the PH value, and most Sb's are generated with the aid of a base. An aromatic aldehyde group interaction with the amine group of an amino acid is more difficult than the creation of ordinary Schiff bases because a different reaction environment is required. Pharmacological properties have been identified for Sb and their metal complexes in biological systems. The amino acid (a a) derivative ligands serve biological and catalytic purposes throughout the different synthesis processes. Schiff bases, an amino acid derivative, have been utilised as a catalyst for the hydrolysis of esters after complexation with transition

metals. Schiff bases produced from amino acids combine with transition metals to form stable compounds that inhibit bacterial and fungal growth after complexation. Researchers also discovered how to manufacture functional metal nanoparticles that might be employed in a range of scientific fields. Several studies have been published on the antibacterial characteristics of homobimetallic tin complexes, with favourable results for complexes over the ligands. Mn, Fe, Co, and Re are only a few of the transition metal ion complexes whose structural features have been studied using a range of experimental methods. Anticorrosion uses of Schiff base (Sb) derivatives have also been proposed and documented. The production and structural elucidation of these compounds has also been reported. Vanadium oxide Schiff base, amino acid complexes proved to be potent inhibitors and effective oxidation-catalyzed catalysts in recent study. It was found that some unique Fe (ii) Schiff base, amino acid complexes were hazardous to embryos and DNA was found to be present. Both antibacterial and teratogenic properties are reported for the same catalysts. Antifungal properties have also been reported. Using iron Schiff base produced from amino acids, "aerobic oxidation of amines to nitriles" was carried out. The production of amino acid-derived Schiff bases and their complexes with various metals has attracted a lot of curiosity. In light of the aforementioned scenario, the following goals have been met in the current study: Schiff base, an amino acid-derived ligand, may be synthesised in a laboratory environment. Synthesis of Schiff base, the formation of twin compounds with various metals, and their antibacterial properties.

Medical chemistry has traditionally employed natural products and organic molecules to treat illness, but the synthesis of metal complexes as anticancer medications and the design and description of complexes as models for biological systems are increasingly gaining interest. There has been a lot of research on the possible anti-carcinogenic properties of metal ions with high biological activity such as vanadium, copper, cobalt, and nickel. When employed in cancer therapy, metal Schiff base complexes reduce tumour cell growth in vitro, disrupt protein function, target nucleic acids and speed up the creation of redox-active oxygen species. This results in cell cycle arrest and death. The utilisation of metal-based anticancer medications is one of the most advanced and intriguing topics of pharmaceutical research today. A variety of metal complexes have been created and studied for their anti-cancer capabilities, and their varied applications have attracted a great deal of attention because of their anti-cancer qualities. As a result of its many intercalations with DNA and high level of biological activity, this particular complex has piqued researchers' curiosity. Anti-cancer activity was shown by many Schiff base

complexes including N, O-donor Schiff base ligands derived from 2-aminonicotinaldehyde. Metal-based chemotherapeutic medications benefit from the addition of the ligand's activity. As part of our study, we've been looking at how the structural characteristics of N, O-donor Schiff base ligands and coordination compounds with amines that include methoxy groups affect biological activity. The structural importance of Schiff base ligands in the complex anticancer activity of copper & nickel complexes seemed to warrant further investigation. For the MKN-45 gastric cancer cell line, the newly produced anticancer chemicals.

Figure 2.3 “Synthetic routes for the preparation of complexes”.

Resistant microorganisms might grow uncontrolled since new medications are hard to come by. Chronic infections are becoming more common, which exacerbates the situation since many of these diseases are incurable due to drug resistance. DNA has recently attracted a lot of attention as a possible target in bacteria. The antibacterial activities of a number of DNA binding medicines have been shown. Against "clinical isolates of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA)," for example, the DNA intercalate echinomycin is highly effective in vitro and in vivo in mice. Antibacterial activity has been noted for derivative products of the DNA binder metallo-complex $[CoL_3]^{2+}$ actually contains 2, 2-bipyridine, 1, 10-phenanthroline, imidazole, methylimide, ethylim. It has been found that DNA gyrase inhibitors, such as the minor groove binder pentamidine, are effective against Gram positive as well as Gram negative bacteria with MIC values of 0.3 to 2.6 M. The metal complexes of benzimidazoles as well as their derivatives have already shown therapeutic applications as an inhibitor; and pentamidine has been used in clinical studies for a wide range of protozoal illnesses since the 1940s."

Figure 2.4 Benzimidazole, azomethine (Sb) functionality, complexes and metallocomplexes [M= Zn (II), Pd (II), Ni (II), Cu (II)].

Biomedical uses of (benz) imidazole Sb metal complexes have been examined in a new study. According to in vitro studies, the Schiff base complexes Zn (II), Pd (II), Sn (II), and Ag (I) are effective antimicrobials and antibiotics. A multitude of biological effects, including antibacterial, antitumor, and anticancer properties, are attributed to Schiff bases' azomethine functionality (-HC=N-). It has also been shown that these biological effects are increasing in their metal (ii) complexes.

Currently, a significant amount of coordination science research is focused on the synthesis of compounds with bioactivities, due to the wide variety of metals that can be synthesised and the flexibility with which their organic ligands can alter the reactivity and structure of metal complexes as a whole. There are several factors that may influence the biological activity of transition & non-transition metal complexes, including the type, amount, and isomers of ligands and molecules. Specialized therapeutic metal complexes may be created by understanding the factors that impact biological function. Non-transition and transition metal complexes derived from 'Sb' continue to be the subject of much study across the globe. There are many different types of cancer, all of which are caused by abnormal cell development and have become the biggest cause of mortality in the world.

Chemotherapy's severe side effects have been countered for years by attempting to prevent the production of production of reactive oxygen species species. It has thus become increasingly important to develop "antioxidant and anticancer" compounds that scavenge free radicals as well

as an action Oxygen species while killing tumour cells, reducing or avoiding chemotherapy side effects, despite the fact that platinum-based medicines are given to 70% of all cancer patients, nephrotoxicity and resistance are the most common adverse effects. Molecular chemotherapeutics that are not based on platinum will have their cytotoxicity lowered as a result of future study.

both thiophene and C_6H_6 have a significant bioisosteric link, and both are relevant to the dye industry. Consequently, while studying new series of potential medications, it is worth synthesising thio-derivatives since they demonstrate fascinating and advantageous features. Carboxylic group, imidazole nitrogen atoms, and amino groups are major donor sites for metal adsorption in Lhis, which is a well-known heterocyclic nitrogen-containing amino acid system, and its absence may lead to pulmonary and chronic renal disorders.

Hydrocarbons abound in both natural gas and oil. Hydrocarbon usage is a major subject in the quest for long-term and cost-effective global carbon reduction. Oxidation has been deemed the most important phase in the process. Alcohols and ketones have a strong oxidation-reduction interaction in liquids, where they may be oxidised with H_2O_2 or oxygen. C-H bond activation is very difficult since hydrocarbons are chemically inert. This means that activating C-H bonds needs severe conditions, such as increased pressure and temperature.

Alkanes ($C_6H_{12}O$ and C_6H_{12}) must be combined with oxygen (O_2) in the presence of KA oil. Cyclohexanol and cyclohexanone are produced via the air oxidation of C_6H_{12} , which is a prominent technique of alkane oxidation. The existing process is plagued by a lack of ability, poor yields, less conversion, and the formation of environmentally polluting gases and wastes. $C_6H_{12}O$ and C_6H_{12} (KA-oil) is a popular issue in industry because of its selective reactivity to C_6H_{12} . C_6H_{12} and $C_6H_{12}O$ and C_6H_{12} are created every year for the production of Nylon 6 polymers across the globe. To convert cyclohexane to cyclohexanol and/or cyclohexanone, commercial procedures employ co-basis homogen catalysts (4 percent conversion and 70-80 percent action with getting adipic acid from the yield).

As a result of C_6H_{12} 's high effective number of H-C bonds, greater pressure and temperature are required. Reaction action impact may be improved if the catalyst can oxidise cyclohexane under moderate conditions (the cyclohexane boiling point). Nitric acid, a very hostile catalyst used in

the following oxidation phase, is used in the oxidation of cyclohexane." Catalytic processes that are both environmentally friendly and cost-effective are required for greener materials and processes. To oxidise alkanes, for example, the catalyst must be highly selective, the rate of material conversion into the product must be high, and materials and solvents must be as environmentally friendly as possible. Several processes, including those involving OH or -O-OH and reactive metal ion species, have been described by Fenton, who used iron (II) salts in an acidic aqueous solution of hydrogen peroxide as an oxidant. Cyclohexane oxidation drew the interest and attention of scientists to improve catalysts for oxidising cyclohexane under mild conditions, and it was reported that metal complexes with metalloporphyrin

Schiff bases are extensively employed as ligands in coordination chemistry. Schiff ligands with an imine group ($-RC=N-$) are formed via the condensation of an amine with an active aldehyde. Flexible, accessible, and capable of a wide range of densities and functions, they are ideal for a wide range of applications. Another advantage of Schiff is that it allows for fine control over both the stereoisomers of metallic centres and the amount of metal ions present in homo and heteropolynuclear complexes, as well as the kind of donor atoms. Metal complexes that are useful in bioinorganic chemistry, catalysis, transport, and separation processes may be made using Schiff bases because of their properties. A chemical compound with a wide variety of biological properties, Schiff bases are known as Schiff bases. Chemotherapeutic Schiff base development is now a hot topic in the medical chemistry community. In addition to their anticancer and antibacterial effects, Schiff bases have been shown to have herbicidal, antifungal, and antibacterial action in several studies.

Antibacterial, antifungal, and genotoxic effects have been discovered in Schiff bases synthesised from various amine and carbonyl derivatives. Relative locations in Schiff bases of the donor atoms may impact the stereochemistry, as well as the quantity of metal ions, in homo & heteropolynuclear complexes, of metallic nuclei. Metal complexes important in bioinorganic chemistry, catalysis, encapsulation, transport, and separation may be synthesised using Schiff bases because of these advantages. A chemical molecule known as Schiff base exhibits a variety of biological properties. There has been an increase in the attention of medicinal chemists in the creation of a new Schiff base. Many studies have examined the biological features of 'Schiff', such as its cancer-fighting, fungicide-killing, and herbicide qualities.

The important role of Schiff bases in Co-ordination chemistry is one of the most fascinating topics in Co-ordination chemistry because of their direct synthesis and ease of variation. With a carbonyl molecule and an amine, the majority of Schiff bases can be easily synthesised using simple synthetic methods. The use of Schiff bases as ligands in coordination chemistry is widespread. As a starting point for the design of a wide range of ligand systems with precisely controlled binding to metal ions in coordination chemistry, Schiff base ligands are indispensable. Coordination chemistry relies heavily on 'Sb' metal compounds, one of the most meticulously prepared classes of molecules. There are numerous Schiff base complexes being studied for biological and pharmacological purposes, some of which have been commercially successful and are now being used in research.

Reversible coupling of oxygen, chemical reaction in hydrogenation of alkenes, photochromic nature, and ability to interact with some harmful metals have all been found in Schiff base metal complexes. Molecular drugs with metal ions in their backbones have had a major impact on medicine. Despite the fact that these elements are present in extremely low concentrations in living organisms, they play a significant role. Many people are interested in the biological and pharmacological properties that 1, 2, 4-triazoles have. There are numerous biological actions of 1, 2, 4-triazole and its derivatives, including antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant, anti-malarial, and anti-leishmanial medicines. " In light of the above and our continued interest in this field, Copper (II), Cobalt (II), Nickel (II), and Zinc (II) complexes containing the Schiff base ligand generated from 5-amino-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol and 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzaldehyde were produced, spectroscopically described, thermally studied, and biologically active."

There has been extensive research into the biological efficacy of transition metal compounds derived from Schiff bases, and it appears that Schiff bases play an important role in many different enzyme activities, including the exchange of enzymes with amino or aromatic aldehydes deposited on an underlayer. When an enzyme, such as a lysine residue, adds a 1^o-amine to a functional set of substrates to create "Schiff base," it is one of the most important kinds of catalytic processes. Biological active sites can be modelled using complexes of transition metals with various oxidation states, which are important in bioinorganic chemistry research. However, zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO) are of particular interest because they can be used in numerous applications. Human and animal cosmetics and health care products are frequently made using these ingredients because

they can be prepared quickly, cheaply and safely for both species. Is one of the most serious issues in science today, and it's been broken down into its various components and subcomponents. In the context of protein folding, the ability to accept co-ordination numbers 6, 5, or 4 with ease. They can be used in a variety of industries, including electronics, biotechnology, and energy production. More than a few applications are possible with heterogeneous catalysts in the presence of remediation of atmospheric pollution. A few examples of fields include: slicing; thin films; pigments; disinfection; and antibacterial activity. The letters M and MO can be used in a variety of ways. Nanoparticles underwent morphological and dimensional changes. There has been a lot of attention given to the study of biologically significant metal ions in terms of the detection method. Developments have been made in the field of Zn²⁺ ion inquiry or capteur. Zn²⁺ has a special interest because it is a crucial element and the second most abundant trace element on Earth. It's the most common metal ion in humans.

"Metal-chelate Schiff base complexes have remained one of the most important stereo chemical models in main group as well as transition metal coordination chemistry due to its preparative accessibility, variety, and stretchability, we recently published a study on the synthesis, spectroscopic characterization, and antimicrobial studies of a series of polydentate ligands as well as their copper (II) complexes, and found that the 8-[1-(2-)-[1',2'-dimethylamino]benzoic acid" (Garnovskii et al., 1993, p. 1). The ligand 8- [1-(4 amino-phenylimino)-ethyl]-7 hydroxy-chromen-2 one (HL1complexationphotophysical)'s characteristics are currently being researched, according to EL Husseiny et al. Due to Coumarin's remarkable photophysical characteristics, such as a high Stokes poste and visible excitation and emission, it was selected as the fluorophore. Co-ordination science of free ligand compounds created and characterised using analytical methods is also the goal of this research, which is aimed at determining the organic ligand's co-ordination mode and form of its metal complexes. Infrared, ultra-violet, 1H, and 13C-NMR techniques were used to get this data. Fluorescence results from the system's wide range of chemistry are a reflection of this.

Figure 2.5 “The photophysical properties of the ligand 8- [1-(4- amino-phenylimino)-ethyl]-7- hydroxy-chromen-2-one (HL1 complexation)”

The cleavage efficiency of binuclear complexes is superior to that of mononuclear ones. The anticancer properties of Schiff bases and certain metals have been shown to be effective in the treatment of animal tumours. Metal complexes that can be used in biotechnology & medicine are being studied because of the need to generate innovative metal complexes. Despite their widespread usage, cisplatin & carboplatin are chemotherapy drugs that have a multitude of side effects. As a consequence, we're working hard to create chemotherapy drugs with as little side effects as possible. A DNA N atom base is used in covalent binding to replace the complexes' labile ligand, and non-covalent DNA conversation occurs between complex formation, electrostatic binding of cationic metal complexes in the groove (surface), and groove (surface) binding of these complexes in the major or minor grooves of the DNA helix. As "new therapeutic agents" and because of their photochemical features, which produce a possible DNA tube and confirm, this damage may cause a range of pathogenic modifications in living organisms. Using basic examination, molar conductance, ultraviolet and infrared spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), and magnetic investigations, we synthesised and investigated novel compounds derived from butanedione monoxime and 3, 3-diaminobenzidine

in this study. There has also been work done in the area of thermal research. These chemicals were tested for DNA binding, DNA breakage, antibacterial and antifungal properties.

Synthesis of ligand and its complexes

Figure 2.6 Synthesis of ligand and its complexes

In addition to advances in bioinorganic chemistry, there has been a surge in interest in macrocyclic compounds. When it comes to chemistry, the macrocycle-containing moieties are highly sought after for their versatility as ligands and their ability to coordinate in both neutral and deprotonated forms (due to the availability of several potential donor atoms). According to Valencia and colleagues (2001), It is thought that many transition metal ions in biological systems serve as enzymes or carriers when exposed to macrocyclic ligand environments. As a consequence of important research in this area, simple models of physiologically occurring metalloenzymes may be built. The $-C=N$ bond's behaviour is greatly influenced by the amine

moiety's structure, which controls the efficiency of correlation and may contain structural characteristics that modulate the steric crowding around the coordination. Many studies have shown that the -C=N group has biological significance. In the last decade, there has been a surge in interest in the coordination chemistry of Schiff bases synthesised from heterocyclic carbaldehyde. Sm (II) reagent was used to test the stability of N₄ tetradentate Schiff bases, and the results showed that these Schiff bases are stable in the presence of the pyrrole ring, which is capable of coordinating to the Sm (II) ion.

Berube et al. In response to these findings, we synthesised and characterised new symmetrical "Sb' N, N/bis (pyrro-2-carbaldehyde) "ethylenediamine," and M molecules.

Structure of the ligand.

Figure 2.7 Structure of ligand

For Schiff bases and their pyridine derivatives, antibacterial, antifungal, and anticancer characteristics have been shown to be true. H-bonding between the azomethine N atom and the active centres of cell components may be used as a mechanism of action. When complexed with a M ion, Schiff-bases contain at least one functional group that forms a six- or five-membered ring. Metal chelates derived from Schiff bases have been identified for almost a century. Chelating Schiff-bases may be generated by altering the kind and position of the functional group, as well as by including various substituents into the reactive molecules. According to studies, the biological activity of the ligand is enhanced when the transition metal is incorporated into Schiff bases, while the cytotoxic effects of M ions and L on host are reduced.

A rise in metal chelate concentration increases their activity because of the impact of M ions on routine cell activities. Biochemical, analytical, and antibacterial reagents are increasingly relying on Schiff-base complexes. Oxygen and Nitrogen donor sites on azomethine-N and

benzimidazole-N3 tetradentately connect the L to M ions. As part of this research, the Schiff base was created by condensing trimethoprim and trimethyl orthoformate, which were then combined to generate the pyrimidine-4-ylformimidate Schiff base. Analysis of ligand metal-complexes was done using physicochemical and spectroscopic methods. Spectroscopy was used to investigate the impact of gamma radiation on the substances in question.

Ethyl N-2-amino-5-(3,4,5-trimethylbenzyl)pyrimidine-4-ylformimidate.

Figure 2.8 Ethyl N-2-amino-5-(3,4,5-trimethylbenzyl) pyrimidine-4-ylformimidate

Schiff base ligands have been extensively studied, although coordinated ligands have received less attention since they can form stable compounds with most M ions. 'Sb' ligands are incredibly important and explored. Metal ions may alter and enhance the activity of biologically active molecules when they attach to them. The use of 'Sb' compounds containing O and N donor ligands to bioinorganic systems has piqued the curiosity of chemists. These compounds are widely recognised. Citral and naphthofuran-2-carbohydrazide combine to generate 'Sb', which has chelation properties. Stronger physiologically active molecules and a better understanding of their structure might be achieved by using other M ions, such as Co, Ni, Copper, Cadmium, Zinc, and Mercury (ii). There were several tests conducted on all of the compounds that were created. They were all evaluated for biocidal properties.

Suggested structure for Co(II), Ni(II), Cd(II), Zn(II) or Hg(II) complexes.

Figure 2.9 Suggested structure for Co (ii), Ni (II), Cd (II), Zn (II), and Hg (II), complexes

An amino and carbonyl molecule are used to synthesise Schiff bases, a well-studied set of L's that connect to M ions through azomethine-N. The N=C link is critical for biological activity in several azomethine derivatives, which have been demonstrated to have significant anti-cancer and antimalarial properties. Since the 1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives have a high degree of aromaticity in their ring system, they exhibit interesting biological activity, which is useful in vivo and often harmful for increased backbone, including species. However, when you add a variety of utilitarian to this ring, you obtain molecules with distinct characteristics. While some antibacterial sulfonamides are no longer utilised therapeutically but have historical value, the most famous example is the "5-amino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole-derivatives". It is also possible to study the chemistry and applications of these new Schiff bases and thiadiazoles derivatives by coordinating them to various metal ion moieties. As a result, the 1, 3, 4-thiadiazole structural activity link inquiry may be expanded in the near future. As a follow-up to our work on transition metal complexes, we provide the synthesis and characterization of new compounds similar to "2N-salicylidene-5-(p-nitro phenyl)-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole.". In addition, the produced complexes are subjected to preliminary antimicrobial testing in vitro. It was not necessary to purify any of the catalyst, starting ingredients, or solutes since they were all commercially available and used.

Five new metal compounds derived from '2N-salicylidene-5-(p-nitro phenyl)-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole', HL, were devised and produced in an alkaline medium using metallic ions vanadium (ii), cobalt (ii), rhodium (iii), palladium (ii) and aurum (iii). FT-IR, UV-Visible, mass, ^1H & ^{13}C -NMR, magnetic, and conductivity tests are used to characterise the compounds quantitatively and qualitatively. There are only two compounds that are neither square-pyramidal or tetra-hedral in form, Vanadium (ii) and Co (ii), which were synthesised as monomeric structures with the metal core medium. The discovery of complexes was made possible because to early antibacterial in vitro screening.

In large set and t-M co-ordination research, Schiff base complexes are an important stereochemical class because of their simple manufacturing method and structural variation. Drug-transition metal interactions are a hot topic in bioinorganic chemistry research. Coordination with M ions and inhibition of metalloenzyme production are known to have a role in the actions of a number of drugs. In the biological process of drug absorption, metal ions may be crucial. Sb's and compounds have been studied. When Sb's are administered as M compounds rather than as free ligands, their anticancer activity is boosted, which makes them potential anticancer treatments. Phenyl derivatives of hydrazine-pyrrole-2-carboxaldehydes, hydrazine-furan-2-carboxaldehydes, and hydrazine-thiophene-2-carboxaldehydes have been produced and analysed, as well as their mixed complexes with Cobalt II, Copper II, and Nickel II (Chohan, 2008). Not only are human and fungus cells molecularly similar; resistance is also a major obstacle in the development of safe and effective antifungals, as is well known.

Many diseases may be treated using benzimidazole derivatives, which has a broad spectrum of biological activities and therapeutic applications. Their antibacterial, fungicidal, analgesic/anti-inflammatory and anti-amoebic properties make them ideal for treating a wide range of ailments. Pyrimidine, pyrazoline, and thiazole chemicals all fall under this umbrella. A number of other anticancer medicines, including "4-amino-thiazolidine, 4-oxothiazolidine, 4-fluorobenzylidene, and cycloalkylidene," have been connected to 2-substituted benzimidazoles with a carboxylic or chlorine group at the 5-position. A new molecular design with significant biological activity was then discovered as a result of all the surveys (Osipyan et al.). Benzimidazoles are versatile ligands that may take the form of metal compounds and function in a variety of chemical reactions. Studies on benzimidazole complexes include anti-amoebic, protein tyrosine

phosphatase inhibition, anti-proliferative agents, antibacterial and antimalarial properties. 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole complexes, on the other hand, have been extensively studied and are one of the most sought-after compounds by pharmaceutical companies because of their wide range of biological characteristics. Antiplasmodial and insecticidal characteristics of several benzimidazoles have led to their usage as antiplasmodial agents. The 2-position heterocycles of substituted benzimidazoles have been proven to result in strong anticancer medicines in a number of carcinoma cell lines, as shown by current research. The MCF-7 cell line, colon carcinoma, laryngeal carcinoma, hepatocellular carcinoma, and neuroblastoma have all been demonstrated to be highly cytotoxic to 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole complexes.

Thiosulfate, a significant contaminant, is produced by the printing, paper, and textile industries. The detection and degradation of this substance need a sensitive, fast, low-cost, and analytical approach. For example, iodometry is a useful method, although it is time-consuming and unreliable. Electrochemical analytical methods are a great option since they are quick, easy, and inexpensive. Noble M-based electrodes, such as Pt and Au, were used to thoroughly investigate the electro catalytic oxidation process by thiosulfate. In light of the higher price, changing activity, and non-linear phenomena displayed during the electrical interaction of thiosulfate on the Pt overside and the leaching of gold by thiosulfate anion. Several researchers have used chemically modified electrodes as strong tools for synthesis and electro-catalysis since Lane, Hubbard, Murray, and Miller first developed them. Analyze and find out. Electrodes with metal hexacyanoferrate films are commonly studied for their high electronic-catalyst nature toward diverse activities, such as "hydrazine, ascorbic acid, and thiosulfate oxidation," due to the ease of their manufacture method, lower cost, and less expensive nature. There are several different kinds of carbon that may be used as a conductive and chemically inert support material. For example, it has a wide surface area, excellent adsorption properties, and good chemical and physical properties. Carbon paste electrodes were first reported by Adams in 1958. (Adams, 1958). A number of researchers have been motivated to actively improve these electrodes because of their practical advantages, such as their ease in manufacture and regeneration, their usefulness in evaluating different modifiers, and their excellent electric properties among chemically modified electrodes. As a suitable and soft electrode material for thiosulfate studies, this work uses a C-paste-Ni 'Sb' complex altered electrode. X-ray diffraction had previously shown that the (N, N'-bisalicylidenepropylenetriamine) Ni (II) complex exists in one crystal, and

the modified carbon paste electrode was tested using scanning electron microscopy, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, cyclic voltammetry, and chronoamperometry. Following adding thiosulfate to the solution, a well-defined Ni (III)/Ni (II) redox pair and a linear dependence of catalytic current were detected in alkaline medium. The electrode's sensitivity, selectivity, and stability make it ideal for this application. They used commercially available complexes that had no further purification steps. While Sigma Aldrich provided N-N'bis (3-aminopropyl)amine and salicylaldehyde, Fluka supplied all of the solvents, including ethanol and dichloromethane. Fluka supplied nickel acetate tetrahydro and sodium hydroxide, while Merck supplied analytical grade $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$.

Schiff base complexes have been used as anticancer drugs and have a wide range of antibacterial activity against a wide range of bacteria, and they are becoming increasingly important in the pharmaceutical, dye, and plastic industries, as well as liquid-crystal technologies and mechanistic investigations of medications used in pharmacology, biochemistry, and physiology." Certain drugs have a greater degree of effect when delivered as metal chelates and may inhibit tumour growth. Because of their intricacy and complications, transition metal binuclear metal complexes (containing many Schiff bases) have attracted people's interest. Cisplatin is a frequent anticancer medicine, notably for ovarian and testicular cancers, because of its role as a biological model, organic reaction catalyst, and component in the development of newly developed materials. In spite of the fact that chemotherapy has a 90% success rate in treating testicular cancer, there are substantial drawbacks to using cisplatin. A number of systemic symptoms, such as nausea and nephrotoxicity, have changed these disadvantages. Non-platinum-based metal treatments have been revolutionised by late 3d transition metal ions, in particular. A list of endogenously compatible elements includes Copper II, Ni II, Co II, Fe II and Zinc II. Vanadium is not one of them (ii). We're particularly interested in the coordination chemistry of electron-rich first-row transitions. These include copper and nickel, as well as vanadium. There is significantly greater structural variety and therapeutic capabilities in Ms from the centre and left of the transition metal row, which are 5, 4, or six co-ordinate compounds of metals such as Copper and Nickel. Copper is a redox active metal with antibacterial and anticancer properties that is involved in several biological processes. Cu molecules preferentially penetrate cancer cell membranes, resulting in the accumulation of copper in tumours. Strong antifungal and cytotoxic capabilities against human pathogenic bacteria are attributed to "the nickel complexes of Schiff base

derivatives," particularly compartments. The insulin-stimulating properties of vanadyl 'Sb' complexes have been widely studied in biological research.

Since transition M compounds with Sb ligands are useful in medicine, researchers have focused on synthesising and characterising these compounds throughout the last decade. In light of these findings, the aim of this study is to use tetradentate to build novel binuclear Copper(II), Ni(ii), and Va(ii) molecules. Researchers used a variety of techniques to describe the binuclear Schiff base complexes made from 3,3'-dihydroxybenzidine, glyoxal/diacetyl, and 2-aminophenol, as well as elements analysis, molar conductance, infrared, electronic spectra, and cyclic voltammetry. They also investigated the Schiff base ligand and its complexes for their ability to cleave DNA.

Because Schiff bases are stable in both oxidation and reduction, they have a unique capacity to bind L's in the biggest group and T-M co-ordination chemistry because imidazole L's are borderline Lb's. Intermolecular H bonding and proton transfer equilibrium play a critical role in the Sb's biology. Other applications include increasing the dissolvability of heterogeneous or homogeneous catalysts, as well as introducing chirality into the substrate or changing metal-centered electrical characteristics. In order for a person to have a life, a variety of biological processes involving T-ms are necessary. In a variety of scenarios, Ms may coordinate with proteins' O- or N-terminals, and they play an important role in the conformational and structural mapping of bioactive compounds. The relevance of 'Sb' compounds in providing natural models for M sites, which include "metal-lo-proteins and metallo-enzymes," has piqued attention in the field of coordination sciences. Aromatics, dyes, agrochemicals and medicines are all products of indole and its derivatives. M-complexes linked to artificial and natural O carriers increasingly utilise tetradentate and tridentate Schiff base complexes. Copper complexes with a tridentate 'Sb', particularly those with dimeric units, are bioinorganic model compounds. Chemicals derived from indole have received a lot of attention in recent years. Intriguing biochemical features include antibacterial and analgesic properties. For the development of chemotherapeutic medications, the ability of metallodrugs to cleave DNA is essential. Many transition M complexes have been shown to enhance DNA breaking because of their redox properties. A work on 'Sb' metal complex systems was recently published by our group. Synthesis, personality,

antibacterial and DNA cleavage study of mono-nuclear 'Sb' ligand compounds derived from "indole-3-carboxaldehyde and glycylglycine" are covered in this article.

Inorganic cation sensors based on polyaza macrocycles with big holes have gained interest in recent years. Their flexibility and the huge quantity of donor electrons in a cyclic configuration make them good hosts for complexes of ions. As an example, heavy metal ions, which are very effective enzyme inhibitors, are often used as spectrophotometric analytical reagents in a variety of biological processes. A healthy existence requires the separation and determination of environmental sources of dangerous metal ions such as "mercury, lead and cadmium". Despite the fact that oxygen, sulphur, and nitrogen make up the majority of macrocyclic compounds, the majority of macrocyclic compounds used in solvent extraction were oxygen-based. A number of methods have been documented for the production of big polyaza macrocyclic molecules. Nitrogen atoms are protected and activated during the cyclization phase by N-tosyl groups, which are often utilised in synthetic procedures. An N-tosylation condensation process happens in DMF when a base is present, and the appropriate ditosylate ester/halide is used. However, the removal of the N-tosyl groups needs severe conditions and isn't always easy in these reactions. Another cyclization technique employs the template ring closure creation of the cyclic di- or tetra Schiff base. Because of its simplicity, this approach may be complicated when the template cation does not align with all of the nitrogen atoms in the nitrogen-containing rings. When the cyclic "Sb" is reduced and the template ion is removed, there are various issues. A non-template method to the synthesis of macrocyclic poly- 'Sb' has also been studied. Without the requirement to remove a metal ion, this method usually produced a polymeric material in addition to the cyclization reactant. To transport various M ions from the aqueous to the organic phases of liquidliquid extraction systems, we employed a non-template approach to make two novel macrocyclic 'Sb's: (ii) and (iii).

As antibiotic resistance in microorganisms continues to evolve, it is critical to develop new antibiotic classes that ultimately target the pathogen's lipid layer and other elements of the pathogen life cycle. ' Metal complexes, which are known to form stable compounds with little transition, may be one example of a putative class of physiologically active chemicals. Modern coordination chemistry relies heavily on M ions, 'Sb' and their structural counterparts, including acyclic and cyclic aliphatic amines. It is critical to develop new antibiotic classes that "target the

lipoid layer of organisms" as well as other aspects of pathogen life cycles, given the ongoing development of antibiotic resistance in microbes. One of these kinds of biologically active materials may be M materials. In today's inorganic chemistry, ligating compounds such as acyclic and cyclic imines and their structural equivalents, such as Sb, are important. It is essential to develop new antibiotic classes that ultimately "target the lipoid layer of organisms" as well as other aspects of pathogen life cycles because of the constant development of antibiotic resistance in bacteria. One of these chemical classes, the M complexes, may have physiological effects. Modern inorganic research relies heavily on 'Sb's and structural equivalents like ligating compounds like acyclic and cyclic imines. Research on transition metal complexes is encouraged by the current emphasis on the synthesis of novel Sb's and their M complexes by many modern researchers.

Using "4-amino-5-mercapto3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole/4-amino-3-ethyl-5-mercapto1,2,4-triazole and 5-nitrofurfuralde," the researchers produced, characterised, heated, and tested for antibacterial activity Schiff base compounds of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and Zn^{+} . The sample Sb and M complexes produced here are the first of their kind and have never been reported before.

Due to their simple synthesis, broad range of applications, and ability to undergo structural alterations, Sbl's have played an important role in the development of science since the late 1800s. M-complexes of these ligands are commonly utilised. Many organometallic and bioinert chemical compounds have been synthesised using S-base ligands and their M complexes. Metal complexes containing porphyrin, salen, and phthalocyanine ligands have been studied as viable alternatives to enzymes as inorganic mimics of enzymes. The Schiff base is famous for allowing geometrical cavity control for host-guest interaction, as well as lipophilicity modification that allows for excellent selectivity, sensitivity, and stability for a specific metal ion." According to current scientific thinking, azomethine linkage is responsible for many biochemical actions such as those involved in the progression of cancer and in the prevention of bacterial and viral infection. Hetero-homo-geneous catalysis for organic molecule oxidation and polymerization have all been linked to these complexes, as have chemical analysis, oxygen absorption and transport, and insecticides. Scientists are intrigued by T-metal complexes containing O and N donor Sbls. The metals in these complexes function as catalysts for chemical reactions. There has been an increase in the prevalence of antimicrobial diseases, although they are still difficult to

diagnose clinically. More and more diverse kinds of antibiotic and fungal medications have been discovered throughout time, particularly in the past decade or so. At the time, antimicrobial activity may be found in antibacterial sulfa drugs, nitrofuranes and penicillins, as well as antifungal treatments like fluconazole, ketoconazole and miconazole and amphotericin B. Antibacterial and antifungal medications have come a long way, but there is still a long way to go for most antimicrobial drugs. Antifungal amphotericin B is often utilised in clinical settings because of its significant nephrotoxicity. Fungi infections aren't necessarily confined to the skin, although they may be. The number of persons who have died as a result of life-threatening systemic fungal infections has increased significantly. Primary reasons for this increase include a greater number of people who are at risk for infection due to their ageing, having had a majority of their organs removed, being on immunosuppressive therapy, or having HIV/AIDS, cancer treatment, or having solid-organ and hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. Sb' compounds using glyoxalic acid-derived thiosemicarbazide have been reported to exhibit antifungal action, and some Sb's have been identified as having this potential. A new Schiff base compound, H2L, has been synthesised and its spectroscopic and in vitro antibacterial properties have been studied.

For the separation of metal species in solution, chelate extraction is a very effective analytical approach. Solvent origin techniques are among the investigated methods for the synthesis and recovery of various metal ions from various sources due to their simplicity, speed, and extensive reach. Solvent origin methods include. A process known as "solvent extraction of metal chelate complexes" has been in use for decades. Chromium and Cu are both essential and detrimental to a wide range of cellular functions. Trace quantities of Cu and Cr are becoming more important since environmental pollution is becoming a hot topic. Because of the extremely low concentrations of some Ms in H₂O, a direct assessment is practically impossible without pre-concentration and separation, but these metals can be accurately and quickly determined in natural waters and wastewaters using "flame and graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry and spectrophotometric techniques," The most widely used ones for the separation and preconcentration of trace quantities are liquid-liquid extraction, precipitation, sorption, solid phase methods, and chelating resins. Separation and preconcentration are frequently required, and one advantage of solvent extraction is that both can be accomplished in one step. As a result of these factors, metal recovery from aqueous phases in the system selected has high distributions, coefficients, and pH sensitivity. Chelating agents include crown ethers, Sb's,

oximes, amines, and various phosphine oxides. Infrared, mass spectrometry, and elemental analyses were used to characterise the ligand. A novel extraction reagent with specific selectivity at varying pH levels may be possible because of the O and N donor atoms in this structure.

Synthesis of Schiff base

Figure 2.10 Synthesis of Schiff base

Schiff base compounds have been shown to have both biological and modelling applications. Pathogenic fungi have been demonstrated to be more active when M ions, such as Cu, Ni, and Fe, are combined with these chemicals. People's fascination in Schiff's base metal complexes continues to grow. An comprehension of and ability to simulate the mechanisms governing reversible O₂ binding and activation in various "natural oxygen transport systems and mono- and dioxygenases" depends on this point of view. When it came to "metalloorganic hybrid materials," Schiff bases were regarded one of the most promising classes of chelating agents. As analytical reagents, SB complexes are becoming popular because they make it simple and affordable to evaluate a wide range of chemical and inorganic components. Solid complexes are made possible by the strong affinity of Schiff bases for chelate transition metal ions. Coordination activite of a novel and unique H₂L "Sb" with several binding sites for Cr (iii), Mn, Iron, Co, Ni, Cu, and Zn ions is the focus of this work. It was also tested for antibacterial activity against a wide range of bacteria and fungi to establish its heat resistance.

Hydrozone compounds have been shown to have a wide range of beneficial properties in the fight against a wide range of pathogens and cancers, as well as the prevention of heart disease due to their cardioprotective properties and their ability to reduce inflammation and analgesia. This class of compounds includes ANHN, CHA, and is essential to the development of pharmaceuticals. Several researchers have studied hydrazones' biological effects, and the results

have been published. It has been shown that hydrazone derivatives, including 2-thiazoyl, have antiinflammatory, antiviral and antioxidant effects. Metal complexes of hydrazones are also known to have pharmacological effects. Complexes of hydrazone derivatives, for example, have been shown to be highly toxic to human cancer cell lines. " These ligands' ability to chelate diverse T-M ions is due to their own (N-C) and two (O-C) groups, that are electron donors. To avoid corrosion, Hydrazones include two N atoms and an imine link, which operate as active adhesion sites for liquids. In previous research, the highest percentage inhibition effectiveness was reported in several novel hydrazone derivatives on copper corrosion in a Saline media. Bioactive bisatins have been shown to target cancer cells in a number of ways and combinations. Many anticancer medicines may be made using the pyrrole moiety of different "heterocyclic rings on site 3 of indolin-2-," and the effects of gamma irradiation on the complexes of ruthenium (II), palladium (II), vanadium (II), and mercury (II) have been described.

The investigation of synthetic metal compounds included the use of elemental analyses, molar capacitance, magnet charges, far-infrared, ¹H-NMR, UV-Visi, and thermal techniques. In the case of "unirradiated and irradiated metal complexes, spectral, thermal, powder X-ray diffraction patterns, and surface morphological investigations were carried out; the energies of the highest occupied molecular orbital, energies of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital, energy gap, absolute electron affinity, the chemical potential, Pi, the absolute hardness, and the softness for the same compounds were calculated using molecular modelling structures; the synthesis

Figure 2.11 2-phenylamino-N-(thiophene-2-yl) methylene) acetohydrazide ligand

We know that Schiff base complexes are important in group and T-M co-ordination research because of the way they are created and formed throughout the sample preparation procedure. When administered as M-complexes, Sb's have the potential to be an effective anticancer medication, outperforming the free ligand in terms of efficacy. The Sb's of 4-aminoantipyrene (4-AAP), as well as their complexes, have anticancer and antiviral properties. The Sb's of (4-AAP) have the advantages of having 2-potential donor properties and are to form 3-types of metal ion compounds: (i) chelates that use both donor atoms, (ii) amine salts that use only the amino nitrogen atoms, and (iii) two types of complex Schiff bases have been published, and with this knowledge in mind, we decided to investigate the synthesis of Copper (II) and Zinc (II) complexes using Schiff bases made from the condensation of 1-phenyl-2,3-dimethyl-4-aminopyrazol-5-one(4-aminoantipyrene) and 2-amino-3-methylbutanoic acid. Because this ligand system contains both nitrogen and oxygen donor sites, the carboxylic oxygen atom, the This research include DNA binding and cleavage studies as well as the structural features of the RNA. Bangalore Genei contributed the DNA for this experiment (India). "Molecule living matter level agarose and ethidium bromide were provided by Sigma, and deionized, sonicated triply distilled water was used to prepare a Tris (hydroxymethyl) aminomethane–HCl (Tris–HCl) buffer solution." EAC cells were graciously provided by the Amala Cancer Research Facility in Trissur, India. The mice were infected intraperitoneally once a week with 10⁶ cells per animal in order to maintain them alive.

Figure 2.12 Outline synthesis of ligand

Recently, there has been a lot of interest in developing macrocyclic compounds and their salts for a variety of applications. One example is chelating agents for the selective separation, withdrawal, as well as subsequent measurement of trace and ultra-trace heavy metal ions in complex matrices, which are becoming increasingly popular. Host/guest chemistry and supramolecular electron transfer have been shown using electron-deficient moieties inserted into the backbone of nanomeric macrocyclic complex species. Californian phenols known as metacyclophenanes have shown great promise in the development of molecular sensors that recognise ions and small chemical molecules, according to the University of California.

According to Chawla and Pathak, the addition of "calixarenes to methylene blue" greatly increased the rate of sensitised photooxygenation of 4,5-diphenylimidozolones when exposed to light (2000). The significant influence of calixarene addition is due to the length of the chains of alkyl groups connected to the calixarene. "When comparing calix arenes to calyx arenes and calyx arenes belonging to the same function group R, the effect was larger in calix arenes." Bis amides were created by condensing sequearic acid and its esters with aliphatic or aromatic amines, while 2-alkylthio-4-chloro-5-methyl-N-(1,2-dihydroxycyclobuta[e][1,2,4]-N-(1,2-dihydroxycyclobuta[e][1,2,4]-N-(1,2-dihydroxycyclobuta[e][1,2,4]-N-(Sequearic acid was cyclocondensed with amino guanidine in a 1:1 molar ratio to produce triazin-3-ylbenzenesulfonamide, which was then used to synthesise benzenesulfonamide. These medications demonstrated anti-tumor action in vitro when tested against the HOP-62 non-small cell lung cancer cell line." Recently, a number of nanomeric compounds, as well as a number of their metal salts, have been discovered and described. Therefore, I am testing the moluscicidal abilities of the compounds produced; (ii) investigating the redox characteristics of selected compounds for use as selective reagents in stripping voltammetry for mercury detection in wastewater; and (iii) evaluating the effectiveness of the compounds produced.

In the recent decade, multidrug-resistant "Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria" have penetrated hospitals all over the globe, producing nosocomial infections and causing hospital acquired diseases. Because of drug resistance, researchers are looking for novel antimicrobial medications and new microbial targets to intervene and avoid the dangers posed by these life-threatening illnesses. "Nosocomial infections, including such hospital-acquired methicillin-

resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* and biofilm formers" have a particularly difficult time being treated. Because hazardous bacteria are becoming more resistant to currently available antibiotics, there is an urgent need for the development of new and effective antimicrobial treatments to combat this threat. Therefore, success in developing antimicrobial compounds that are distinct from those found in traditional antibiotics is critical for treating infectious diseases that are recognised for their chronic nature and inability to respond to conventional antibiotics, both of which can result in death if not treated promptly. According to research, Schiff bases exhibit features such as antibiotic, antitubercular, antimicrobicidal, antibiotic, antiviral, antimalarial, and anticancer activity. They are a significant chemical because of the wide range of biological activities and industrial uses that they have to provide. Aside from that, they're also employed as a starting point for the production of heterocyclic compounds. Ketoacyl–acyl carrier protein synthase (KAS) is an important target in the battle against multidrug-resistant Gram-positive infections, according to the World Health Organization. Extensive research has gone into the production of peptide bonds and Sb's that might be used as potential antibacterial treatments "against Gram positive and Gram negative" illnesses that target the KAS protein. Because of their ability to attach oxygen to oxidation and reduction processes, Sb' and their M-complexes have piqued the interest of scientists for a longer period of time. This is due to their ability to damage DNA. Because of the ability of their metal complexes to scavenge free radicals, they displayed significant antibacterial activity in laboratory tests.

Some researchers discovered that carbonyl Sb' N-aryl thiosemicarbazones were more effective against MRSA than vancomycin at half the concentration of vancomycin after synthesising and physiologically screening the compounds. Early research also revealed that one of the thiazolidinedione-5-acetic acid amide forms, thiazolidinedione-5-acetic acid amide, have antibacterial properties. Recently, the synthesis and characterization of a number of new Schiff bases derived from metronidazole, as well as their anti-giardia and antibacterial activities, have been accomplished. "Schiff bases derived from isatin derivatives and N [4-(4-chloro phenyl) thiozole-2-yl] thiosemicarbazide have already been shown to have antimicrobial action; it has been observed that 2, 2-diamino Aside from that, information on the cytotoxicity of antimicrobial drugs is usually absent from studies that describe antimicrobial activity.

Because their structure and function characteristics are similar to those of naturally occurring macrocyclic molecules, artificial macrocycles and their M-complexes have attracted a lot of attention because of this fact. These characteristics include the complexes' advancing thermochemical and kinetic dissociation equilibrium, which leads to lower responsibility and higher relationship than complexes with similar openchain chelating agent. For example, the multidrug resistance that has evolved in antibiotics such as ampicillin (A), chloramphenicol, and others has made the treatment of infection a challenge during disease outbreaks. There has been an increase in the usage of antibiotics to treat human and animal ailments, which has led to the development of multidrug-resistant microbes that pose a huge threat to developing countries like India.

Schiff bases have received a lot of attention throughout the last decade. In the synthesis of biological molecules' building blocks, schiff bases are often utilised. In the medical and pharmaceutical fields, Sb's with sulphur as an element seem to be an important class of compounds. Antifungal, anticancer, antibacterial, and herbicidal activities are all a part of their repertoire. Their extraordinary biological activity has been connected to their ability to synthesise metals. "2, hydroxy methyl-4,8-dihydrobenzo[1,2-b;5,4-b/] dithiophene-4,8-dione-2-carboxylic acid and 4,8-dihydrobenzo[1,2-b;5,4-b/] dithiophene-4,8-dione-2-carboxylic acid," may rapidly accelerate leukaemia cell differentiation and death. It is well accepted that apoptosis induction and cell differentiation are critical to anti-leukemic therapeutic methods. In order to produce new compounds, the condensation of aromatic amines and orthophenylenediamine on 3,3/-bithiophene-2,2/ and -4,4/-dicarbaldehyde seemed like an intriguing idea. In this paper, we describe how to prepare and characterise freshly generated composites. Two and two The compound -3,3-bithiophene-3,3-bithiophene-3,3/bithiophene-3,3/-bithiophene -3,3/-bithiophene-3,3/-bith 4, dithieno -3,30 -bithiophene -3,30 -bithiophene -3,30 -bithiophene -3,30 -bithiophene -3,30 - bithiophenedithieno[2,3-c;30,20-e] azepino[1,2-a] benzimidazole 6 and azepino[1,2-a] benzimidazole 5

New metal complexes are now being investigated for their potential as drug candidates owing to a range of favourable properties such as the high number of coordination barriers they generate, their adaptability in terms of geometric geometry, and their redox states. Making a chemical by fusing molecules with metals like copper is a straightforward and cost-effective process that

opens up a plethora of new possibilities for the development of hybrid compounds. Platinum-based metal complex containing two chloride and two ammonia molecules, also known as cis-diamminedichloroplatinum, has long been utilised as a chemotherapeutic medication in the treatment of cancer. Consequently, new medication choices with lower IC50s and lower side effects are needed. STAT3 and NF-KB are both inhibited by benzofuran-conjugated iridium complexes when tested in the lab and in animals. They also work as a Ras/Raf-1 interaction inhibitor, a luminescence probe, and an inhibitor of cell proliferation in these complexes. Rhodium complexes selectively inhibit lysine-specific demethylase 5, an enzyme that is overexpressed in breast cancer. The rhodium complexes, on the other hand, target and kill cells with mismatched DNA bases.

With photocytotoxicity, ruthenium complexes are utilised to target DNA and damage it. With copper, you have a good metal complex material to employ. To begin with, it is an endogenous metal rather than an exterior metal like platinum, making it less harmful. For one thing, it has a lot of potential for DNA breakage and redox reactions. Three: It was shown to be selectively permeable to the membranes of cancer cells, and that the quantity of it in cells is carefully regulated. Furthermore, several copper compounds have been tested on a wide range of cell lines, with IC50 values that are very low. Consequently, the copper complex proved to be particularly effective in the battle against cancer cells. Cupro-containing compounds may be used to develop new molecules with effective anticancer activities by combining it with other chemical moieties. Imidazole's benzo derivative, benzimidazole, is the name of the drug. Vitamin B12, for example, has a significant amount of it. A wide range of beneficial effects may be found in this compound. These include those related to the prevention of infection and the treatment of various diseases. Amongst many other things. In several studies, benzimidazole derivatives have been shown to have anti-cancer effects. Anti-proliferative effects on "HeLa human cervical, MCF-7 breast, SW60 colon and MiaPaCa-2 pancreatic cancer cell lines, on T47D breast cancer cells, A549 lung cancer cells and HT29 colon cancer cells, several benzimidazole derivatives were discovered to exhibit anti-proliferative function." Researchers observed that 2-substituted benzimidazole compounds reduced the growth of HepG2 liver cell lines. Researchers found that MDA-MB-231 human breast cancer cells were inhibited by trisubstituted benzimidazole and its precursors. "SMMC7721 human liver, BGC823 human gastric, HCT116. human colon, and

HT29, human, colorectal cancer cell lines" were likewise suppressed by copper complexes of benzimidazole.

An extensive body of research has examined the stability of Sb-M-complexes including both N and S donor sites as well as their potential applications in several fields, such as oxidation catalysis & electrochemistry. When oxaloyldihydrazide and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde are joined, the Schiff base H4L is produced. The Schiff bases' propensity for chelation with transition metal ions is used in the formation of their solid complexes. Several transition metal H4L monometallic complexes have been reported. This study focuses on the coordination behaviour of H4L Sb', which possesses many Manganese (IV) and Ruthenium (III) ion binding sites, but no information is available on Mn and Ru metal ion heterobimetallic complexes. When energy is converted into fuel in PS-II using manganese complexes and oxygen is produced in the reaction from coordinated water molecules, manganese (iv) and ruthenium (ii) M-ions are used in equal amounts to synthesise equal products. This document summarises the findings of our investigation.

Reagents included manganese (II) acetate tetrahydrate, ruthenium (III) chloride trihydrate, potassium hydroxide, diethyloxalate, hydrazine hydrate, and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, among others, commercial grade ruthenium trichloride was activated by dissolving it in strong HCl and then evaporating it to dryness over a steam bath before being used in complex synthesis.

It has been shown that Hydrazones have antibacterial, antifungal, anti-convulsant, anti-tuberculosis, and anti-cancer properties, as well. For example, they've been shown to be useful as pesticides and admixtures, as well as plant growth stimulators (e.g. antioxidant initiators), plant stabilisers, and as metal extraction tools for analytical chemistry and spectroscopy to determine the presence of certain T-Ms. The antibacterial and anticancer effects of Hydrazone M compounds are well known. The anti-carcinogenic and antiviral properties of Schiff bases including Nitrogen, Sulfur, and Oxygen donors were revealed via a literature review of their interactions with t-m ions. Many isatin derivatives and M-complexes have been shown to have amazing biological properties. One study found anti-cancer, anti-herbicide, antibiotic and anti-convulsant effects. The antiviral effects of copper (II) complexes comprising isatin and thiosemicarbazone have been identified. The formation of free radicals in the human body is

influenced by a variety of internal and external factors. Singlet oxygen superoxide, peroxy, as well as peroxynitrite radicals are the most dangerous types of oxidative stress-inducing radicals.

Inflammation, cancer, cardiovascular disease, and Alzheimer's disease are all linked to oxidation deformation of cell binding agents such as proteins, nucleic acids, and lipids. Enzymes and amino acids that can bind to and neutralise free radicals are among the defence systems that keep free radicals in check. Oxidative stress and chronic hyperglycemia lead to the production of advanced glycation end-products, such as Amadori, which is the consequence of a chemical interaction between protein amino acids and sugar molecules. The glycooxidation of these products, which are much more reactive dicarbonyl molecules, results in advanced glycation end products (AGEs). When Amadori-adducts are oxidised, they are degraded into CML and CMhL, respectively, whereas pentosidine is produced by the binding of two amino acids. The oxidative process is more obvious in elderly and hyperglycemic patients than in healthy ones. AGE development may be slowed by antiglycation and anti-oxidation medicines, which prevent the oxidation of Amadori products from progressing any further. It's true that compounds with antioxidative and AGEs-inhibitory properties are being researched as possible prophylactic medicines for diabetic problems. Diabetic problems such as neuropathy, retinopathy, cataracts, and atherosclerosis all have a direct relationship to AGEs. In spite of the fact that the number of effective glycation biological processes with anti-oxidant qualities is currently limited, because of their therapeutic potential, considerable effort has been concentrated on the identification of new glycation inhibitors, as the prevalence of type-2 diabetes continues to rise. AGEP cross-links may be broken down by a small number of chemicals, which might possibly reverse the course of diabetic symptoms. All the manganese (ii), co, ni, Cu, Zn, and 2-hydroxy salicylhydrazide (see Supplementary Information) complexes of the Sb' of isatin with the 2-hydroxy salicylhydrazide were generated.

Sb' benzenesulfanohydrazone produced from zinc (II) and benzenesulfanohydrazide with hydroxyacetophenone were shown to have significant inhibitory effects on ulcer activity caused by 100 percent alcohol in rats, the preparation and examination and a biological study was undertaken for the confirmation of its structure. Benzenesulfanohydrazone oral medication reduced stomach lesions development before 100% ethanol administration without raising muco mass in comparison to the influence set. To put it another way, due of its structure and ability to

generate hydroxyl radicals, this molecule may be considered an oxidant. Toxins may be prevented from accumulating in the stomach by the aldehyde group of the molecule. An "electrophilic acceptor" and the mucosal sulfhydryl-containing groups are believed to be the mechanism for the cytoprotective action. Hydroxyl radicals may be produced by compounds with hydroxyl groups, which are known to have a role in the pathophysiology of stomach microbial flora.

These results suggest that benzenesulfanohydrazones may reduce free radical damage to stomach mucosal tissues, therefore preventing ethanol-induced stomach mucosal lesions. Benzenesulfanohydrazones and their complexes have been shown in studies to exhibit antimicrobial action. According to previous studies on the production and characterization of Sb' ligands, these compounds have anti-proliferative, antiviral, and antioxidative characteristics that were superior to those of vitamin E. The present study expands on previous studies by including a wide range of biologically active chemicals. "Sb's of benzosulfanohydrazones and their biological action, notably as anti-ulcerogenic drugs, ulcer is an open sore or lesion on the skin or mucosal membrane of the body, a Peptic ulcer is a lesion that occurs in the stomach or duodenal covering when HCl and pepsin are present," It was previously thought that lifestyle factors like as nutrition were to blame for the development of ulcers, however research has shown that hunger acids such as HCl and digestive enzymes have a role in infection. Medical chemistry breakthroughs have often relied on the identification of potent pharmacological compounds from natural sources like plants or microorganisms. Many of these variations were identified by trial and error. Although this approach was time and labour intensive, it yielded a broad range of medicinal compounds. Drugs that are designed to interact with known biological systems have garnered increasing attention in the past 20–30 years.

Carbonylhydrazide is used to produce Schiff base, which includes extra functional groups. Organic syntheses for fine chemicals and medicines and as an effective oxygen scavenger to prevent corrosion in boiler feed systems have made it a popular choice. Carbohydrazone is an azotic ligand with a single electron pair. Depending on the kind of M ion, it may produce monodentate or multidentate compounds. It is used to construct a wide spectrum of explosive coordination molecules because of its comparably high capacity to reduce them. In deprotonated states, keto and enol tautomerism may occur in these complexes, leading to ligand coordination. Using their

ligand, metal ions may be stabilised in unusual oxidation states and produce neutral complexes. Sbl benzil bis (carbohydrazone) is the subject of this research, which aims to synthesise and analyse the compound using spectroscopic and thermal techniques. The Schiff base BBC was used to build a cadmium (II) selectivity sensor. In addition to causing fever, muscle pains, and inflammation, exposure to cadmium may induce respiratory and kidney damage. Studies have shown a relationship between cadmium and cancers of the lung and prostate. In order to meet this essential requirement, cadmium-detection compounds must be developed.

An array of biological and pharmacological properties are found in Sbl's such as their ability to inhibit the development of bacteria and other organisms as well as their ability to synthesise and describe them. A lot of attention has already been paid to the pharmacological properties of thiosemicarbazone derivatives. In addition to being employed in a wide range of applications, Thiosemicarbazone derivatives are also used in the chemical middle of a range, odour, dyes, rubber, and liquid grain for semiconductors. The hydrazine group's imino and amino nitrogen atoms exhibit varying degrees of hybridization in their valance electrons. Complexes of thiosemicarbazone derivatives against the "HL60 and A.549 cancer cell lines" also show anti-inflammatory, antimutagenic, anticarcinogenic, antiallergic, and anticancer characteristics. For the metal centre, tridentates and monodentates in a mixed system offer the penta-coordinate environment. It is also important in inorganic and bioinorganic chemistry since hydrazine derivative complexes have been shown to be models for a number of medically relevant substances. Many studies have been conducted on the synthesis and characterization of 3d and 4d metal complexes containing these ligands because of their importance in organic chemistry. A chelate ring may be formed by the addition of additional donor particles in L, which facilitates the complexation process.

Condensing succinoyl- and adipoyl-dihydrazines with salicylaldehyde was employed to create the complexes in this study. Acyl and aroyldihydrazines from aliphatic dicarboxylic acids with two $-\text{CONHNH}_2$ groups have been reported to coordinate as a neutral bivalent ligand via two imino nitrogens ($>\text{NH}$), despite the existence of "potentially strong donor functionalities such as $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $-\text{NH}_2$." A pyridyl nitrogen atom in these ligands seems to make the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $-\text{NH}_2$ groups reactive, on the other hand, d The presence of in dihydrazones of this kind has been ruled out. To make the ligands employed in this study, the disalicylaldehyde, succinoyl, and

adipoyldihydrazines were combined with disalicylaldehyde. Cyclic voltammetry was used in a nitrogen atmosphere using a CH Instruments Electrochemical Analyzer to detect the complexes in DMSO (103 M). The electrolytic cell is made up of three electrodes. It is a glassy carbon disc from BAS, with 0.1 M Tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate as the supporting electrolyte. Reference electrode and sample solution were separated by a salt bridge, which was an aqueous saturated calomel electrode or AgCl.

By 2060, the amount of CO₂ con's is predicted to reach 500 mg/litre, with a global temperature increase of no more than 20 degrees Celsius over pre-industrial levels, indicating that human activities have impacted the Earth's weather on a geological scale. Future energy scenarios are strongly dependent on technologies that are both environmentally friendly and financially viable and strong in the conversion and storage of renewable energy sources such as sunlight. Scientists are studying natural photosynthesis mechanisms that are capable of collecting, accelerating, and turning sunlight into chemical energy in order to implement a carbonneutral energy system. Hydroxide may be converted to hydrogen by hydrogenase, which is an enzyme that occurs naturally in the body. Lab experiments and real-world measurements of response dimensions might help address energy issues. A catalyst that is both inexpensive and efficient is the most challenging hurdle to overcome. Because of this, researchers are searching for less expensive ways to produce hydrogen by using non-precious, non-conservative metals. The artificial hydrogen evolution approach has so far revealed Co to be the most effective earth-abundant metal. Diene-N₄ macrocyclic Co complex electrocatalysts with a total oxidised nitrogen (TON) value of 164 have been shown to reduce bulk electrolysis in acid. Because of their ability to adhere to the electrode surface, "Cobalt porphyrin derivatives" have been limited in their application. Cobaloxime complexes have also been utilised as effective reducing agents for proton reduction from aqueous or nonaqueous acidic solutions generated by the catalyst, Imine and oxime ligands are more stable than cobaloximes when it comes to hydrolysis, but all of these complexes, which have a four-coordinate square planar backbone, have axial sites that are either free or occupied by labile monodentate ligands/solvents for catalysis, and active acid reduction electrocatalysts have also been reported. . In clathrochelate trisdioxime complexes, electrocatalysts for proton reduction have been found. This process uses a new kind of Co complex to reduce protons to hydrogen. According to philosophical study, the Co (ii/i) pair is decreased at a voltage that corresponds to the centre of a range for the transitory substrate

catalizador. Electro-catalytic and photochemical transformations of protons in extracts of a Ni compound with a N_2S_2 type Sbl' were studied using a highly reactive CoIII-hydride intermediate produced by ligands containing both phosphorus and nitrogen donor ligands. Monocyclic bis "(thiosemicarbazonato) Cu (II)" complex may also be used to decrease protons with the assistance of a metal-aided ligand, as proven.

There is a significant gap in the translation of scientific research discoveries into trader development for application in real-world situations because of this prompting research in various precisely researched chemical compounds for H production from amino acids. Because of this, we'll be using fossil fuels for a few more years still to come. As a consequence, decreasing atmospheric CO_2 levels has become a popular second-tier hot issue. It will be important in the near future to develop C-neutral vim solutions that effectively capture, store, and use CO_2 . You may utilise CO_2 by making fuels or other industrially important molecules from it. To achieve this, chemists may employ methods like photocatalytic and electrocatalytic reductions. Develop "effective electrocatalyst or photocatalyst for the conversion of CO_2 into C-1 (CH_4 , CO , and $HCOOH$) or C-2 ($COOH$) building blocks" might reduce total greenhouse gas emissions. Consequently, the study of energy and the environment is becoming more concerned with this topic. Oxalate forms when carbon dioxide (CO_2) is subjected to a negative potential. As an intermediate, the ligand [N-(2-mercaptoethyl)-N, N bis(2-pyridylmethyl)amine] produces a dinuclear copper(I) complex, which is preferentially oxidised by atmospheric CO_2 to form an oxalato bridged tetranuclear copper complex. Additionally, the chemical exhibits electrocatalytic reduction of CO_2 to oxalate at a potential of 0.03 V. Ni macroring compounds have been intensively explored by organisations working on CO_2 electrocatalysis. Aprotic solvents such as dimethyl sulfoxide decrease CO_2 to $HCOOH$, while CO_2 is transformed to CO_2 in water at a pH of 5–6. Several Ni-cyclam compounds prefer to convert carbon dioxide to carbon monoxide rather than acid to hydrogen during the reduction process. The "ligand 2,4,9,11,11-pentamethyl-2,3,4 triaza-1-one4-amine" is electrochemically reduced to create oxalate utilising a Nickel (II) Schiff base combination of CO_2 as a competent catalyst for electrocatalytic CO_2 reduction to Carbon monoxide as the sole carbon-containing product. Chemistry has made significant contributions to resource activity research, but there is still a lack of information on catalyst costs, activities, and stabilities. Commercialization requires low-cost yet high-performance catalysts. In order to produce less and more effective chemicals, 1st row T-with m's Sb' ligands

were employed. We achieved this by "combining 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with N, N-dimethyl-1,3-propanediamine to form cobalt, nickel, and zinc complexes of a Schiff base," as stated in the paper.

In order to maintain the same ligand environment, transition metal ions are used as core metal ions. However, even if the ligand environment changes with metals, this does not affect the molecule. As reagents for proton and carbon dioxide reduction investigations, we looked for Co and Ni complexes. "The thermodynamic reduction potential of these two processes, which are enhanced by the cobalt and nickel complexes, was also carefully evaluated; both the cobalt (I) and nickel (II) complexes were investigated as electrochemical CO₂ reduction and proton reduction catalysts, complex 1 has been shown to be active in the reduction of acid to hydrogen, whereas complex 2 has been found to reduce CO₂ and generate oxalate as a main product, the oxalate." Merck and Across Organics provided the N,N-dimethyltrimethylenediamine and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, respectively, while Fisher Scientific provided the oxalic acid, formic acid sodium dihydrogen phosphate, and orthophosphoric acid," while Spectrochemi provided the tetrabutyl ammonium hydrogen sulphate. HPLC-grade solvents were used for spectral and electrochemical analysis. The solvents methanol and dimethylsulfoxide were supplied by Spectrochem. Dichloromethane was one of Rankem's several high-pressure liquid chromatography-grade solvents. To make metal-powered oxidising agents, the M-carbonates were processed according to the procedure outlined in the preceding section. A.R. solvents were used throughout the artificial occupation, and they were used just as they were intended. In the electrochemical testing, tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP), a recognised chemical compound, was used.

We face an increased threat from drug-resistant germs expanding out of control due to a lack of new medications on the market. Chronic infections are becoming more common, which exacerbates the situation since many of these diseases are incurable because of drug resistance. Many possible targets exist in bacteria, but one that has recently received a lot of attention has been DNA. One upshot of this is that many DNA-binding drugs also have antibacterial characteristics. A number of other DNA-binding metal complex (metallo-complex [CoL₃]²⁺) derivatives have also been shown to have antibacterial action against *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* as well as *Enterococcus* and *Enterobacteriaceae* bacteria.

"Echinomycin" is more efficient than vancomycin in vitro and in vivo in mice against clinical isolates of "methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*," while the pentamidine analogue bis-(3-(4-dimethylaminophenyl)allylidene). 1,2-diaminoethane's Zn(II) complex has MIC values of 0.49 g mL⁻¹ for both bacteria; the benzimidazole heterocycle, which is found in commercial drugs like omeprazole, mebendazole, and astemizole, is also found in many biologically important DNA minor groove binding molecules like Hoechst33258 and Hoechst-33342" and several antimicrobials and could be used as Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antiulcer, antihypertensive, antiviral, antifungal, antihistaminic, and antiparasitic effects of benzimidazole-based compounds are also notable. Aside from their intriguing spectral, magnetic, and structural properties, coordination chemistry with benzimidazoles and their derivatives is receiving attention due to their therapeutic applications as anticancer agents, antioxidants, and enzyme inhibitors in metal complexes of benzimidazoles and their derivatives. In addition, benzimidazole-based compounds have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antiulcer, antihypertensive, antiviral, antifungal, antihistaminic, and antiparasitic effects that are worth mentioning.

Among the many ligands that contain "O, O'-chelating 4-acyl (formyl)pyrazole-5-one ligand and their Schiff base derivatives," "their structural versatility and relevant applications of their metal complexes exhibiting antitumor, antimicrobial, catalytic, and high photoluminescence and electroluminescence efficacy" are of particular interest in coordination chemistry. Those containing a thiol or thione group in the 5th position of the pyrazole ring, on the other hand, have had significantly less research done on their chemistry. It is possible to create trans-cis planar or tetrahedral structures in the presence of the N₂S₂ ligand by using monocyclic tetra-coordinated M-chelates of zinc (Zn(ii), cadmium(ii), nickel (ii), and palladium (i2). In order to better understand the structural, spectroscopic, and electrical properties of "blue copper proteins," Cu (II) compounds of bidentate mercaptopyrazole are Sb's with Nitrogen and Sulfur donor-atom combinations. The Fe (III)-thiolate low-spin complex with a Fe (III) N₃ S₃ coordination core mimics naturally occurring metalloenzymes such as nitrile hydratase and is based on the tridentate It is important to note that the magnetic properties of the tri- and pentadentate Cu, Nickel, and Co generated from tri- and pentadentate ions have been studied. Mercaptopyrazole fragment-containing Sb's have been reported. The aminoheterocycle 2-amino-1-ethylbenzimidazole was chosen as a co-ligand for two reasons. For starts, the competitive reactivity regulation of

ambidentate ligand systems relies heavily on aminoheterocycles with two or more potential donor centres. It is also feasible to predict the binding processes of different transition metal aminoazole and aminoazine adducts. Biomolecular assemblies that are immobilised on metal surfaces need to be placed in the appropriate areas for metallation.

Organic molecules known as Schiff bases have a wide range of uses, including as ligands in the synthesis of t-m-complexes. Aside from a host of other health benefits, Sb's also contain antibacterial and antifungal effects. There is no doubt that M-complexes have played a significant role in the development of chemistry, as indicated by the large number of articles devoted to anything from pure research to the investigation of physicochemical features. A new generation of Schiff bases is being developed by medicinal chemists at the moment. The physiological effects of Schiff bases have been studied by a number of research organisations. The antitumor efficacy of Sbs derived from 2-aminonicotinaldehyde and substituted benzyl semicarbazide was examined in three different human tumour cell lines. "7-amino-4-methylcoumarin" and "benzaldehydes" were used by Ronad and colleagues to generate a range of Sb's with "anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects equivalent to or greater than a reference medication" in certain circumstances. Combining aromatic aldehydes with coumarin acetohydrazides in convection and micro-onde conditions yielded Schiff bases, which Bertinaria and colleagues used to produce compounds with significant antibacterial activity against various pathogens.

Among the many applications for metal-salicylaldimines, which are coordination molecules, are agriculture, optoelectronics, antibacterial drugs and treatments, polymers and dyes as well as medications and catalysts. In addition, liquid-crystalline materials based on related chemicals have lately gained interest. It is well knowledge that salicylaldimines are the ligands of choice because of their ease of synthesis and their pliable coordination environment. OLEDs, information storage, sensors, lasers, and enhanced contrast displays are among the many uses for photo-responsive materials with well-coordinated fluid phases. The luminous properties of M-complexes, as well as the capacity of (LCs) to self-organize, are of particular interest, as they provide a practical approach to the creation of multipurpose materials. The luminescence of metallomesogens like Pd(ii), pt(II), iridium(III), nickel(II), rhodium(I), gold(I), silver(I), zinc(II), and copper(II) has attracted scientists (I). Intriguing fluorescent properties of Zn (I2) and its

relatives Cd (II) and Hg (II) compounds are due to l-centered charge transfer or m-centered luminous plat, allowing for the construction of novel functional materials. For example, metallomesogens containing Pd (II), Cu (II), Oxo-Vanadium (IV), Ni, iron (III), or Mn have been synthesised using salicylaldimine (III). An important metal in producing luminescent materials is the Lanthanide family. Cd and Hg ions appear to be nonexistent, but the description of "mesomorphic cadmium alkanoates or with porphyrins as ligands, there's only been sporadic reference of cadmium-based mesogens in the research, in undocumented reference to undescribed cadmium and mercury di-thiobenzoate compounds, with ill-defined phases was made in 1993." This mesomorphism is often lost due to the Zn metal ion's decision to take on the tetrahedral form. Even in the last decade, there have been very few discoveries of transparent or liquid-solid phase tetrahedral zinc complexes with mesomorphism; the literature only contains very few instances of the latter kind. To counteract the "tetradentate salen type ligands, which force the metal ion to assume the thermodynamically stable tetrahedral form, bidentate ligands with long alkyl arms allow the metal ion to attain the tetrahedral form, procedure order in molecular self-assembly, we suggest a range of luminous tetrahedral zinc (II), cadmium (II).

These Schiff base compounds have received much attention in the field of coordination science due to the ease with which they may be synthesised and the favourable steric, electrical, & reagent characteristics that they exhibit. Supramolecular structures may also be created using these materials. Over the last decade, "polyazamacrocyclic ligands" have been extensively explored in the field of co-ordination science because of their ability to form complexes with different M-ions or anionic species, which has led to a wide variety of applications. Although metal macrocyclic chemistry has been around for a long time, its significance in co-ordination research has only just begun to take shape. These macrocyclic ligands contain a variety of N, S, & O donor atoms in varying sizes, amounts, and types that may be coordinated with different metal cores. The stiffness of the coordination compounds, the size of the inner void, and the morphology of macro-cyclic materials. An aliphatic molecule with a high nitrogen content, piperazine In supramolecular complex chemistry, piperazine's role as a hydrogen-bond receiver makes it a very important metabolite. It also has the ability to bind with metals. New macrocyclic Sb' compounds with a piperazine moiety have recently been identified for Mn(ii), Cadmium(ii), Zinc(ii), palladium(ii), Cobalt(ii), and Nickel (ii) (II). X-RC was used to evaluate the solid properties of some of these compounds. A distorted octahedral geometry with an N₄O₂ core is

formed by coordination by the macrocyclic framework's four donor nitrogen and two oxygen from the bidentate Nitrate Ion in $[\text{CoL}(\text{NO}_3)]^+$ complexes, whereas in Nickel (II) complexes, two nitrogen atoms from the piperazine as well as two nitrogen atoms from the imine groups coordinate the Nickel (ii) ion to an N_4O_2 core. Synthesis and characterization of a Schiff base ligand derived via the "condensation reaction of 1,4-bis(2-formylphenyl) piperazine and 1,4-diaminobutane" is the subject of this study (ii). Elemental analysis, infrared, fast atom bombardment mass spectrometry, conductivity tests, and ^1H -Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy were used to evaluate the Schiff base's co-ordination inclination toward T-S ions in the $[\text{ZnL}(\text{NO}_3)]\text{ClO}_4$ complex. Theoretical investigations of the interactions of metal ions were conducted.

Salicylaldehyde and salicylaldehyde derivatives are used in a one-step reaction with "primary diamines," such as 1,2-diaminoethane and 1,3-diaminopropane, to produce stable mono- and polynuclear complexes with many transition metals. A synthesising agent is any species that contains the information necessary to arrange a set of building blocks in a certain way. We found that hydrolytic division of monocondensed tridentate Schiff base produced two bidentate strong-field ligands that could fill all four equal places on Cu by utilising counter anions that were only weakly coordinated (II). To prevent the mono-addition Schiff base from rearranging into a N_2O_4 donor Schiff base in the absence of azide or pyridine, we first prepared the tridentate Schiff base before adding azide or pyridine. Our lab recently published a paper on the Cu (II) functionalized, formation of monodcondensed Schiff bases from "1, 2-diaminoethane and 3-methoxysalicylaldehyde." Schiff base interacts with copper in the presence or absence of strongly coordinating cyanate (II). It has been shown that the Schiff base's amine nitrogen is formed in the absence of the presence of cyanate, which results in the conversion of a tridentate Schiff base to the bidentate form of Schiff base. Due to the inhibition of protonation by a base, a copper (II) complex with a tridentate Schiff base forms in dimethylformamide solution. The fourth coordination site is occupied by a DMF molecule. Cu (II) complexes are shown to be affected by the counter anion/coordinating solvent's capability. Supramolecular systems based on coordination compounds have previously garnered a lot of attention because of its numerous applications "as sensors, probes, photonic devices, catalysts, and in host-guest chemistry." It's the only one there... π , c-h, and anions, and the only one there. Among supramolecular chemists, π interactions are widespread and well-accepted, and they are all connected to the stability of molecules in the solid state, anion... Recent years

have seen a growing amount of crystallographic and theoretical evidence for anion- π interactions, which were previously assumed to be implausible due to anions' electron-donating nature and the predicted repulsive interaction with aromatic systems. Discoveries have been made about π 's interactions. Structures and supramolecular assemblies of molecular building blocks in three novel Cu (II) complexes by lone pair synthesis, description, and X-ray crystal structures "Interactions between π , π ... π and anion... are detailed."

When oxygen is broken down in the body, free radicals with higher atomic number and more chemical activity are produced. Damage to the peptide bond, lipids, and DNA in bio-fabric, as well as the production and detoxification of free radical species, causes oxidative stress and, as a result, diseases such as neoplasia, inflammation, ischemia and reperfusion, emergent pancreatitis, atherosclerosis, and diabetes mellitus. When it comes to the therapy of free radical-related illnesses and disorders, it's vital to develop molecules that are more antioxidative in nature. π ' complexes of T-metals in a wide variety have generated interest owing to their diverse therapeutic properties, including anticancer activity. Transition M compounds' medicinal actions are, surprisingly, dictated by the M-ions and Ls themselves. It took him a long time and a lot of labour to construct π ' complexes with diverse M-ions that have significant anticancer qualities, in addition to helping medications operate quicker. Manganese (III) complexes containing salen derivatives (salen = salicylaldehyde-ethylene diamine Schiff base) were extensively studied as anti-oxidant agents against inflammatory diseases, as well as the bulk of their chemical and biological properties have been reported. Cu, co-ordination compounds with Schiff base ligands, have also been investigated as antioxidants and superoxigenes. Our interest was piqued by the synthesis of Mn and Cu complexes made from bis (N-(3-methoxysalicylidene)-4-aminophenyl) ether Schiff base as well as their biological properties, although Paula Cucos reported the structural, magnetic and luminescent properties of a Copper (II) complex made from bis(N-[3methoxysalicylidene]-4-aminophenyl) ether Schiff base, we used the same ligand, different metal salts and different solvents, resulting in the same double-helical.

The biological, bactericidal, and fungicidal properties of acid hydrazides, hydrazine derivatives, and their M-complexes are well-known, and their analytical, industrial, and medicinal relevance has piqued interest in Sbs. This is because they produce more stable complexes with the majority of t-m-ions. In our investigation into the synthesis, spectroscopic and crystal structure of 3d

metal complexes of a series of mesogenic organic Schiff-bases, we report the results of our investigations into the hydrazone-based mesogenic Schiff-b hydrazone-based Schiff-b hydrazone-based Schiff-b Conventional methods were used when required to dry off the liquid.

Molecular proton carryover reactions, which may be utilised to make laser dyes, optical memories, and switches, as well as to control and monitor radiation intensity, have drawn a lot of attention. The O-hydroxylated Sbs show absorption imovel such as "photochromism and thermochromism" in the cubic state and in liquid, and have been investigated in this area for many years. There are two instances of reversible colour changes in these substances, namely photochromic and thermochromatic (thermochromism). The O in hydroxy and the N in imine are connected by an intramolecular proton because of these characteristics. Excited and tierra states are both known to cause hydrogen carryover. Enol-imine (nitrogen... hydrogen–oxygen) and keto-amine (nitrogen–hydrogen... oxygen) forms of 2-hydroxy are tautomerized and equilibrium occurs between them It is because of intramolecular hydrogen transfer that the p-electronic configuration of Sbl's has been altered. The (Nitrogen...Hydrogen–Oxygen) kind of hydrogen bonding is created by the Sbs produced from salicylaldehyde. Sb's derived from "2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde" create forms of hydrogen-hydrogen bonding. A number of Sb crystallised from 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde were studied using NMR and X-ray analyses. In both polar and non-polar solvents, the UV spectra of several 2-hydroxyl Sbs were studied. The Sb"s keto-amine variant shows an absorption band in excess of 400 nm.

enol-imine is more prevalent in nonpolar solvents, while keto-amine is more prevalent in polar solvents. Schiff bases can be incorporated into crown ether structures and provide interesting cation binding ligands, in these kind of structures, the cation can fill the crown cavity or start creating the Schiff base complex via the imine group, depending on the donor atom and cation characteristics, the chemometric technique was used to quantify indefinite mixtures of function Sb's of 2-hydroxynaphthaldehydes in a recent ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy study. When it comes to macrobicyclic molecules with an ortho-hydroxylated Schiff base, there is no example of one with an O, N, and S atom donor atom in the wreath ether moiety. The O-hydroxy naphthaldimine region and complex formation features of a novel macrobicyclic ligand were discovered by the synthesis of a new macrobicyclic L using a N–O–S mixed donor. The complex

equilibrium constant and complex configuration of M ions with L were determined using spectrofluorimetric titrations in acetonitrile-dichloromethane.

For their structural diversity as well as potential applications as antitumor, catalytic, antimicrobial, redox, photochemical and photophysical agents, and building blocks for efficient luminescent, electroluminescent and photoswitching devices, the chemistry of metal complexes predicated on 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and its derivatives is widely studied. Functionalized phen ligands have been used widely over the past three decades by scientists working on molecular recognition and sensing, as well as DNA/RNA binding and cleavage. M-chelates of Sb tridentates with diverse groups of nitrogen, oxygen, and sulphur donors in the complexing ring have received little attention. Cu (II) compounds based on semi(S)- or TS ligands are among the M compounds that investigate a variety of vital functions in biological systems. To make the series of complexes, an electrochemical cell containing tridentate Sbl' and phen was used, along with a one-step electrolysis procedure called electrosynthesis, with a metal plate acting as the sacrificial anode.

Sb's and their M-ion complexes provide a variety of advantages and have been well regarded in the past, therefore they are considered an advantageous class of thoroughly investigated compounds. Their ligands are formed by condensation of amino and aldehyde molecules and include carbon-nitrogen double bond groups. They may interact with all or some of the donor particles in nature of the molecule to coordinate a large number of transition M-ions in mono- or polydentate systems. These compounds offer a number of benefits due to their low cost of manufacturing and broad variety of applications. It is because of this that even small modifications in an individual ligand may have a significant impact on the characteristics of related complexes. Recent study has focused on transition M-complexes with Sbls because of their allure. Complexes of this kind have antitumor, cytotoxic, antibacterial, anticancer, & antimicrobial properties, amongst many others. The catalysts have a key role in both homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions. The responsiveness of this class of coordination compounds is affected by the kind of ligand coordination sites and the metal used.

The halogenated salicylaldehyde yields Schiff base Ni(ii) and Cu(ii) compounds, which may be synthesised using a variety of 10-amines. Structure flexibility enables these materials to combine magnetic features with other fascinating models, including a number of essential biological

systems that might be exploited in practical applications. Catalytic activities involving these Sb complexes include the epoxidation of olefins, electro-reduction of CO₂, electro-oxidation of -OH, and asymmetric sulfo-oxidation as well as organic compound oxidation. There is a quantitative synthesis that gives high yields for the preparation of ligands known as the Sb' method. This study describes the synthesis of a bidentate Sb', which was made from "2-(4-methoxyphenyl) ethylamine and 3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde". After reacting with "Ni (CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O and Cu (CH₃COO)₂·2H₂O (2:1)" in methanol, the ligand HL produced the expected Ni II and Cu II compounds, which will be discussed in more detail below. The structure of a suggested bidentate Sb' with copper and nickel compounds is shown in the form of the created L and M ion compounds, which were comprehensively revealed utilising complementary spectroscopic and architectural methodologies.

First row TM complexes have long been used to synthesise a wide variety of coordination compounds, but these days they're getting more attention because of their crucial structural, catalytic, magnetic, and biological properties. Complexes with Schiff bases synthesised from 2-thiopheneethylamine are rare. Yet little study has been done on complexes containing the Sb' generated by 2-thiopheneethylamine and salicylaldehyde despite the availability of Co³⁺, Ni²⁺, and Cu²⁺. Four novel complexed first-row transition metals of unique first-row transition metals are prepared and their structural features are reported. Cobalt (III), nickel (II), and copper (II) all have a bivalent Schiff base ligand (HL).

Hydrazones-based compounds have been examined and shown to have antibacterial, antiviral and antibiotic effects in antituberculosis and antimalarial processes. We sought to integrate the activity of benzoylhydrazones and uracil derivatives in a new ligand in order to add to this area of research. Antitumor and antiviral properties of thiosemicarbazone, a molecule produced from hydrazone, have been discovered in recent years. N, N, and S are the most common modes of coordination for them. Oxygen, Nitrogen, Oxygen, or Nitrogen, Nitrogen, Oxygen hydrazone molecules have received less attention in the scientific community. Only a handful of papers have been published on benzoylhydrazones, despite the compounds' significant antibacterial potential. The 6-aminouracil moiety in the ligand we used in this study allowed us to explore the possibility of benzoylhydrazones having a second metal binding site (O₄ or N₆). Additional

complexes with structures comparable to those seen in biological systems could arise if an uracil ring is present.

An investigation on the use of new water-soluble hexadentate Schiff base ligands as sequestering agents for iron (III) and gallium (III). In physiological pH, the pH values of the highly water-soluble complexes were higher than those of compounds derived from N, N, N', N'-Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), N, N, N', N'-diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA), or transferrin, but were similar to those of relative hydroxamic acid siderophore compounds. It's no secret that chelating agents for Fe (III) have long been used in biomedical applications, but there's also an increasing focus on the use of Al (III) in biological systems. Siderophores and siderophore models as Al (III) and In (III) sequestering agents have been the subject of recent study (for use as radiopharmaceuticals). These Schiff bases may be used as ligands for Al (III), In (III), Tl (III), and SC, as well as the trivalent metal ions Tl (III) and SC, in order to further examine their reactivity (II). Biological systems are becoming more and more interested in Al (III) aqueous coordination chemistry, in addition to the long-established interest in natural and synthetic chelating agents for Fe (III). Siderophores and siderophore models as Al (III) and In (III) sequestering agents have been the subject of recent study (for use as radiopharmaceuticals). Because of this, we show how these water-soluble hexadentate Schiff bases are used as ligands for the trivalent metal ions Tl (III) and SC (III), the divalent cations Zn (II), Ni (II), and Cd, as well as the trivalent metal ions Al (III), In (III) (II). As we tested the stability of Schiff base complexes with Al (III), In (III), and Zinc (III), we found pH values at appropriate pHs (II). Phosphorus (pH) values may be more useful than stability constants since they represent binding strength at that pH. Consequently, it is possible to compare the performance of several ligands in sequestering a metal ion in the same environment under the same conditions. For this reason, Schiff bases were not separated, but rather stoichiometric amounts of aldehydes and polyamines were used to synthesise ligands in situ instead.

More recently, the study of new molecular fabric for photonic crystal and optical applications has been dominated by the study of organometallic and co-ordination complexes containing Sbls. Sbl's are simple to make by mixing 10-amines with aromatic carbonyl and can form complexes with almost every metal ion while maintaining a wide range of metals in different oxidation numbers. Electron donor and receiver pro-forms on the ligands' skeletons make them favoured

because of their structural flexibility. Monocondensation methods of dicarbonyl compounds, which are easy to create and alter using a primary diamine, allow for the production of unsymmetrical or symmetrical Sbls. Oligo-polymers have been the focus of our research for the past several years, as we've concentrated on producing the most important chain and alongside chain polymers of suitably modified Sb M(II) complexes with significant 2nd order nonlinear vision responses.

In order to avoid a solubility constraint, "we assumed that electropolymerization of a Schiff base complex with a pendant electroactive 2-thienyl fragment would be of interest, especially in the case of main-chain polymers, in this regard, we recently investigated the electrochemical properties of the bis-1-(2-thienyl)-3-(3-thienyl) propane-1, 3-dionato complex of copper (II), revealing f'' in this case. 1,1,1-Trifluoro-4-(2-thienyl)-4-[(2-[4,4,4-trifluoro-3-oxo-1-(2-thienyl)-but-1-en-1-yl] aminoethyl] amino], Using this method, we offer here updated synthesis processes for the well-known N, N'-Bis [1-(2 Thienyl) Ethylidene] Schiff base complexes using but-3-en-2-one 2 as a ligand. Analytical and spectroscopic methods, single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis, and cyclic voltammetry were all used to describe and verify the complexes, as well as 1,2-diaminoethane and its bis-trifluoroacetylated derivative 2, which were then reacted with the appropriate metal (II) acetate salts to produce the symmetrically substituted N_2O_2 -tetradentate Schiff base complexes of Co

Because they may be synthesised from a broad variety of aldehydes and amines, Schiff base-type compounds are the most often used ligands in co-ordination chemistry. Various Schiff base ligands with different numbers of coordination sites have been used to define various molecular structures with specified properties (optical, magnetic or electrical) for sp^2 hybridised orbitals of the Azomethine group, which can coordinate to various M-ions from S, P, d or f-blocks with various oxidation numbers due a single electron pair in N particle (beginning with bicompartimental N_2O_2 types and progressing to polydentate N_xO_y structures). A wide range of fields have found success with them, including medicine (active principles), biology (antibacterial and antifungal drugs), analytical chemistry (optical and electrochemical sensors), and material science (antibiotics) (catalysts and antimicrobial reagents, emitting diode OLED, PLED).

Research in this area has focused on the production of novel homo- and heteronuclear complexes, as well as the evaluation of their potential use in the relevant fields of interest: magnetism, catalysis, and optoelectronics. When compared to other studies, our objective was to create unique siloxane or silane-type complexes with transition metal ions, lanthanides, or combinations of these, rather than similar compounds seen in the literature. The issue discussed in this study is challenging to produce and explain because of the intriguing features that these compounds may acquire, either in the form of silicone or a rigid and polar complexed metal component, given the qualities of the suggested structures' building blocks. Silicone is a good environmentally friendly material for electrical applications because of its high moisture resistance and broad temperature range. Having the capacity to chemically alter them contributes in the development of new significant materials with enhanced optical, mechanical, and thermal properties for a variety of different uses. Many Schiff bases have interesting optoelectronic characteristics and can be used in electronics, such as organic field-effect semiconductor devices, electrochromic equipment, and others. Silicone can also be utilised for compounds that have nonlinear optic characteristics or electro-optical effects. Nonlinear optical properties of metallic Schiff base complexes are exciting, and they might be helpful in fluorescence sensors and electroluminescence.

In the development of new drugs, organic techniques involving the condensation of many molecules to produce novel complexes are often used. In the presence of certain media, 10- amines combine with aromatic aldehydes to produce Sbs. They are essential because of their vast range of catalytic, industrial, and biological applications, as well as their ability to bind M-ions in a wide range of oxidation levels. Antitumor, antiviral, antifungal, and antibacterial actions are all due to the "azomethine lone pair of electrons" (-CH=N-) bonding in their structure. They are often studied as antimalarials and are used to treat drug resistance in cancer patients..

It is possible to use them to immobilise enzymes. Some of the Sbls and M ion compounds have been studied for their intriguing properties and applications, such as their photochromic properties, while others have significant biological activity and applications. These compounds have also been important for the advancement of inorganic bio-chemical research, contemporary coordination chemistry, and visual art. Chemicals containing salicylaldehyde were used to create anti-inflammatories as well as antibiotics and sterilants as well as fungicides and insecticides. In

order to gain an understanding of action of newly discovered benzaldehyde Schiff bases, a variety of high-yielding Schiff bases were produced and their structures was described using Nuclear Magnetic Resonance and Mass spectroscopy data.

Researchers synthesised and investigated the tetradentate Schiff base (E)-2-((3-aminophenyl-imino)methyl)phenol (HL) ligand derived from the "condensation reactions of mphenylenediamine and 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde," as well as their metal complexes, as the primary focus of this study. Different spectroscopy techniques, such as elemental analysis, conductometry, magnetic susceptibility, thermogravimetric analysis, thermal gravimetric analysis, FT-IR, ultraviolet-visible, ¹H-NMR, mass investigations and molecular docking approaches, were used to investigate their interaction with metal ions. After theoretical optimization, the quantum chemical properties of the Schiff base (HL) and its M-complexes were discovered and reported. The antibacterial activity of the produced materials L and M ion compounds was tested against bacterial species. Receptors (Escherichia coli (3 T88) and Staphylococcus aureus (3Q8U) for Schiff base ligand HL in contrast to antibacterial activity against Gram bacteria (Escherichia coli) and Gram + (Staphylococcus aureus) (HL).

Because of the wide range of useful compounds that may be made from epoxides, olefin epoxidation is an essential step in the synthesis of fine chemicals, medicines, and agrochemicals. Research into epoxidation techniques has been driven by an increase in the demand for epoxide molecules. Olefin oxidation has traditionally relied on traditional organic oxidants (peracids), but this has its downsides, such as toxic byproducts and a difficult time isolating the oxidant from the resulting product. Examples include peracids and tertbutyl hydroperoxides, both of which have environmental concerns and a high price. Styrene aerobic epoxidation was improved by the addition of a manganese complex in the interlayer space of Zn (II)-Al (III) layered double hydroxide, as compared to a homogeneous sulfonatosalen manganese (III) complex. Oxovanadium (IV) and iron (III) salen complexes grafted onto amino-modified graphene oxide were shown to effectively catalyse the epoxidation of styrene in our investigation. When it comes to olefin epoxidation, molecular oxygen is the oxidant of choice due to its favourable effects on both the environment and the economy. When an aldehyde and an amine are combined to form a Schiff base, a bivalent ligand, stable transition metal complexes may be formed. In

organic transformation processes, homogeneous reagents like T-metal Sb' have been demonstrated to be as effective as biological catalysts.

Among the most effective and reactive catalytic systems for styrene epoxidation are chiral iron-sexipyridine complexes. There are, however, a number of limitations, including a lack of stability, expensive costs, and difficulty in recovering from them, that restrict their usefulness. As a method for attaching uniform metal complexes, covalent attachment is a particularly effective one. Since it allows for the production of catalysts that are acceptable to the environment, homogeneous heterogenization has been a hot research issue in recent decades. A wide range of materials, including carbon compounds, silicates, clays, organic polymers and metal-organic frameworks, have been studied for heterogenization. The development of homogeneous catalysts that are high-efficiency, recyclable, low-cost, & environmentally benign is dependent on the immobilisation of transition metal complexes onto support materials. Composite materials may be made using graphene oxide (GO), which is used as a precursor in the production of graphene-based goods on a large scale and at a cheap cost due to its electrical, mechanical, optical, and thermal capabilities. Due to the presence of hydroxyl, epoxy, carboxyl, and carbonyl groups, oxygen atom functional group modifications may serve as extra reactivity sites for focalism ions and complexes. A variety of T-metal complexes may be supported by it, making it an excellent choice.

Sb-complexes stand out from the crowd of other types of complexes. In part, this is due to their simple synthesis process and excellent features, which include bioactivity, catalysis, and optical sensing. Researchers have already looked at the antiviral and antitubercular properties of Sb metal complexes in the past. N=C-C=N linkages, as well as electron delocalization and prolonged conjugation, contribute to ligands' complexing activity. A complex's personality may be affected by this. Multicentered Sbl's, which are found in nature, were also used to create mono- and polynuclear complexes. These transition metal complexes, particularly the first row, have a wide range of applications in a variety of industries. More synthetic chemists are pursuing Schiff bases as a target material because of their advantageous features. Coordination with Mn ions like Cu, Mn, Fe, and Ni has been proven to boost the activity of certain Sb'-compounds employed as diverse O transport particles for living organisms; this has been shown for pathogenic fungus. There is much to learn about the fascinating physical and chemical properties

of M-complexes that combine Fe-ions and Sbl's, as well as their biological potential, when they are coordinated with a broad range of ts-ions. The core features of the related complexes may be dramatically altered by structural adjustments, which is one of the most fundamental characteristics of malls.

These compounds, which may link to monocyclic M-ions through several of the donor atoms in the synthesised ligand's cores, may yield good spectrum data, allowing a more complete structural investigation of the isolated complexes. The structures of these complexes were completely described by means of elemental analysis and spectral examinations. Antibacterial characteristics were the focus of the investigation. The geometric form of the Sbl' was optimised using the DFT/B3LYP method. Schiff base ligand binding to the receptors of *Bacillus subtilis* (5 h67), *Escherichia coli* (3 t88), *Proteus vulgaris* (5 i39), and *Staphylococcus aureus* (3ty7) was evaluated using molecular docking studies.

The interaction of the M-complex with DNA and amino acids plays a significant role in the reaction because of the therapeutic implications of this interaction. As a result of the influence of organic and inorganic complexes on biological processes, the fields of chemical biology, pharmacology, and medicine are all linked. Small chemical compounds have the ability to connect to DNA in an irreversible manner. Aflatoxin-B1 is a DNA binder that forms irreversible covalent connections with DNA. Noncovalent interactions, such as electrostatic interactions, intercalative contacts, major or minor nut binding, and major or minor nut binding, are involved in the process of reversible DNA binding. Multifunctional ligands used in metal-based medicinal treatments reduce antagonistic effects of metal ion overburden, significantly affect favoured metalloenzymes, and promote metal ion redistribution, all of which are caused by the ability of tiny organic molecules to significantly alter biological characteristics.

M-complexes are enhanced in terms of their pharmacological effects when a protein component is included in the ligand, since this allows them to target specific DNA binding through major/minor narrow interactions. The anticancer activity of ligands containing the indole moiety has been shown in a number of different cell lines. It has also been proven that M-complexes of ligands have antibacterial activity in the laboratory. The usage of M-complexes with precisely specified geometrical and electrochemical properties as DNA binding agents has been shown to be effective. “ Nickel (II) complexes with ligands containing nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms

have been found to have anticonvulsant and antiepileptic properties, as well as significant antibacterial, antifungal, antimicrobial, and anticancer activity. Zinc (II) complexes have been found to have anticancer activity, and copper (II) complexes have been found to have anticonvulsant and antiepileptic properties.

The increasing frequency of multidrug resistant microbiological diseases, as well as the potentially hazardous side effects of the antibiotics now in use, are the key challenges in modern antimicrobial treatment. As a consequence of these circumstances, it is vital to develop new approaches for better antibacterial therapy. Attempts to develop innovative medications by reengineering existing drugs to enhance bioavailability and antibacterial activity, for example, are being explored. Due to the vast variety of coordination properties and reactivity that transition metals exhibit, they are particularly well suited for the formation of complexes with organic ligands. Transition metal complexes have a variety of uncommon and fascinating features, such as the ability to alter oxidation states and the ability to form specialised interactions with other proteins, among others. A combination of certain metals and antibiotics, as a consequence, may be able to prevent bacteria from acquiring resistance, uncover novel mechanisms of action, and increase the antibiotic's antimicrobial qualities. The use of metaldrug complexes has been shown to be more effective than the use of the pure drug. The biological activity of Schiff base derivatives has been extensively studied, including their anticancer, antibacterial, antifungal, anticonvulsant, and antiviral properties. Recent studies have focused on the synthesis, classification, and bactericidal activity of transition M-complexes containing an amoxicillin-based Sb' , which was produced by condensation of amoxicillin antibiotic with 1, 2-diaminopyridine, as well as previous research, in order to achieve this goal, amo

Lanthanide complexes are of particular relevance in the fields of bioinorganic and coordination chemistry. Certain lanthanide compounds are used as magnetic resonance imaging contrast agents in biomedical, while others are used as catalysts in nuclear reactors. Because of their unusual luminescence, lanthanide complexes have inspired a great deal of interest in research and development as potential anticancer and antibacterial treatments. This is owing to the fact that they contain unique electrical structures that might be used to treat cancer and germs. Substituting metal ions for polydentate ligands, such as Schiff bases, results in the formation of highly structured supramolecular metal complexes. The binding sites & holes in these complexes

are occupied by a variety of cations, anions, and organic molecules. Sb' complexes derived from proteins are notable for their particular structural characteristics as well as their biological significance. Lanthanide Schiff base complexes provide a number of advantages over other types of complexes in luminescence studies because of their distinct structures. Rare-earth M-complexes of Sb-type ligands are being created due to their exceptional optical characteristics and vast diversity of biological applications. Lanthanide compounds have a wide range of cytotoxic properties that are difficult to categorise. The biological effects of novel Praseodymium (ii), Samarium (iii), Gadolinium (iii), Erbium (iii), Terbium (iii), and Ytterbium (iii) Sbl-complexes were explored as a result of the characteristics of these complexes. Praseodymium (ii), Samarium (iii), Gadolinium (iii), Erbium Several dangerous bacteria, including *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, and *Candida albicans*, as well as the fungus *Candida albicans*, were exposed to varying amounts of Schiff base compounds, according to the study. The antioxidant activity was further studied using the 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl radical scavenging method, which was developed by the National Institutes of Health.

Many bacterial strains have developed resistance to penicillins despite the fact that they are effective at preventing bacteria from forming cell walls. One such strain is "Staphylococcus aureus, MRSA is an acronym for methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus", which is a strain of Staphylococcus aureus that has been rendered resistant by a disease to the antibacterial action of methicillin and other penicillin-related medicines. MRSA strains are capable of producing penicillinases, which are enzymes that can break down and deactivate penicillins. Staph infections are among the most lethal human illnesses for which there are few or no drugs in late-stage development, further reducing the alternatives for effective and safe treatment solutions. Antibiotic resistance to lactam antibiotics such as PMP is most often caused by lactamases (enzymes that bind to enzymes that are involved in cell wall synthesis and cell division). In the presence of penicillinases, which are enzymes that may break down and deactivate penicillins, the antibiotic's antibacterial action has been shown to be ineffective against MRSA strains. As a consequence, in order to prevent medication resistance and severe side effects, the ligand nature or the way in which it interacts with M-ions must be altered. The use of metaldrug complexes has been shown to be more effective than the use of the pure drug. TM Sb' compounds have been extensively studied in the laboratory for many years and have found considerable use in a variety

of sectors of chemistry. In addition, some of these compounds have shown substantial biological activity in animal studies. A variety of biological features of Sb's and associated M-complexes have been investigated, including their genotoxicity, antimicrobial, and antifungal capabilities. This research on the preparation and characterisation of T-metal Schiff base complexes, including a PMP-derived Schiff base 3, which was produced by reacting free PMP 1 with 1,2-diaminobenzene, was carried out in order to determine whether complexation has an impact on the bactericidal properties of the compounds.

Compared to other bases, Schiff bases are unique in that they allow for the simple change of fragments at the exocyclic C=N bond, enabling for the investigation of important qualities including such tautomerism, conformational equilibria, acid–base and donor–acceptor properties, among others. The greatest property of azomethines, on the other hand, is their high proclivity to form complexes with other compounds. When forming macrocyclic complexes, the size of the internal cavities, the stiffness of the macrochains, and the nature of the S, N, and O atom donor atoms, as well as the characteristics of the metal ion engaged in coordination, all play a role. Recently, the use of azomethines and their metal complexes as metalloenzymes as well as for hosting and transporting small molecules or catalysis has attracted attention. The list includes substances such as lubricants, fuel additives, photochromic materials, physiologically active compounds, and other similar substances. Because of its favourable properties, the interaction of Sb M-complexes with proteins such as DNA and albumins has been extensively studied. In addition, the coordination chemistry of Sb' ligands has aroused the interest of researchers for decades. Schiff bases, which include azomethine, phenolic, or thiolic groups and can form coordinate bonds with a wide range of metal ions, have been used to synthesise metal complexes due to the simplicity with which they can be produced and the high metal binding capabilities they possess.

In recent years, there has been a resurgence of interest in coordination compounds containing physiologically active ligands. Significant changes in the biological properties of ligands and metal moieties occur as a result of chelation. It has been shown that chelation is involved in the causes and treatments of a range of ailments, including cancer. In recent years, the understanding of the binding of TM-complexes to DNA has become more significant in the development of DNA compound explorateur and chemotherapeutisch agents. There have been a plethora of

various complexes designed and developed in an attempt to locate anticarcinogens that can detect and disrupt DNA. Metals or ligands in these complexes may be modified in a straightforward manner to aid in the development of particular applications. This has resulted in a huge increase in the amount of current research that is conducted employing M-complexes of Sb's, which now covers a broad variety of problems in biocoordination and bioinorganic chemistry. The following is a summary of the current research: "A novel Schiff base ligand, namely 2,2'((1E,1'E) (1,3-phenylenebis(azanylylidene)) bis(methanylylidene)) diphenol (H2L), was synthesised; complexes were formed by reacting H2L with lanthanum (III), Erbium (III), and Ytterbium (III) chlor. An investigation was conducted into the antimicrobial and antifungal properties of innovative and diverse compounds in comparison to those of standard antibacterial and antifungal drugs against different species.

An essential element of pharmaceutical research is the development of novel, cost-effective, and potentially useful analogues of molecules with proven biological activity that have not yet been discovered. Splitting macromolecules is a critical enzymatic process in biotechnico chiropractic of genetic materialell, as well as noumenon biological applications in molecular life sciences, biotechnology, and medicine, as well as biosensors. The origin form is used to improve the actividad of the strong variable physical quantity while removing the negative effects or toxicity of the original medication. It has taken a long time to build chimic enzymes based on the Co-ordination environment, as well as the flexible redox assets of the core M-ion surrounded by the appropriate choice of ligands. Despite the fact that the wide range of medicinal applications of "2-aminobenzothiazole," "diketone," and their derivatives is well known, the chemistry of transition metal compounds with multidentate ligands has piqued researchers' interest for applications in biological, analytical, and pharmacological domains even though metal ions can have variable oxidation states and therefore can form M compounds with Sb ligands, the flexibility that can be improved by hydrogenation of their C = N bonds. A great deal of interest has been drawn to M-complexes of Nitrogen and Sulphur chelating agents as a result of their fascinating physicochemical features as well as their potent biological and pharmacological activities. Because of their anticancer activity when supplied as M-complexes, the ketones, which are structural phyto-polyphenols, have been shown to be neuroprotective against the effects of oxidants such as H₂O₂ in a cellulaire type of deformation oxidation. The nitrogen and sulphur are essential elements in the metals at the operative sites of many metallo-biomolecules.

Polyphenol, for example, has major neuroprotective qualities because it is a powerful scavenger of superoxide, which is a kind of free radical. A range of neurological illnesses may be prevented with the use of curcumin-based analogues, which have much more potential than conventional therapies. In the interaction of the ketone's active methylene group with an aldehydic group, the nonenolizable Knoevenagel condensate is formed, which has the potential to react with amines to create Schiff bases and other products. Because of the azomethine relationship, it has been shown that Schiff bases have a variety of biological activities, including the destruction of plants and the death of living creature features.

Since the 1950s, research into the anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of 2-aminobenzothiazole, polymers, flavouring and odour agents, and the luciferine responsible for bioluminescence has focused on hetero bicyclic ring systems based on 2-aminobenzothiazole's unique structure and importance as a medicinal chemistry. It was decided to use Congo red as a model dyeing pollutant because it has two azo groups in its chemical structure, the synthesis of macrocyclic complexes of novel elevated Schiff base with conjugated adaptable ligand derived from the condensation reaction of curcumin with 2-aminobenzothiazole as Schiff base and 2,2'-bipyridine as coligand. Single crystals were not extracted that were suitable for X-ray examination."

One of the most significant potential applications of inorganic compounds, such as metal complexes, is their anticancer properties. Because of the discovery of platinum-based medications such as cisplatin and carboplatin, which have the potential to be used as chemotherapeutic agents, there has been an increasing interest in the creation of nonplatinum metal complexes for use as pharmaceuticals. Several complexes comprising core metal ions such as copper, palladium, nickel, cobalt, and vanadium have been researched because of their biological activity. Copper, palladium, nickel, cobalt, and vanadium are just a few of the metals that have been examined. They are considered to be potential anticancer medicines, and they have been shown to outperform conventional anticancer medications in several cases. The production and use of complexes containing NO ligands, for example, has resulted in a number of therapeutic applications, including the treatment of fungal infections, the treatment of bacteria, and the treatment of cancer. It is being attempted to produce a new drug design that is more active and has fewer bad effects than existing medications. Many anticancer therapies, such as

organic compounds, inorganic complexes, and metal oxide nanoparticles, cause apoptosis in cancer cells, which is characterised by impaired cellular respiration. In recent years, because of the unique features of metal oxide nanoparticles, they have been used as catalysts, gas sensors and surfactants, as well as batteries, superconductors, and anticancer agents.

When compared to bulk materials, metallic nanoparticles exhibit much improved chemical, mechanical, and biological properties than do bulk materials. Investigations have been conducted on the ability of different nanoparticles to cause DNA damage, as well as their cytotoxicity and antibacterial properties. Nanoparticles may pose a greater threat to cancer cells than larger particles because of their increased surface area, improved capacity to move inside an organism, and chemical properties. Metal oxide nanoparticles offer unique features that have enabled them to be employed in a wide range of biological applications, including cancer therapy. Toxicity studies on cobalt and vanadium nanoparticles have not yet been completed for these metals. The cytotoxicity of nanoparticles, as well as their ability to kill cancer cells, were investigated in this study. No, we're just interested in the in vitro production, characterization, and anticancer activity of NO Schiff base complexes. This study tried to create and synthesise new Sb-complexes in order to test for cytotoxic qualities using the MTT assay, which was performed in this work. This study describes the synthesis, characterization, and solid structure evaluation of unique Cobalt (III), V (IV), and Copper (II) Schiff's complexes, as well as the results of the solid structure evaluation. According to previously reported findings, the Schiff's (HL1 and HL2), as well as the Cu (ii) complex, were synthesised and found by researchers.

Because of its well-known superior coordination abilities with various transition metals, the Imine (-RC=N-) group, which includes Schiff's base compounds, is a prominent area of research exclusively in coordination chemistry. The Imine (-RC=N-) group comprises Schiff's base compounds. Several natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic compounds include Schiff's bases, and the importance of the imine group in the biological system, particularly with respect to the transamination and racemization processes, has long been recognised. It is possible to produce Schiff base ligands by condensing a ketone or aldehyde with an amine in a condensation procedure. A number of anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and antiviral properties of Schiff's base ligand and related compounds have been established. The selectivity of Schiff's is being studied in particular because of their mode of manufacturing. After combining with metal ions, Schiff's bases form

stable complexes that are capable of stabilising metal ions in a variety of oxidation states while also enhancing biological activity. The core metal ions of these complexes serve as active sites for catalysing a number of chemical reactions in nature, as well as serving a variety of commercial purposes in biochemistry, food chemistry, medicine, and agricultural chemistry, among other fields. Chemicals containing transition metals (Cobalt, Nickel, Copper, Manganese and other elements) and manganese have been proven to have antibacterial properties against a variety of microorganisms. Additionally, Sbl's have been employed in organic photovoltaic materials and electrochemical sensing due to their unique properties, which include fluorescence, electroluminescence, catalytic activities, and nonlinear optical (NLO) capabilities. We have retained a strong interest in Schiff's base ligand chemistry with donor atoms because of the vast variety of applications it may be applied to (N, S and O). These azomethine-containing Schiff's bases are used as a reactant in the creation of complex compounds that are both physiologically and industrially active. This is accomplished by ring closure reactions. The antibacterial, antiviral, and antifungal properties of several semicarbazone complexes have been hypothesised. The creation of semicarbazone metal complexes and the evaluation of their chemical features is also a viable approach for the development of biological system models. On the one hand, the present work offers a novel synthesis technique for manganese (ii) and cobalt(ii) complexes with a semicarbazone ligand (L) in the presence of a furan ring (Figure), on the other, it discusses their biological activity against two fungi and bacteria.

Figure 2.13 2-Acetyl-5-methylfuransemicarbazone

A striking similarity was found between the metal grammatical category found in N and C based group macrocyclic Sbl's and that found in metallic proteins, where the needed metal was attached in a macrocyclic incavo or split formed by the protein's conformational analysis, respectively. Metal ions may be coupled to proteins such as monoclonal antibodies, allowing for the development of novel instruments for biology and medicine research and development Those ligands were thought to be crucial because they had the ability to produce an umbworld with a controlled form and ligand strength, according to theory. It was revealed that bi-functional chelating compounds, which were used for such attachments, were also excellent catalysts for the breakdown of the phosphate-esterbond during the research. With the use of macrocyclic ligands and their guests, researchers were able to examine fundamental aspects of intramolecular chemistry. They had a significant impact on a wide variety of industries, including chemistry, medicine, and technological advancement. It has been predicted that there would be an increase in interest in exploring the electrochemistry of (reduction and oxidation processes) as a result of the biological significance of the less prevalent oxidation number of Cu and Ni. The comparative thermodynamic equilibrium of the 2-oxidation number in a specific ligand atmosphere was shown to be the most critical factor in determining Cu (II)/Cu (II) redox potentials in a variety of ligand environments (I).

It is possible that the biological activity of metal complexes is related to their redox properties. Mixed ligand complexes have been utilised as active catalysts in a variety of biological, industrial, and environmental processes, including the oxydation and hydrolysis of unsaturated fatty acids, hydrogenation of hydrogen, and carboxylation of CH₃. There was a significant amount of significance associated with the usage of ambivalent ligand compounds that included amino acids as a secondary ligand, and because of their stability, they could be utilised to create enzym M-ion substrate molecules. The majority of the metal complexes containing 8-hydroxyquinoline were shown to be biologically active, with the exception of a few. In this research, "the preparation, "characterization, and antimicrobial properties of two Schiff base ligands obtained from the condensation of quinolone 2-aldehyde with 2-amino pyridine (La) and the condensation of oxamide with furfural (Lb) as primary ligands and 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylic acid as secondary ligand (Lc) as secondary ligands, as well as their transition metal complexes, are discussed In addition, a molecular docking study was undertaken in order to offer new information on how metal complexes function and interact.

Sb's are a significant class of chemical ligands that coordinate to M-ions through a C=N link. They are produced via the condensation of a 10-amine with an aromatic aldehyde molecule, which is a common reaction in organic chemistry. Multiidentate Sbl's have played an important role in the development of Co-ordination Chemistry, owing to the fact that they generate a reasonably stable complex with a large number of TM-ions. Schiff base nitrogen donor ligands have received a great deal of attention due to their combined hard-soft donor character and flexible coordination behaviour, as well as their biological activities, which include toxicity against bacterial growth, anticancer activity, and other biochemical characteristics. Schiff base nitrogen donor ligands are also being studied for their anticancer activity and other biochemical characteristics. M-complexes derived from Sb's have received a great deal of attention because of their potential use in industry, as well as their antifungal, antibacterial, anticancer, and herbicidal properties in the laboratory. Many authors have been interested by the potential of tetradentate SBs, which include a N2O2 donor atom and can be configured to coordinate with various metal ions, to interact with different metal ions. Many studies have been carried out on the reactivity of tetradentate Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or its derivatives with ethylenediamine in order to understand how they work. Schiff base transition metal complexes are used in the production of antibacterial and anticancer drugs, efficient pharmaceuticals in the area of pharmacology, excellent homogeneous and heterogeneous phase catalysts, and chemosensors, to name a few applications. Cancer is a malignant condition characterised by uncontrolled cell development and a reduction in the rate of apoptosis (cell death).

In medicine, cisdiammine dichloroplatinum (II) is the first metallodrug to be used therapeutically as an anticancer drug (cisplatin). In spite of the fact that cisplatin has shown to be quite effective in treating a range of tumours, it has a number of side effects, the most important of which is renal damage. When arsenic was revealed to be a chemotherapeutic drug, scientists were able to develop new transition metal-based compounds for cancer treatment. Our prior work included the development and characterisation of bidentate and polydentate ligands composed of N and O donors and their M-compounds, with an emphasis on their photophysical properties and biological nature. In the work detailed here, the drug structures of a newly discovered tetradentate ligand as well as various TM-complexes were determined via the use of analytical and spectroscopic techniques. Also tested for anticancer action are the MCF7 cell line as a control and the L929 (mouse fibroblast) cell line as a model, both of which were used in

conjunction with the complexes. A method called B3LYP/LANL2DZ was utilised to optimise the complexes in the gas state, and structural characteristics were taken into consideration. In order to correlate the anticancer investigation with quantum chemical features (such as the energy of the highest-occupied molecular orbital, the energy gap among LUMO and HOMO, softness, and nucleophilicity index (N)), a novel formula was established using matrix analysis.

A variety of medicinal applications have been demonstrated for the Schiff base and chromones compounds against Mythemna. The Sb's-complexes have been demonstrated to have biological, therapeutic, and pharmacological applications in a number of investigations, including antimicrobial, fungicidal, cancer-fighting, antioxidant, anti-HIV, anti-inflammatory, and insecticidal activity. In the course of investigating 4-amino-2, 6-dihydroxy pyrimidine and its Schiff base complexes, it was discovered that the molecule has a diverse spectrum of biological applications. Based on previous research, we are interested in investigating the therapeutic uses of Schiff base-generated 3-formyl chromone and 4-amino-2,6dihydroxy pyrimidine, as well as their complexes, in particular. On the basis of the foregoing information, this research focuses on the preparation, characterisation, and medicinal applications of newly synthesised Sbl's based on "chromone-3-carbaldehyde and 4-amino-2,6 dihydroxy pyrimidine (H2L) and their Cobalt (II), Nickel (II), Copper (II), and Cadmium (II) complexes, as well as their Cobalt (I II), Nickel (I In order to describe the shape of L and M compounds, various techniques such as elemental analysis, molar conductance, thermal analysis, Inductive Coupled Plasma, magnetic moment measurements, x-ray powder diffraction, infrared, mass, 1H-Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, 13C-Nuclear Magnetic Resonance", Ultraviolet-Visible, and ESR spectrum investigations are used. It was discovered that the synthesised compounds possessed anticancer, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties. Molecular modelling was used to investigate the ligand and M-complexes. The goal of the structure activity connection research was to establish a link between the chemical characteristics and biological activity of the substances investigated. The "DNA binding of complexes with calf thymus-DNA" was investigated using viscosity measurements and electronic absorption spectrum titration, among other techniques.

Due to rapid advances in molecular biology and amino acid chemistry knowledge, a broad class of compounds has been developed that can now be used to better understand the biological functions of macrocyclic proteins. Free amino acids, such as D-L-homocysteic acid, have been

proposed as agonists of endogenous glutamate receptors in the mammalian central nervous system, which are involved in a variety of physiological activities. Due to the finding of the efficacy of these chemicals, much research into the properties of D, L-homocysteic acid in neuroanatomy, electrophysiology, and pharmacology has been carried out since their discovery. Potent donor sites in amino acids, as well as a broad class of mettalic-based complexes including Carboxylic groups and/or amino groups, have a high potential to form complexes with metal cations. The existence of important metal elements in the human body is generally acknowledged, and these elements perform critical tasks and interact with a broad range of biological components. Metal elements are also known to play a role in the production of certain enzymes.

Investigating the chemical coordination and behaviour of such molecules might be important in order to have a comprehensive understanding of their physiological function. With the expansion of the current study on Sb M-complexes, it now encompasses a wide range of topics, including their many characteristics in bio-coordination chemistry. It has been demonstrated that the presence of M-ions bound to physiologically active compounds increases the activity of the compounds. Coordination/chelation with metal ions, according to our current findings, causes "non-biologically active molecules to become active and less biologically active compounds to become more active." The authors present a series of antibacterial and antiviral amino acid-derived Schiff bases (L1–L5) that were produced by the condensation reaction of aromatic aldehydes with amino acids such as glycine, alanine, methionine, and cysteine. These Schiff bases (L1–L5) have antibacterial and antiviral properties. In this study, metal complexes of the type $K_2 [M(L)_2]$ [where M = Cobalt (II), Copper (II), Nickel (II), and Zinc (II)] were synthesised using these Schiff bases. All of the Schiff base ligands, as well as their metal complexes, were tested in vitro against four Gram-negative (*E. coli*, *S. flexenari*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S.*

Transition metal complexes of multidentate heterocyclic ligands containing N donor sites have gained popularity as a result of their diverse structural characteristics, varied ligational behaviour, beneficial biological actions, and potential applications in medicine, materials research, and catalysis. Metal complexes, particularly those containing sp^2 hybrid N in the aromatic system of the ligands, offer a wide range of medical applications in a variety of fields.

Schiff bases containing nitrogen aromatic moieties act as good ligands for transition metal ions, forming complexes with them that are both stable and stable to oxidation. Furthermore, several quinoxaline derivatives have been shown to have a wide range of therapeutic effects, including anti-inflammatory and antidepressant qualities. This is in addition to its use as a reagent and chemical synthesis. Sodium borohydride (Sbl) compounds derived from quinoxaline are commonly employed in the creation of M-complexes that have a diverse variety of forms and applications in analytical, industrial, and medical research. The formation of Schiff bases of 3-hydrazinylquinoxalin-2-(1H)-one has piqued the attention of researchers due to the projected coordination properties of the ligands and their considerable pharmacological activities. Benzimidazole may also be found in a wide range of natural and synthetic chemical compounds. As an essential component of vitamin B₁₂'s structure and its broad range of biological activities, which include antioxidant, antihistamine, and antiallergic properties, DNA binding properties, and anticancer properties, it is a valuable scaffold in the development of a variety of therapeutic medicines, including anticancer agents.

Coordination chemistry is one of the most exciting areas of science. One of the most fascinating parts is the interaction of TM-ions with biological molecules. The compounds known as M-complexes are employed as medications and chemotherapeutic agents in a range of applications. Iron is an essential mineral that may work as a regulator, activator, transmitter, and controller in a range of enzymatic processes. It is found in a variety of foods and can be found in a variety of minerals. Iron compounds have received a great deal of interest as a consequence of their biological significance, which includes antiviral, antiproliferative, and anticancer properties. Because of the efficacy of orally administered iron chelators and medicines for the treatment of iron overload, the stability and coordination chemistry of iron (III) with bidentate ligands has been altered. BZH isoxazoles are an important class of heterocyclic pharmaceuticals and bioactive compounds. They are employed as antipsychotics and HIV treatments, as well as being involved in a wide range of organic processes, including the formation of benzo[1,2-c]isoxazoles. In critical synthetic processes such as the reductive ring opening of isoxazoles, isoxazole metal complexes are widely suggested as intermediates to be used as intermediates. The isoxazole metal complexes have been reported and fully characterised in various publications. In a study of the investigation of isoxazole M-complexes, the binding nature of the isoxazoles in the compounds has been investigated, and some early results about the regularity of

isoxazole complexation behaviour have been provided. Schiff bases, on the other hand, are a significant class of organic ligands with important biological characteristics. Schiff bases are found in a wide range of natural products. In coordination chemistry, Schiff bases provide a number of advantages over ligands in a variety of applications. In coordination chemistry, they are the most studied ligands because of their structural variety and peculiar characteristics. In response to these observations, two new fluorescent aromatic Schiff base ligands were developed from "2-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-alkyl-3H-imidazo [4',5':3,4] benzo [1,2-c] isoxazol-5-amine and their Iron (III) complexes. The antibacterial abilities of the new ligands and complexes were tested against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria."

Figure 2.14 Schiff's base compounds are intriguing and flexible ligands

Schiff's base compounds are fascinating and versatile ligands due to the ease with which they may be coordinated to a range of transition metals through the imine functional group, which serves as a good N-donor in many cases. Salicylaldimine ligands have been demonstrated to promote metal ion chelation as well as to increase the stability of a metal centre in several studies. In the past, salicylaldimine-based ligands have been utilised to synthesise metallomesogens and optical metal ions, as well as to catalyse enantioselective processes. Sb' M-complexes are used in a variety of industries, pharmaceuticals, and catalysis, to name a few.

Metal Sb'-complexes are used as reagents in a variety of reactions including oxidation, aziridination, cyclopropanation, polymer, epoxidation, and heteroDiels–Alder processes. A important class of bioactive chemicals, sb' metal compounds include molluscicidal, antibacterial, antifungal, and other biological characteristics in addition to their metal chemistry. Scientists are becoming more interested in the wide variety of applications for molecules containing azo groups, which include medical treatments, indicators, and organic colours. It is also crucial to note that in both medical and pharmaceutical chemistry, compounds containing both azo and imine (-C=N-) functional groups are relevant structures. Even though a number of metal complexes with various substituted salicylaldimine ligands have been found so far, metal complexes with azo moieties attached to the salicylaldimine scaffold are still rather rare. In the

presence of an azo group, the chemical, physical, and biological features of the resulting complexes may be considerably altered, according to the literature.

Because of the presence of the azomethine group (-CH=N-) and the structural similarities between natural biological and nonnatural species, the highly effective chelating agent Schiff base moieties has piqued the interest of researchers around the world who are interested in therapeutic applications. As medications, Sb' and complexes have been utilised for a wide range of applications, including the treatment of microorganisms, fungi, and some kinds of tumours, as well as the investigation of a wide range of biochemical, clinical and pharmacological properties. Metal complexes are currently extensively employed in cancer diagnosis and therapy, and their applications are expanding. Due to their shown chemotherapeutic efficiency, platinum complexes are today considered one of the foundations of cancer therapy. For their part, platinum complexes have been shown to be less effective than chemotherapy against a wide range of common cancers due to intrinsic drug resistance, to be of limited therapeutic value in a small number of tumours, and to cause a variety of side effects, including nerve damage, hair loss and nausea. The development of innovative medicine candidates with greater potency, selectivity, and fewer bad effects is now underway to overcome these limits. Some ruthenium-based compounds have been produced and tested against cancer cell lines, which are potential research avenues to pursue. The severe side effects of these molecules are less severe when compared to those of platinum-based drugs.

Ruthenium has received a great deal of interest as a building block for innovative new metalloid pharmaceuticals in the area of transition metal synthetic chemistry because of its low overall toxicity, which contrasts with the pharmacological features of platinum medications. Several factors have been proposed as explanations, including cancer cells' preferential absorption of ruthenium compounds via the transferrin cycle and mechanisms such as activation by reduction (activation by reduction). To understand more about the anticancer effects of novel ruthenium complexes, which were generated by combining "Ru₃(CO)₁₂ with a new family of monodentate V-shaped Schiff base ligands," the authors set out to conduct their research. They are created by mixing 3'-aminoacetophenone and 4'-aminoacetophenone with benzaldehyde derivatives such as 4-bromobenzaldehyde, 4-(dimethylamino) benzaldehyde, and 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde, among other things. The composition and formulas of the compounds that were discovered as a

result of this study were investigated utilising a range of physiochemical and spectroscopic techniques. The anticancer activity of ligands and their ruthenium compounds against liver carcinoma, breast carcinoma, and colon carcinoma cell lines was evaluated in vitro, and the results were compared to those of cisplatin and doxorubicin.

In recent years, the preparation of Schiff bases "containing $>C=O$, $>C=N$, $>C=N$ groups with potential ligating ability" has received a great deal of attention because of their applications as chelating agents, analytical reagents, metal indicators in complexometric titrations, and colorimetric reagents, as well as biochemical research. The structure of the amine moiety, which regulates the effectiveness of the conjugation and may include structural features capable of modul

"Copper (II) complexes have either four or six coordination geometry, with only a few exceptions; Cu(II) in the $3d^9$ form is particularly interesting because it represents a simple one-hole magnetic system; the introduction of Schiff bases with an O–N–O donor set to Cu(II) complexes containing triphenylphosphine was carried out because of the rich photophysical and catalytic characteristics of organometallic copper(II) complexes; Tridentate Schiff bases were created by combining anthranilic acid with salicylaldehyde/2-hydroxy-1-naphthalene/o-hydroxyacetophenone/o-vanillin and forming a tridentate Schiff base.

The study of metal organic complexes is one of the most active fields of materials science and research at the moment. Significant progress has been achieved in the field of these materials as a result of their fascinating features and potential in a wide range of applications. A major focus of current research is the preparation of novel Schiff bases and M-complexes, because they "easily form stable complexes with most transition metals, Schiff bases have played a significant role in the development of coordination chemistry, they exhibit unique properties such as the ability to reversibly bind oxygen, catalytic activity in alkene hydrogenation, amino group transfer, photochromic capabilities, and the ability to bind dangerous metal complexes." Schiff bases have played a significant role. These applications were motivated by the capacity of transition metals to create certain intricate combinations with other elements. Only a few research on Schiff base ligands, such as aromatic aldehydes and amino acids, have focused on the practical use of these compounds. The discovery of metal complex coordination geometries was made possible by the use of ligands derived from substituted salicylaldimine. Among the many different chemical variations available in copper (II)-containing compounds is the fact that they may include not

only different coordination geometries but also different ligand modifications. Bond length variations and deviations from projected ligand geometry are typical in complexes containing 4, 5, or 6 donors or large tetrahedral 'distortions,' as well as in complexes including four, five, or six donors. It has come to our attention that there have been many reports of so-called "stepped" or "umbrella" distortions, along with deviations from polarizability and strange bond lengths. Schiff bases have the potential to establish a new class of pharmaceuticals via immunological potentiation and therapeutic potential; complex combinations of Schiff bases with metallic ions result in a group of molecules with the most critical characteristics in terms of chemical and biological activity. According to the findings of the study, the compound reaction of Schiff bases with a variety of M ions has antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties.

Scientists have been intrigued by azobenzene derivatives, which are photochromic chemicals that have previously been documented in the scientific literature, for a long period of time. In actuality, these compounds offer a great deal of promise because of their ease of production, reversible trans-cis isomerization, outstanding equilibrium, and several applications. Azobenzene derivatives photoisomerize from the thermally equilibrium T-isomer to the cis isomer when exposed to ultraviolet light, whereas visible light causes the inverse transition when exposed to the same light source. Azobenzene compounds may be employed in a variety of applications, including optical switches and molecular machines, as a consequence of this approach. These compounds exhibit a wide range of biological features.. Chemicals that are flexible and have a broad variety of applications are used to produce Schiff bases. There have been significant contributions to the pharmaceutical industry from antimicrobials to antidepressants to cytotoxics to analgesics to antileishmanials to anticonvulsants to fungicides to anti-inflammatory and anticancer drugs. Schiff bases are favoured ligands in coordination chemistry because they are capable of forming stable complexes with transition metals. Cu and Zn Schiff base complexes, which are essential elements for humans and have a wide range of biological activities, are of special scientific interest because they are essential elements for people and have a range of biological functions. In this report, we describe the preparation of novel $[Zn(L)_2]$ and $[Cu(L)_2]$ complexes containing an azo Schiff base ligand (L) formed via condensation of 2-hydroxy5-(tolylidiazonyl)benzaldehyde and propylamine, X-ray crystallographic analysis of complexes, $[Zn(L)_2]$ and $[Cu(L)_2]$ revealed the ligand coordination sites as well as the monitored using Ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometrically, the antibacterial screening of ligand L and the two

metal complexes against four dangerous bacteria (one Gram-positive coccus (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and three Gram-negative bacteria)" is also described here.

The chemistry of organotin (IV) complexes of Schiff bases was motivated by the biocidal and anticancer capabilities of organotin (IV) complexes of Schiff bases, as well as the behaviour of Schiff bases as a model for biological systems. There have been a significant number of Schiff bases synthesised and extensively researched because they possess certain distinguishing characteristics, such as the manifestation of novel structural forms, thermal stability, biological relevance and relevance to therapeutics, as well as a high degree of synthesis flexibility and therapeutic value. In addition to their antimalarial and anti-inflammatory qualities, Schiff bases also have anticancer, anti-HIV, and anticancer features, and they have been used to create a number of prospective pharmaceuticals. Schiff bases have been used to generate a number of possible drugs. It has also been proven that Sb' M-complexes formed from salicylaldehyde cause DNA damage in an unexpected manner. Additionally, salicylaldimines are currently a hot topic due to their fascinating physical and chemical properties, which include various aspects of photoanalytical chemistry. Salicylaldimines are generally used as a precursor for the design of novel M-complexes and as an excellent model for B6 vitamins, but they also have fascinating physical and chemical properties that include various aspects of photoanalytical chemistry. The structural alteration of an organic molecule has a wide range of biological effects. The ability of a biomolecule to function is significantly determined by its ability to coordinate with metal ions. The researchers discovered vanadium (IV, V) and copper(ii) compounds of Sb', which were generated from salicylaldehyde and 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole, and they presented their findings. The organotin (IV) complexes formed by this flexible ligand have never been before synthesised. The synthesis, spectral characterization, thermal and biological behaviour of Hsal-ambmz organotin (IV) complexes of Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole are described in this paper in order to investigate the effect of an organic group on the anti-inflammatory activity of organotin (IV) complexes of Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde and 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole.

In recent years, researchers have discovered that cis-platin is a highly effective anti-cancer therapy, and that it is the target of many regularly used platinum-based therapies. As a result, DNA has come to be recognised as a critical target for anti-cancer drugs. Pharmaceuticals used

to treat cancer that covalently bind the polynucleotide, such as platinum, might cause serious side effects in certain patients. As a consequence, there has been an increase in interest in the studies of DNA not covalent link recognition by small molecules, which is a relatively new field. However, despite the fact that a greater number of these complexes have been extensively used, and some have even been utilised in clinical studies, the severe side effects and lack of selectivity associated with them have caused a steady decline in interest. "The identification of more specific biological targets, such as proteins, enzymes, and cell surface receptors, has diminished the original attraction of DNA as a target." DNA-based treatments, on the other hand, have been given a fresh lease of life as a result of recent findings in non-canonical structural arrangements of DNA that may play a role in carcinogenic events. It has been shown that the length of telomeres may self-organize into guanine-quadruplexes, which are four-stranded DNA structures (G4). The presence of G4 sequences, which are G-rich sequences that, in general, may produce highly "polymorphic 4-stranded structures with stacked guanine tetrads connected by looping, DNA bases and maintained by a central alkali ion channel, the nature of the central ion, the relative direction of the strands, the syn or anti glycosidic conformation, and the length of the sequence connecting the strands," as well as the folding G4s in telomeres have been shown to have a role in maintaining chromosomal integrity by inhibiting an enzyme that is activated to lengthen telomeric overhangs and increase cell lifespan. Given that the human genome has over 350 000 guaninerich sequences, the finding was particularly significant; for example, the proto-oncogene c-myc contains a putative G4-DNA in its Nuclease Hypersensitive Region. Multiple cancers have been related to aberrant overexpression of the c-myc gene, and several G4s motifs in promoter provinces have been postulated as potential transcriptional control molecular switches. There have also been reports of G4 structures being found in RNA G-rich regions, and these structures seem to play a role in post-transcriptional gene expression regulation. The goal of the research collection has been to construct or produce small molecule ligands that selectively bind to G4-DNA, which is known to halt the growth of cells. The compounds that have been discovered to be capable of stabilising a G4 structure have distinct characteristics, such as a π -delocalized system, a certain service group that can interact with the nut and can π -stack with G-quartets. Transition metal ions functionalized with planar aromatic organic molecules have recently been discovered to be capable of stabilising a G4 structure. Because of an electron withdrawing effect, the presence of a metal ion lowers the electron density on

coordinated aromatic ligands, which promotes stronger π interactions with the G-quartets. Additionally, by occupying the core of a G-tetrad and ideally continuing the central ion channel typically produced by alkali metal cations, the metal ion improves electrostatic G4 stability. The development of G4-DNA binders is largely concerned with the selectivity of their binding sites. When bound to a G4-DNA structure, the ligand has a high affinity for it and will recognise the G4-DNA rather than the duplex B-DNA. A new class of G4 DNA stabilisers has been discovered in the form of "cationic Salphen-like metal complexes," which were previously recognised as B-DNA binders. Developing "a series of square planar transition metal complexes with salphen-like N, N'-bridged tetradentate donors" that have a high affinity and selectivity for human telomeric DNA stabilisers is the focus of this research.

Structure of the ML_2^{2+} complex (1: $M=Ni$, 2: $M=Cu$, 3: $M=Zn$: H_2L^{2+} = N, N'-bis-5-triethyl ammonium methyl)-salicylidene-2,3-naphthalendiimine)

Figure 2.15 ML_2^{2+} ($M=Nickel$, $Copper$, and $Zinc$),

To increase the selectivity of M-complexes over B-DNA, the binding affinity of three square-planar anion exchange complexes, ML_2^{2+} ($M = Nickel$, $Copper$, and $Zinc$), which were recently generated and described by a range almost planar area, was compared to that of B-DNA. The goal was to expand the library of Sb' G4-binding M-complexes and increase their selectivity over B-DNA. "We were able to monitor the metal complex-G4 interaction and differentiate the quadruplex fold from other designs, utilising computational chemistry methods, atomistic models of supra-molecular metal complex-G4 binding complexes were constructed, and we were able to

show the impact of the chosen medicines on DNA processing using in vitro polymerase chain reaction assays," according to the researchers. The antiproliferative effect of the chemical was further investigated in the cancer cell lines HeLa and MCF-7, respectively.

The selective oxidation of alkenes is widely recognised as an essential and basic process in synthetic chemistry because of the vast variety of applications it has in this field. For this reason, cyclohexene epoxidation is one of the most essential processes in organic synthesis. Epoxide molecules are crucial building blocks for medicines, agrochemicals, and food additives, among other applications. In recent years, several efforts have been made to develop systems for the manufacture of epoxides that make use of efficient catalysts while operating in ecologically friendly conditions. When it comes to oxidation, one of the most essential objectives is to choose oxidant reagents that boost the efficiency of the atoms. Some of the oxidants employed in the epoxidation of alkenes include peracids, organic peroxides, H_2O_2 , and molecular oxygen, which are all instances of peroxides. Peracids, organic peroxides, H_2O_2 , and molecular oxygen are examples of peroxides. Because it is less expensive and more environmentally friendly than H_2O_2 , molecular oxygen has recently gained popularity as an oxidant for the epoxidation of olefins. Because it is less expensive and more environmentally friendly than H_2O_2 , it is being utilised more and more.

Although it is reactive toward the strong C-H bond, it is normally unreactive toward it until it is activated by exceptionally efficient catalysts. A range of homogeneous catalysts containing molecular O_2 have been developed as a consequence of this research. The results have been published in peer-reviewed journals and published in peer-reviewed journals. "Metalloporphyrins, metal phthalocyanines, transition metal oxides, salen-metal complexes, and heteropoly acid are among the catalysts that have been discovered to successfully catalyse the epoxidation of cyclohexene with molecular oxygen." However, the production of metal phthalocyanines is difficult and necessitates the use of a large amount of toxic solvents; transition metal oxides are easy to work with but have lower conversion and selectivity than other catalysts. When used in the epoxidation of cyclohexene, cyclohexene is converted to cyclohexene and a metal phthalocyanine is formed. Sb ligands, which share structural characteristics with metalloporphyrins, are an important family of ligands that play critical roles in catalysis and chemical synthesis, as well as having a wide variety of applications in analytical,

biological, and industrial sectors. M-complexes with Sb' show catalytic activity, as demonstrated by substantial research in a number of activities, including epoxidation and keton reduction (Figure 1). In recent years, Sb' metal complexes have been widely used to catalyse the oxidation of alkenes because of their high catalytic activity and selectivity in the epoxidation of alkenes. A number of Schiff-base complexes have been employed to catalyse the epoxidation of styrene under mild conditions, and the cyclohexene oxidation catalyst Cobalt (II) Schiff-base complex, which o-Aminophenol (AP) and 2,6-pyridinedicarbaldehyde (PDC), which was synthesised from 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylic acid, were used to produce the four pyridine Schiff base ligands L1, L2, L3, and L4 in order to develop a universal method for cyclohexene epoxidation with molecular O₂ using direct catalytic epoxidation and investigate the possibilities for creating " In this study, the synthesis and description of four novel pyridine Schiff-base Mn(II) complexes, that were employed to catalyse the epoxidation of cyclohexene under Mukaiyama conditions with molecular oxygen as the oxidant, were followed by investigations into the stability and catalytic effectiveness of these complexes. The stability and catalytic effectiveness of these complexes were investigated.

Figure 2.16 Schiff base-manganese (II) complexes

When dyes from industrial wastewater are not properly handled, they have a significant detrimental influence on the environment, leading to a loss of biodiversity in aquatic environments. They also contribute to the poisoning of water supplies and the desertification of the environment. Consequently, hazardous goods containing dye must be handled before disposal. A range of physicochemical procedures are used to treat industrial effluent as a consequence of this. However, these treatments have a poor removal effectiveness and need significant financial investment in the pigment removal process. While biopolymer metal complexes, on the other hand, perform more effectively as photocatalysts for dye degradation, the elimination of hazardous compounds from the environment is typically complete. Because of its physicochemical properties, chitosan may be used in a variety of different applications. It is used in a number of different industries, including biology, pharmacology, biomedicine, and industry, among others.

A variety of chemical modification procedures are available to enhance the material's physical and chemical qualities. The carboxymethylation of chitosan is advantageous because it makes use of inexpensive catalysts and produces a product that is environmentally friendly, water soluble, non-toxic in nature, and has a metal affinity, as well as having medicinal and industrial applications. TM-complexes are formed as a result of this characteristic (chelation), and they are used in a variety of chemical, photo-chemical, and photo-biological degradation processes. An increasing number of these M-complexes are being used to degrade and remove organic pollutants such as CO₂ and H₂O. Its pH value is 3. Methylene blue (MB) is an acidic azo dye with a pH value of 3. When used in the textile industry, it binds strongly to the interstitial while of cotton fibres and is securely fixed to fabric; "a number of biopolymer photocatalyzed organic dye removers have been described in recent research; Among the materials studied were zinc oxide nanoflowers, cellulose nanocrystals, chitosan nanocomposite, cellulose microfibers, and chitosan microspheres. Other materials studied included nanoparticles, nanosheets, multi-walled nanotubes, nanomaterials, nanostructure compounds, and various types of metal complexes, such as "tri-nuclear complexes," "bi-nuclear complexes," and other types of Sb' biopolymer contains copper (ii) compounds derived from the biopolymer O-carboxymethyl chitosan. The benefits of the sustainable catalysts that have been developed are biocompatibility, photodegradability, low cost, stability, environmental friendliness, ease of accessibility, and reusability.

3.1 Results and discussion

Here I am proposing my Scheme:

The new ligand, (*E*)-2-((3-aminopyrazin-2-yl)methylene)-*N*-phenylhydrazine-1-carbothioamide and its metal(II) complexes are stable at room temperature and non-hygroscopic. However, at higher temperatures, the ligand undergoes melting while the complexes decompose without melting. The ligand is soluble in MeOH, EtOH, CHCl_3 , DMF, and DMSO and the complexes are only soluble in dimethyl sulfoxide and dimethylformamide. The authenticities of the synthesized compounds were ascertained using various spectroscopic methods and elemental analysis. The theoretical percent values of the elements in the complexes have been calculated for the formulations given in Table 6.1 to indicate that experimental values agree, within the experimental error, with calculated values.

Table 3.1 Analytical, molar conductance and physical parameters for the ligand and its metal complexes

Molecular formula	Elemental analyses: Found (Calculated)				
	C	N	H	M	Molar Cond. (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)
[Co(3-APPHC)2Cl2]	50.93 (51.00)	13.66 (13.72)	3.65 (3.62)	9.69 (9.62)	12
[Ni(3-APPHC)2Cl2]	50.97 (51.02)	13.67 (13.73)	3.58 (3.62)	9.52 (9.59)	16
[Cu(3-APPHC)2Cl2]	50.58 (50.62)	13.59 (13.62)	3.55 (3.59)	10.25 (10.30)	19
[Zn(3-APPHC)2Cl2]	50.41 (50.47)	13.54 (13.58)	3.55 (3.58)	10.50 (10.57)	15
[Pd(3-APPHC)Cl2]	37.37 (37.30)	10.09 (10.04)	2.59 (2.65)	25.31 (25.42)	11
[Cd(3-APPHC)Cl2]	36.91 (36.78)	9.98 (9.90)	2.64 (2.61)	(26.59) (26.48)	16

3.1.1 Spectroscopic characterization

The positions of the selected characteristic IR bands unambiguously unveiled the formation of new ligand 4-(2-aminopyridin-3-methylene)aminobenzoic acid and its metal complexes. The important absorption frequencies are presented in Table 6.2. The ligand showed the strong band at 1629 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, on the other hand, this band was lowered by 20-30 cm⁻¹ in the complexes pointing to the fact that the nitrogen of this group is involved in binding with the metal ion [23-25]. The amine group nitrogen of the ligand showed the band at 3420 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$ has been found at lower frequencies by (3401-3371 cm⁻¹) in the complexes, this kind of shift suggested that amine nitrogen is bonded to the metal [26,27]. The carboxylic acid (C=O) and (C=N)_{py} stretching frequencies of the ligand occurred at 1701 and 1567 cm⁻¹. These bands do not undergo any perceptible shifts in the metal complexes suggesting that there are no

interactions between oxygen and nitrogen of these groups. The aforementioned results proved that the ligand coordinate with metal ions through amine nitrogen atom and azomethine nitrogen. In the complexes, the other peaks observed in the region of 478-520 cm^{-1} and 275-321 cm^{-1} correspond to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ and $\nu(\text{M-Cl})$, respectively. The conductance measurements of the metal complexes in DMF solution were made at 10^{-3} mol.dm^{-3} concentrations. All the complexes show only residual molar conductance values (11-19 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and hence they may be considered non-electrolytes [28,29]. This implies that both the two chloride anions associated with these complexes are present inside the coordination sphere. The electronic and magnetic data are given in Table 3.3. The UV-Visible spectrum of the ligand exhibited bands at 30390 cm^{-1} and 33245 cm^{-1} corresponding to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, respectively. The electronic spectra of Co(II) complex exhibits three bands around 9000 cm^{-1} [${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (ϑ_1)], 18500 cm^{-1} [${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (ϑ_2)] and 20400 cm^{-1} attributable to [${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ (ϑ_3)], respectively, characteristic of octahedral geometry [30,31]. The octahedral geometry of Co(II) complex also supports $\vartheta_2 / \vartheta_1$ (2.02) values [32]. The Racah interelectronic repulsion parameter (B) value for Co(II) complex was found to be 756 cm^{-1} which is lower than the free ion value ($B_1 = 971 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicating a good overlap of the orbitals involved [33]. Further, the nephelauxetic effect parameter ($\beta = B/B_1$) value (0.78) is less than one suggesting that ML bonds are covalent in character. The Ni(II) complex exhibits three peaks in the regions 9800, 15900 and 25800 cm^{-1} . These peaks have been attributed, respectively to the transitions ${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, ${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ of octahedral geometry [34-36]. The value $\vartheta_2 / \vartheta_1$ (1.61) further supports octahedral geometry. The values of B (820 cm^{-1}) and β (0.80) observed for Ni(II) complex is indicative of the orbital overlap and M-L bonds are covalent in character. The Cu(II) complex reveals a peak at 18351 cm^{-1} (${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$) and a shoulder on the lower energy side at 13825 cm^{-1} (${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$), respectively indicates the distorted octahedral geometry around Cu(II) ion [37]. Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes show no bands in the visible region as expected for d^{10} system and have a peak at around 28500 cm^{-1} due to charge transfer. The complexes have been assigned octahedral geometry for [Zn(II)] and tetrahedral geometry for [Cd(II)] [38,39] in conformity with analytical, conductance and infrared spectral data. Pd(II) complex shows three peaks at 18700 (${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{A}_{2g}$), 21500 (${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$) and 24850 cm^{-1} (${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{E}_g$) where these transitions are characteristic of square-planar geometry [40]. Further, the band at 28000 cm^{-1} is due to charge transfer. Further, the $\vartheta_2 / \vartheta_1$

value observed for the complex is 1.14 which also supports the square-planar geometry [41]. The experimental magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) values for Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes are 4.95, 3.22 B.M. respectively, these values also suggest octahedral arrangement [42-47]. The magnetic moment value of Cu(II) complex is observed at 1.90 B.M, which indicates distorted octahedral geometry [48]. The complexes Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pd(II) are diamagnetic. The ESR studies are performed in order to identify the number of unpaired electrons and the type of bonds between ligand and metal ion of Cu(II) complexes. The EPR parameters are listed in Table 6.4 and Fig. 6.1. The ESR spectrum of Cu(II) complex in solid state was recorded at room temperature and shows two bands, one of small intensity towards low field and another one of large intensity towards high field. Based on these bands, the values of $g_{\parallel}$ and $g_{\perp}$ have been calculated [49]. From the results, $g_{\parallel} = 2.24$ and the other to $g_{\perp} = 2.05$. i.e. $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$, pointing out that metal ion contains an unpaired electron in its $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital, and suggests a tetragonal distortion around Cu(II) ions [50]. Kivelson and Neimann [51] showed that $g_{\parallel} > 2.3$ for ionic environment and < 2.3 for covalent compounds. The data presented in Table 6.4 showed that $g_{\parallel}$ obtained for present complex is less than 2.3 indicating the covalent character of M-L band. According to Hathaway and Billing [52], if G value is larger than 4, the exchange interaction is negligible, whereas if its value is less than 4 there is considerable interaction in solid complexes. In the present case, G is found to be greater than 4, thus ruling out solid state exchange interactions between copper centers. Further comparison of $K^2_{\parallel}$ and $K^2_{\perp}$, the observed $K^2_{\parallel}$ value is (0.603) greater than the value of $K^2_{\perp}$ (0.484) indicate out of plane pi-bonded [33] complex. The spin-orbit coupling constant (λ) was calculated using the relation.

$$g_{\parallel} = [2 - (8 \lambda / 10 Dq)]$$

The λ value for Cu(II) complex which is - 499 cm^{-1} was found to be much lower than free ion value λ_0 (-828 cm^{-1}) which also supports covalent character of M-L bond. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the ligand and its metal complexes are shown in Figs 6.2-6.4. In ^1H NMR spectra of the ligand, the carboxylic acid attached to O-H proton showed a signal at 12.93 ppm. In the complexes, the O-H proton showed the signals around 12.82-12.07 ppm. The signal for azomethine CH proton appeared at 8.72 ppm. The signal due to the proton of NH_2 attached to the pyridine ring was observed at 7.38 ppm as a singlet. In the spectra of complexes, the azomethine CH and NH_2 protons appeared in the range of 8.74-8.61 ppm ($\text{CH}=\text{N}$) and 7.33-7.28 ppm (NH_2), respectively. ^{13}C NMR spectra of the ligand showed chemical shift values at

167.49, 163.88 and 158.44 ppm due to carboxylic acid (C=O), (C=N) and (C-NH₂), respectively. The aromatic carbons were observed in the range 158.44-112.34 ppm, respectively.

Table 3.2 Infrared absorption frequencies (cm⁻¹) of ligand and its complexes

Compound	$\nu(\text{N-H})$	$\nu(\text{C=N})$ azomethine	$\nu(\text{C=N})$ (py)	$\nu(\text{C=O})$ carboxylic acid	$\nu(\text{M-Cl})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$
Co(II)	3371	1604	1564	1699	321	493
Ni(II)	3389	1663	1569	1704	275	520
Cu(II)	3390	1590	1562	1703	284	501
Zn(II)	3384	1592	1571	1697	315	481
Pd(II)	3401	1608	1570	1705	292	478
Cd(II)	3395	1618	1563	1705	283	490
3-APPHC	3420	1629	1567	1701	-	-

Table 3.3 Electronic spectral data, ligand field parameters and magnetic data of the complexes

Complexes	Frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	θ_2 / θ_1	10 Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B (cm ⁻¹)	β	Geometry
Co(II)	9000 18500 20400	4T _{1g} (F) → 4T _{2g} (F)(ν_1) 4T _{1g} (F) → 4A _{2g} (F)(ν_2) 4T _{1g} (F) → 4T _{1g} (P)(ν_3)	4.95	2.02	9250	756	0.78	Octahedral
Ni(II)	9800 15900 25800	3A _{2g} (F) → 3T _{2g} (F) (ν_1) 3A _{2g} (F) → 3T _{1g} (F) (ν_2) 3A _{2g} (F) → 3T _{1g} (P) (ν_3)	3.22	1.61	9800	820	0.80	Octahedral
Cu(II)	13825	2B _{1g} → 2E _g	1.90	-	-	-	-	Distorted

	18351	2B1g → 2B2g						octahedral
Zn(II)	-	-	Diamagnetic	-	-	-	-	Octahedral
Pd(II)	18700	1A1g → 1A2g	Diamagnetic	1.14	---	---	---	Square-planar
	21500	1A1g → 1B1g						
	24855	1A1g → 1Eg						
	28000	Charge transfer						
Cd(II) Tetrahedral	--	--	Diamagnetic	--	--	--	--	Tetrahedral

Table 6.4 ESR spectral data of Cu(II) complex

Complex	$\square_{\parallel}$	$\square_{\perp}$	$ g $	G	$\square_{\parallel} \times 105$ (cm-1)	$\square_{\parallel}$	$\square_{\perp}$	$-\lambda$ (cm-1)
Cu(II)	2.22	2.05	2.11	4.56	465	0.534	0.468	442

Fig.3.2 (a) ^1H NMR spectrum of 3-APPHC

Fig.3.2 (b) ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 3-APPHC

3.2 DFT Computations

The optimized molecular geometry for the ligand and its metal complexes are shown in Fig. 6.5. The results of bond angles, bond lengths and dihedral angles are presented in Tables 6.5 and 6.6. On optimization of geometry, the observed global minimum energy of the compounds are -816.95688 Hartree (3-APPHC), -2698.19907 Hartree [Co(II)], -2723.30339 Hartree [Ni(II)], -2749.76705 Hartree [Cu(II)], -2779.56640 Hartree [Zn(II)], -1865.00019 Hartree [Pd(II)] and -1904.886800 Hartree [Cd(II)] complexes, respectively.

Molecular electronic properties i.e. electron affinity (A), ionization potential (I), chemical potential (μ), global hardness (χ), global electrophilicity power (ω) of ligand and its metal complexes were obtained from frontier molecular orbital energies comprising of HOMO and LUMO.

HOMO and LUMO are known as frontier molecular orbitals. They are important in quantum chemistry, as they determine the molecular reactivity of conjugated systems [53] and the ability of a molecule to absorb electromagnetic radiation. HOMO plays the role of an electron donor, whereas LUMO acts as electron acceptor [54,55] The results are presented in Table 3.7 and illustrated in Fig. 6.6. The complexes under investigation, the frontier molecular orbital energy gap were found in the order 3-APPHC > Zn(II) > Co(II) > Pd(II) > Ni(II) > Cu(II)

> Pd(II). Generally, complexes with a small frontier orbital gap are readily polarizable and normally exhibit high chemical reactivity and low kinetic stability [56-58]. The frontier molecular orbital gap of metal complexes are small compared to the free ligand, hence the complexes are more polarizable than the ligand (Table 6.7). The chemical potential (μ) for the compounds being investigated are -7.31717 [(Co(II)), -6.71403 [(Ni(II))], -5.25906 [(Cu(II)), -6.76342 [(Zn(II)), -4.34001[(Pd(II)] and -6.18355 [(Cd(II)), complexes respectively, where the negative values indicate the complexes are stable [59].

Table 3.5 Optimized geometrical parameters of the ligand 3-APPHC

Bond length	Value (Å)	Bond angle	Value (°)	Dihedral angle	Value (°)
C1-C2	1.42122	C1-C2-C3	117.21480	C1-C2-C3-C4	-1.75184
C2-C3	1.39995	C2-C3-C4	120.27239	C2-C3-C4-C5	-0.45624
C3-C4	1.38588	C3-C4-C5	117.63683	C3-C4-C5-N6	1.91374
C4-C5	1.39556	C4-C5-N6	123.85376	C4-C5-C6-C1	-0.91487
C5-N6	1.33104	C5-N6-C1	118.55648	C5-N6-C1-C2	-1.54473
N6-C1	1.34098	N6-C1-C2	122.39875	N6-C1-C2-C3	2.84768
C3-H7	1.08346	C1-C2-C13	121.81121	C2-C3-C4-H7	-178.91721
C4-H8	1.08244	C2-C1-H14	116.88223	C3-C4-C5-H8	-179.00745
C5-H9	1.08661	C2-C13-N15	122.70621	C4-C5-N6-H9	179.66909
C1-N10	1.37990	C13-N15-C16	120.12913	C2-C1-N6-N10	178.14106
N10-H11	1.00981	N15-C16-C17	118.08140	C2-C6-N10-H12	31.02831
N10-H12	1.00683	C16-C17-C19	120.56235	N6-C1-N10-H11	-10.65379
C2-C13	1.46032	C17-C19-C23	120.28755	C1-C2-C13-N15	-169.38350
C13-H14	1.09707	C19-C23-C21	119.32780	C2-C13-N15-	-174.81323

				C16	
C13-N15	1.28063	C23-C21-C18	120.51530	N15-C26-C17-C19	-179.71188
N15-C16	1.39967	C21-C18-C16	120.30906	C16-C17-C19-C23	1.51244
C16-C17	1.40447	C18-C16-C17	118.95816	C17-C19-C23-C21	0.12311
C17-C19	1.38617	C16-C17-H20	118.56143	C19-C23-C21-C18	-0.82620
C19-C23	1.40246	C17-C19-H24	120.10095	C23-C2-C18-C16	-0.10306
C23-C21	1.39970	C23-C21-H25	118.76452	C21-C18-C16-C17	1.70937
C21-C18	1.38711	C21-C18-H22	119.96215	C18-C16-C17-C19	-2.41612
C18-C16	1.40679	C19-C23-C26	122.40065	C16-C17-C19-H20	-179.35360
C17-H20	1.08330	C23-C26-O27	125.22327	C17-C19-C23-H24	179.43723
C19-H24	1.08215	C23-C26-O28	113.07488	C23-C21-C18-H25	179.45454

C21–H2 5	1.08323	C26-O28-H29	106.54015	C21-C18-C16- H22	177.9093
C18–H2 2	1.08387	O27-C26-O28	121.70174	C19-C2-C26- O28	0.62241
C23–C2 6	1.48157	H14-C13-N15	120.40763	C2-C23-C26- O27	−0.26012
C26-O27	1.21031	C2-C1-N10	122.49422	C23-C26-O28- H29	−179.96170
C26-O28	1.35995	C1-N10-H12	119.07478	-	-
O28-H29	0.96819	C1-N10-H11	113.62942	-	-

Table 3.6 Selected bond lengths and bond angles of the complexes

Co(II)		Ni(II)		Cu(II)		Zn(II)		Pd(II)		Cd(II)	
Bond length	Value (Å)	Bond length	Value (Å)	Bond length	Value (Å)	Bond length	Value (Å)	Bond length	Value (Å)	Bond length	Value (Å)
Co1-N2	2.03218	Ni1-N2	2.30606	Cu1-N2	2.35000	Zn1-N2	1.91254	Pd1-Cl2	2.35353	Cd1-Cl2	2.40394

N2-C3	1.25976	N2-C3	1.27349	N2-C3	1.11398	N2-C3	1.30598	Pd1-Cl3	2.35015	Cd-Cl3	2.43548
C3-C4	1.44058	C3-C4	1.46220	C3-C4	1.37670	C3-C4	1.46406	Pd1-N4	2.07926	Cd1-N4	2.45793
C4-C5	1.42907	C4-C5	1.42019	C4-C5	1.43970	C4-C5	1.41436	N4-C5	1.31025	N4-C5	1.30728
C5-N6	1.47725	C5-N6	1.45039	C5-N6	1.46491	C5-N6	1.54326	C5-C6	1.46658	C5-C6	1.46379
N6-Co1	2.00350	N6-Ni1	1.96345	N6-Cu1	1.92265	N6-Zn1	2.06224	C6-C7	1.42277	C6-C7	1.42981
Co1-N2	2.03915	Ni1-N7	2.31058	N7-Cu1	2.33000	N7-Zn1	2.45651	C7-N8	1.44905	C7-N8	1.41537
N7-C8	1.26117	N7-C8	1.27292	N7-C8	1.11757	N7-C8	1.52726	N8-Pd1	2.10592	N8-Cd1	2.46608
C8-C9	1.44408	C8-C9	1.46166	C8-C9	1.37729	C8-C9	1.61935	Bond angle	Value (°)	Bond angle	Value (°)
C9-C10	1.42799	C9-C10	1.42012	C9-C10	1.43970	C9-C10	1.45384	Cl2-Pd1-Cl3	93.43178	Cl2-Cd1-Cl3	148.69442
C10-	1.48072	C10-	1.45018	C10-	1.46706	C10-	1.48	Cl3-	92.73	Cl3-	104.60784

N11		N11		N11		N11	986	Pd1-N4	289	Cd1-N4	
C11-Co1	2.00790	N11-Ni1	1.96451	N11-Cu1	1.93074	N11-Zn1	1.92163	Pd1-N4-C5	121.26035	Cd1-N4-C5	121.92251
Co1-Cl12	2.27016	Ni1-Cl12	2.29934	Cu1-Cl12	2.16467	Zn1-Cl12	2.29848	N4-C5-C6	125.87500	N4-C5-C6	126.03368
Co1-Cl13	2.28411	Ni1-Cl13	2.29944	Cu1-Cl13	2.16388	Zn1-Cl13	2.28958	C5-C6-C7	124.58417	C5-C6-C7	125.60388
Bond angle	Value (°)	Bond angle	Value (°)	Bond angle	Value (°)	Bond angle	Value (°)	C6-C7-N8	120.56767	C6-C7-N8	122.06983
Co1-N2-C3	111.64135	Ni1-N2-C3	119.58391	Cu1-N2-C3	100.05199	Zn1-N2-C3	123.34310	C7-N8-Pd1	112.52592	C7-N8-Cd1	112.57241
N2-C3-C4	142.99340	N2-C3-C4	126.55903	N2-C3-C4	138.89470	N2-C3-C4	123.78851	N8-Pd1-Cl2	85.61200	N8-Cd1-Cl2	114.37103
C3-C4-C5	115.68172	C3-C4-C5	124.07261	C3-C4-C5	123.35645	C3-C4-C5	128.93135	N8-Pd1-N4	88.21715	N8-Cd1-N4	73.41523

C4-C5-C6	119.35257	C4-C5-N6	121.01749	C4-C5-N6	121.34667	C4-C5-C6	121.95938	-	-	--	-
C5-C6-Co1	118.62623	C5-N6-Ni1	119.20823	Cu1-N7-C8	100.29560	C5-N6-Zn1	109.94615	-	-	-	-
Co1-N7-C8	111.65681	Ni1-N7-C8	119.45140	N7-C8-C9	138.75878	Zn1-N7-C8	99.63015	-	-	-	-
N7-C8-C9	143.07162	N7-C8-C9	126.62006	C8-C9-C10	123.21746	N7-C8-C9	134.60675	-	-	-	-
C8-C9-C10	115.57772	C8-C9-C10	123.92696	C9-C10-N11	121.23341	N8-C9-C10	98.91166	--	-	-	-
C9-C10-N11	119.19665	C9-C10-N11	120.95988	C10-N11-Cu1	101.77903	C9-C10-N11	120.17000	-	-	-	-
C10-N11-Co1	119.30108	C10-N11-Ni1	119.11235	N2-Cu1-Cl12	76.70180	C10-C11-Zn1	119.84187	--	-	--	-
N2-Co1-	91.87577	N2-Ni1-	91.59393	N6-Cu1-	92.18965	N2-Zn1-	85.26809	-	-	-	-

Cl12		Cl12		Cl12		Cl12					
N6- Co1- Cl12	86.81401	N6- Ni1- Cl12	85.80806	N7- Cu1- Cl13	77.89497	N7- Zn1- Cl12	83.2 7208	-	-	-	-
N7- Co1- Cl13	91.57108	N7-Ni1- Cl13	91.32768	N11- Cu1- Cl13	91.76743	N6- Zn1- Cl13	93.9 4000	-	-	-	-
N11- Co1- Cl13	87.35005	N11- Ni1- Cl13	85.84111	-	-	N11- Zn- Cl13	81.3 4695	-	-	-	-

Table 3.7 Frontier molecular orbital parameters of ligand and its metal complexes, values are expressed in (eV)

Frontier molecular Orbital parameter	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)	Pd(II)	Cd(II)	3-APPHC
HOMO energy	-7.82452	-7.12383	-5.50614	-7.57527	-4.84491	-6.36546	-9.05255
LUMO energy	-6.80982	-6.30424	-5.01199	-5.95158	-3.83511	-6.00165	-6.26097
Frontier molecular orbital energy gap	1.01470	0.81958	0.49415	1.62368	1.00979	0.36381	2.79157
Ionization potential	7.82452	7.12383	5.50614	7.57527	4.84491	6.36546	9.05255

energy (I)							
Electron affinity (A)	6.80982	6.30424	5.01199	5.95158	3.83511	6.00165	6.26097
Global hardness (η)	0.50735	0.40979	0.24707	0.81184	0.50489 6	0.18190	1.39578
Chemical potential (μ)	-7.31717	-6.71403	-5.25906	-6.76342	-4.34001	-6.18355	-7.65676
Global electrophilicity power (ω)	52.7653 1	55.0015 8	55.9690 3	28.1729 4	18.6530 2	105.0996 1	21.0011 7

3.2.1 Non-linear optical (NLO) behaviour

For the most part, density functional theory based approaches are of considerable importance for investigating new non-linear molecular systems [60]. Theoretical approaches have been utilized for determination of polarizability (β_{at}), hyperpolarizabilities (β_t), total dipole moments (μ_t) and anisotropy of polarizability ($\beta\alpha$) using density functional theory based on finite field approach and following Buckingham's definitions [61]. This method can reduce the cost and avoid synthesis work for measuring NLO properties. Generally, α_t and β_t were estimated for compounds in the presence of an applied electric field in order to predict cross section of various scattering process, molecular interactions and NLO properties of the system [62,63]. β_t is a third rank tensor hence, it was measured as a 3 x 3 x 3 matrix. From the basis of Kleinman symmetry [64], all the twenty seven components were condensed to ten components indicated as β_{xxx} , β_{xxy} , β_{xyy} , β_{yyy} , β_{xxz} , β_{xyz} , β_{yyz} , β_{xzz} , β_{yzz} , β_{zzz} . So, by using these components X, Y, Z we can calculate the μ_t , α_t and β_{tot} through the following equations.

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{\alpha_{xx} + \alpha_{yy} + \alpha_{zz}}{3}$$

$$\Delta\alpha = 2^{-1/2} [(\alpha_{xx} - \alpha_{yy})^2 + (\alpha_{yy} - \alpha_{zz})^2 + 6\alpha_{xx}^2]^{1/2}$$

$$\beta = (\beta_x^2 + \beta_y^2 + \beta_z^2)^{1/2}$$

$$\beta_x = \beta_{xxx} + \beta_{xyy} + \beta_{xzz}$$

$$\beta_y = \beta_{yyy} + \beta_{xxy} + \beta_{yzz}$$

$$\beta_z = \beta_{zzz} + \beta_{xxz} + \beta_{yyz}$$

Here, α , β and μ were calculated using DFT approach and the results are given in Table 3.8. It is a usual practice to determine the NLO behavior of compounds by comparing its μ and β with corresponding values of urea, which are 1.3732 Debye and $0.3728 \times 10^{-30} \text{ cm}^5/\text{esu}$, respectively. The calculated β of the ligand is $16.962 \times 10^{-30} \text{ cm}^5/\text{e.s.u}$, which is forty five times greater than urea. Hence, the ligand exhibits NLO properties. The complexes Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) showed more first order hyperpolarizability values compared to free ligand. The remaining complexes Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) showed lower first order hyperpolarizability values than the ligand. The non-linear optical activity was associated with the intra-molecular charge transfer, obtained from the electron cloud movement, through resonance [65]. Hence, the ligand and its metal complexes Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) are strong ones for the expansion of NLO materials. The components of first order hyperpolarizability were also helpful to understand charge delocalization in the compounds.

Table 3.8 The values of dipole moment μ (in Debye); polarizability α and first order hyperpolarizability β (in $10^{-30}\text{cm}^5/\text{e.s.u}$) of ligand and its metal complexes

Type of component	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)	Pd(II)	Cd(II)	3-APPHC
β_{xxx}	35.1312	1412.568 2	-437.8606	116.6001	-659.5690	228.2524 1	- 2215.229 1
β_{xxy}	-87.0246	- 1177.867 1	-241.1182	19.3886	737.6800	383.5935 9	-3.2906

β_{xyy}	39.0115	-624.5487	- 1023.028 7	-39.9696	51.2647	- 214.3756 0	159.2177
β_{yyy}	- 149.749 3	-645.5117	- 1755.555 8	-5.5846	1793.076 6	352.0562 6	-155.2760
β_{xxz}	-34.0008	-308.9618	31.8476	16.1393	-177.4568	-70.94831	-6.5763
β_{xyz}	-14.1808	-14.7839	19.7664	-14.5895	28.5835	-31.93086	-8.3224
β_{yyz}	36.1939	296.8233	447.3902	-9.1699	-114.7129	71.91038	-31.5628
β_{xzz}	0.7827	-37.6109	-16.9262	-8.3271	-127.2958	-26.42828	103.1029
β_{yzz}	0.5283	8.3044	89.1589	-7.4804	84.9524	67.61073	-42.6507
β_{zzz}	0.3429	-34.6800	65.0474	-18.8521	-201.0856	- 110.2472 4	7.4817
β_t	2.141×1 0-30 cm5/e.s. u	17.399×1 0-30 cm5/e.s.u	21.347×1 0-30 cm5/e.s.u	0.7048×1 0-30 cm5/e.s.u	23.876×1 0-30 cm5/e.s.u	7.0005×1 0-30 cm5/e.s.u	16.962×1 0-30 cm5/e.s.u
μ_x	0.4443	-4.3181	0.8809	-0.0019	-2.0877	-1.9209	1.7981

μ_y	-2.0118	-4.8734	-1.1144	-0.7539	12.0509	7.6770	-0.5068
μ_z	-1.1451	0.8624	-2.7097	-2.5866	-4.6024	-4.3357	-1.6375
μ_t	2.3571 Debye	6.5681 Debye	3.0595 Debye	2.6943 Debye	13.0676 Debye	9.0236 Debye	2.4848 Debye
β_{xx}	597.219 2	576.2061	608.3871	672.9969	364.6869	355.4640 1	356.8497
β_{xy}	28.7435	-105.6276	-67.3388	17.6290	-25.5022	-32.35211	-4.4959
β_{yy}	545.843 3	410.5628	526.1094	591.4939	242.7347	207.3546 1	170.6526
β_{xz}	-19.4824	22.6534	0.5215	10.0580	8.01807	3.80210	-5.0951
β_{yz}	32.9112	39.5342	-34.6070	-8.2554	23.4425	33.70313	-3.9852
β_{zz}	172.410 3	259.2901	280.3167	274.8413	136.4581	139.4124 5	115.5721
$\beta_{\alpha t}$	438.480	286.040	471.5960	513.1060	247.953	234.0733 3	214.3530

3.3 Biological evaluations

3.3.1 Antimicrobial screening

Microorganisms used in this work were three gram negative bacteria like *Proteus vulgaris*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, two gram positive bacteria like *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* and fungal strains such as *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Curvularia lunata*, *Rhizoctonia bataticola* and *Candida albicans* by disc diffusion method [66]. Streptomycin and Ketoconazole were chosen as the reference drugs for bacteria and fungi, respectively. The MIC values of the tested compounds and reference drugs were expressed in $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The results of antibacterial activity are presented in Table 6.9 and of antifungal activity are listed in Table 6.10. The antibacterial activity results revealed that Cu(II) complex exhibited excellent activity against *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris* strains (MIC: 4.21 and 8.18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively) and it is also showed significant activity against *B. subtilis* (MIC: 5.13 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and *P. aeruginosa* (MIC: 6.01 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The Pd(II) complex exhibited broad spectrum activity against the strains with MIC values of 5.17 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (*S. aureus*), 7.69 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (*B. subtilis*), 10.54 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (*P. vulgaris*), 7.24 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (*K. pneumoniae*) and 7.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (*P. aeruginosa*), respectively. Moreover, Zn(II) complex against *B. subtilis* (MIC: 11.50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), Ni(II) complex against *P. vulgaris* (MIC: 21.01 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), Cd(II) complex against *B. subtilis* (MIC: 13.89 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and Co(II) complex against *P. aeruginosa* (MIC: 10.91 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) exhibited moderate activity compared to the reference drug. The fungi results showed that Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes showed potent activity against *A. niger* (MIC = 3.94 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and *R. bataticola* (MIC = 6.24 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), respectively compared to standard Ketoconazole. The Cu(II) and Pd(II) complexes exhibited significant activity against *A. niger* with MIC values of 4.17 and 4.03 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. The Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes against *C. albicans* showed good activity with MIC values of 7.12, 7.99 and 8.18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. In addition, Ni(II) complex against *A. flavus* (MIC = 10.77 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and Zn(II) complex against *C. lunata* (MIC = 6.41 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) registered moderate activity. The remaining compounds showed poor activity against the tested microorganisms.

Table 3.9 MIC of the synthesized compounds against the growth of bacteria (μM)

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)					
Compound	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>
Co(II)	21.87	25.79	>100	30.79	10.91

Ni(II)	18.15	14.35	21.01	>100	24.86
Cu(II)	4.21	5.13	8.18	8.27	6.01
Zn(II)	>100	11.50	29.28	31.40	29.63
Pd(II)	5.17	7.69	10.54	7.24	7.25
Cd(II)	35.46	13.89	>100	17.28	>100
3-APPHC	50	>100	42.52	35.33	38.94
Streptomycin	3.42	3.15	6.25	3.15	4.27

Table 3.10 MIC of the compounds against the growth of fungi (μM)

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)					
Compound	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>C. lunata</i>	<i>R. bataticola</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
Co(II)	>100	17.25	50	50	7.12
Ni(II)	3.94	10.77	21.44	>100	7.99
Cu(II)	4.17	>100	26.45	6.24	8.18
Zn(II)	19.24	>100	6.41	>100	21.73
Pd(II)	4.03	18.72	>100	26.49	>100

Cd(II)	>100	15.43	>100	19.54	>100
ANABZA	>100	27.45	>100	35.29	21.05
Ketoconazole	2.92	3.85	2.16	4.57	3.26

3.3.2 Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity of the synthesized compounds have attracted a lot of interest and has been evaluated mostly in the *in vitro* systems [67,68]. The tested compounds were investigated for their antioxidant ability and these were carried out by using DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) radical as a reagent in the spectrophotometric test. Ascorbic acid was used as a reference antioxidant. The compounds were performed in triplicate and was then calculated standard deviation [69]. The IC₅₀ (μM) values are given in Table 6.11 and Fig. 6.7. It can be seen from the results that Zn(II) complex exhibited significant antioxidant activity with IC₅₀ value of $6.11 \pm 0.54 \mu\text{M}$ compared to the reference drug which showed IC₅₀ value of $4.61 \pm 0.93 \mu\text{M}$. The Co(II) complex showed good activity with IC₅₀ value of $7.63 \pm 1.57 \mu\text{M}$. Ni(II) and Cd(II) complexes exhibited moderate activity with IC₅₀ value of $13.16 \pm 0.85 \mu\text{M}$ and $17.16 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{M}$, respectively All the other complexes and ligand showed poor activity with IC₅₀ values between $20.96 \pm 1.82 \mu\text{M}$ to $29.47 \pm 0.18 \mu\text{M}$.

Table 3.11 Antioxidant activity of compounds by DPPH radical scavenging assay.

Compounds	IC ₅₀ (μM)
Co(II)	7.63 ± 1.57
Ni(II)	13.16 ± 0.85
Cu(II)	20.96 ± 1.82
Zn(II)	6.11 ± 0.54

Pd(II)	22.89 ± 1.26
Cd(II)	17.16 ± 0.16
3-APPHC	29.47 ± 0.18
Ascorbic acid	4.61 ± 0.93

3.3.3 *In vitro* anti proliferative evaluation

Based on the successful evaluations and positive results of the antimicrobial and scavenging activity, it was also decided to examine the anticancer evaluation against different cancer cell lines, IMR-32 (neuroblastoma), HeLa (cervical), MCF-7 (breast), A549 (lung), HepG-2 (liver) and HEK293 (embryonic kidney) by using 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) method. The MTT assay results are shown in IC₅₀, and expressed in micromolar units and were summarized in Table 6.12. The percentage of cell viability *versus* concentration graphs are shown in Fig. 6.9. Cisplatin was used as reference drug. The results clearly indicate that Zn(II) complex showed excellent anti-proliferative activity against IMR-32, A549 and HepG-2 with IC₅₀ value of 7.81 ± 0.52 μM, 6.18 ± 1.15 μM and 15.28 ± 1.26 μM, respectively. The values are close to standard cisplatin (IC₅₀ = 5.78 ± 0.12 μM, 4.90 ± 0.31 μM and 10.52 ± 0.40 μM, respectively) and they showed good activity against MCF-7 (IC₅₀ = 7.41 ± 0.32 μM) and HeLa (IC₅₀ = 5.99 ± 0.23 μM). Similarly Co(II) complex was potent with a broad spectrum activity with IC₅₀ values against HeLa (5.94 ± 1.13 μM), IMR-32 (8.51 ± 0.12 μM), HepG-2 (16.51 ± 1.18 μM), A549 (8.27 ± 0.38 μM) and MCF-7 (13.26 ± 0.19 μM). The observed higher efficiency of Co(II) and Zn(II) complexes are due to the presence of ligand coordinated to central cobalt and zinc metal ions. Also Ni(II) complex against HeLa (IC₅₀ = 12.72 ± 0.27 μM) and ANABZA against A549 (IC₅₀ = 19.38 ± 1.07 μM) exhibited moderate activity. The other compounds exhibited least activity against the cell lines. In addition, we have also tested the cytotoxicity of Co(II) and Zn(II) complexes against HEK293 with IC₅₀ values of 96.57 ± 0.42 μM and 81.37 ± 0.10 μM, respectively. None of the potent complexes [Co(II) and Zn(II)] interrupted the viability of the normal cell line, suggesting that the potent complexes are not toxic.

Table 3.12 Cytotoxic activities of newly synthesized compounds on human cancer cell lines IMR-32, HeLa, MCF-7, A549 and HepG-2

Compound	IMR-32	HeLa	MCF-7	A549	HepG-2	HEK 293
Co(II)	8.51 ± 0.12	5.94 ± 1.13	10.26 ± 0.19	8.27 ± 0.38	16.51 ± 1.18	96.57 ± 0.42
Ni(II)	40.21 ± 1.25	12.72 ± 0.27	39.98 ± 1.34	34.87 ± 1.19	71.26 ± 1.92	ND
Cu(II)	42.08 ± 0.61	39.08 ± 0.13	51.52 ± 1.12	43.13 ± 0.15	69.94 ± 0.38	ND
Zn(II)	7.81 ± 0.52	5.99 ± 0.23	7.41 ± 0.32	6.18 ± 1.15	15.28 ± 1.26	81.37 ± 0.10
Pd(II)	29.35 ± 0.52	17.38 ± 1.05	28.31 ± 1.52	28.37 ± 0.16	52.75 ± 0.81	ND
Cd(II)	50.12 ± 0.13	35.81 ± 1.26	43.06 ± 0.53	48.64 ± 1.05	61.12 ± 1.12	ND
3-APPHC	55.09 ± 0.81	45.35 ± 0.32	60.57 ± 0.27	19.38 ± 1.07	88.27 ± 0.28	ND
Cisplatin	5.78 ± 0.12	3.25 ± 0.23	4.63 ± 0.13	4.90 ± 0.31	10.52 ± 0.40	ND

Values are expressed in mean ± SD of three replicates. ND stands for not determine

3.3.4 Molecular docking

The *in silico* molecular docking analysis of the ligand and its metal complexes against human epidermal growth receptor (HER2) and epidermal growth factor (EGFR) was carried out to verify the relation between *in vitro* antiproliferative activity results and binding affinities of the inhibitors using auto dock programme. It plays a major role in the malignant growth from various origins [70]. It is expressed on the surfaces of most of the cell of human body [70] The over expression of HER2 involved in several cancers like breast cancer, adenocarcinoma of lungs, stomach cancer [71], ovarian cancer [72] and uterine cancer [71,72]. It is a suitable target for kinase inhibitors [70] on the other hand, EGFR is a prominent cell-surface receptor which belongs to the EGFR family [73]. The TKD (tyrosine kinase domain) and extracellular mutations of EGFR causes non small cell lung cancer and glioblastoma, respectively [74-76]. Its over expression also leads to epithelial tumors of the head, neck and anal cancer [77,78]. By

considering the aforementioned reasons, we have chosen target protein receptors HER2 and EGFR for docking studies. Herein, the main aim is to explore the binding behaviour (in terms of binding energy) of the target compounds against HER2 and EGFR and their results are compared with well established inhibitors (*in vitro* and *in vivo*) such as Canertinib (HER2), Afatinib (HER2), Lapatinib (EGFR) and Gefitinib (EFGR) [79]. The comparative docking studies of the compounds and the reported inhibitors (Canertinib, Afatinib, Lapatinib and Gefitinib) against proteins HER2 and EGFR along with their corresponding binding energies are listed in Table. 6.13. As shown in table 6.13, docking results revealed that Co(II) and Zn(II) complexes showed the least binding energies compared to other metal complexes against receptors HER2 and EGFR with their binding energies of -7.31 and -6.46 kcal/mol (for Co(II) complex); -8.02 and -7.35 kcal/mol (for Zn(II) complex), respectively. Hence HER2 and EGFR were taken as the target protein receptors for insightful discussion on Co(II) and Zn(II) complexes. The molecular docking results for Co(II) complex against HER2 exhibited four hydrogen bonds; one strong hydrogen bond between OH group of carboxylic acid moiety and the amino acid residue LYS875 with bond length 1.80 Å, one hydrogen bond between amino group of 2-aminopyridyl ring and amino acid residue SER720 with bond length 2.28 Å, one hydrogen bond between OH group of benzoic acid moiety and the amino acid residue ALA722 with bond length 2.90 Å and one carbon-hydrogen bond between -CH group of pyridyl ring and amino acid residue GLY724 with bond length 3.03 Å. The pyridyl ring interacts with amino acid residues ARG841 and CYS797 and the phenyl ring of the benzoic acid moiety interacts with amino acid residue ALA722 through hydrophobic interactions. In the related Co(II) complex against EGFR it exhibited eight hydrogen bonds; one strong hydrogen bond between -O- atom of carboxylic acid moiety and the amino acid residues ARG817 and GLY697 with bond length 1.87 Å and 3.28 Å respectively, one hydrogen bond between H-atom of the carboxylic acid moiety and amino acid residue ASP813 with bond length 2.14 Å, one hydrogen bond between carbonyl oxygen atom of the carboxylic acid group and the amino acid residue LYS721 with hydrogen bond length 3.04 Å, one hydrogen bond between amino group of 2-aminopyridyl ring and amino acid residue ARG817 with bond length 2.08 Å, one hydrogen bond between N-atom of pyridyl ring and the amino acid residue CYS773 with bond length 2.87 Å and one carbon-hydrogen bond between -CH group of pyridyl ring and amino acid residue ASP831 with bond length 3.16 Å, one hydrogen bond between N-atom of the imine group and the amino acid residue ARG817. The pyridyl ring interacts with the

amino acid residues LEU820, ARG817 and VAL702 and the phenyl ring of the benzoic acid moiety interact with amino acid residue ARG817 through hydrophobic interactions. The hydrogen bonding interactions and hydrophobic interactions of the Co(II) complex are shown in Fig.s 3.9 and 3.10.

Zn(II) complex against HER2 exhibited five hydrogen bonds; one strong hydrogen bond between the –OH group of benzoic acid moiety and amino acid residue PRO877 with bond length 1.69 Å, one strong hydrogen bond between the –OH group of benzoic acid moiety and amino acid residue ASP837 with bond length 1.85 Å, one hydrogen bond between –CH group of imine moiety with amino acid residue ALA722 with bond length 3.56 Å, one hydrogen bond between –CH group of pyridyl moiety with amino acid residue GLY719 with bond length 3.69 Å and one hydrogen bond between carbonyl group of benzoic moiety with amino acid residue PRO877 with bond length 3.77 Å. The pyridyl ring interacts with the amino acid residues ARG841, LYS745 and VAL726 through hydrophobic interactions. In addition to this there was an electrostatic interaction between the pyridyl moiety with amino acid residues ASP855 and CYS797. In the related Zn(II) complex against EGFR it exhibited eight hydrogen bonds; three hydrogen bonds between carbonyl oxygen atom of the carboxylic acid group and the amino acid residue ARG779, LYS851 and LYS889 with hydrogen bond lengths 1.93 Å, 1.95 Å and 3.37 Å, respectively, one strong hydrogen bond between the –OH group of benzoic acid moiety and amino acid residue LYS889 with bond length 2.98 Å, two hydrogen bonds between amino group of 2-aminopyridyl ring and amino acid residue SER696 with bond length 1.61 Å, and 1.92 Å, one hydrogen bond between *N*-atom of pyridyl ring with amino acid residue GLY695 with bond length 3.57 Å and one Pi-donor hydrogen bond between pyridyl ring and amino acid residue SER696 with bond length 2.97 Å. The pyridyl ring interacts with the amino acid residues ARG817 through hydrophobic interactions. The hydrophobic interactions also played a vital role in increasing the affinity between the synthesized compounds and targeted proteins. The hydrogen bonding interactions and hydrophobic interactions of the Zn(II) complex are shown in Fig.s 6.15 and 6.16. Finally, the docking results clearly suggest that the affinity of the synthesized compounds towards the protein receptor HER2 is better than that of the protein receptor EGFR. The docking results were quite consistent with experimental anticancer activity. The best docking poses of the remaining complexes [Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II) and Cd(II)] against the proteins HER2 and EGFR are shown in Fig.s 11-20.

Table 3.13 Binding energies of ligand and its metal complexes against protein receptors HER 2 and EGFR

HER2 (PDB ID: 3POZ)					EGFR (PDB ID: 4HJO)			
Compound	Binding energy (kcal/mol)	No. of Hydrogen bonds	Amino acid residues involved in the hydrogen bonding	Hydrogen bond length (Å)	Binding energy (kcal/mol)	No. of Hydrogen bonds	Amino acid residues involved in the hydrogen bonding	Hydrogen bond length (Å)
Co(II)	-7.31	4	SER720, GLY724, ALA722, LYS875	1.80, 2.28, 2.90, 3.03	-6.46	8	ARG817, ASP813, ASP831, LYS721, CYS773, GLY697	1.87, 2.08, 2.14, 2.87, 3.04, 3.14, 3.16, 3.28
Ni(II)	-7.08	4	MET793, ASP800, ASP855, CYS797	2.00, 2.37, 2.75, 3.09	-6.02	4	ALA698, PHE699, GLY700, SER696	1.67, 2.44, 2.51, 2.35
Cu(II)	-7.20	5	CYS797, ARG841, ASP800, ALA722, ASP855	2.08, 2.26, 2.88, 2.96, 3.02	-6.10	6	ARG779, LYS851, SER696, GLY695, SER696	1.79, 1.85, 1.91, 2.51, 2.89, 3.53
Zn(II)	-8.02	5	LYS875,	1.69, 1.85,	-7.35	8	ARG779,	1.61, 1.92,

			ASP837, PRO877, ALA722, GLY719	3.56, 3.69, 3.77			GLY695, LYS851, LYS889, SER696	1.93, 1.95, 2.97, 2.98, 3.37, 3.57
Pd(II)	-6.37	4	CYS797, ASP800, MET793	2.07, 2.09, 2.17, 2.31	-6.42	3	ASP831, GLN767, PHE832	1.73, 2.77, 3.38
Cd(II)	-6.90	5	MET793, THR854, ASP855	1.82, 2.20, 2.51, 2.53, 2.67	- 7.37	4	ARG817, ASP813, LYS851, LEU838	1.81, 1.82, 3.52, 2.99
ANABZA	-6.62	3	MET793, ASP855, GLN791	1.80, 1.84, 2.09	-5.56	5	LYS851, LYS721, ASN818	2.00, 2.65, 3.06 1.95
Canertinib	-7.73	2	ASN842, THR854	1.89, 3.36	-	--	-	-
Afatinib	-6.37	3	ASP800, ARG841, LYS745	2.71, 2.86, 2.56	--	-	-	-
Lapatanib	-	-	-	-	-5.94	3	CYS773, LYS721	3.08, 2.29, 2.95
Gefitinib	-	-	-	-	-6.60	6	ASP813, LYS721, ASP831,	3.03, 2.98, 2.85, 2.97, 1.82, 2.23

4. Conclusions

In summary, the complexes with Schiff base ligand have been designed, synthesized and characterized, with an aim to evaluate them for antioxidant, antimicrobial, cytotoxic activity, DFT calculations and HER2, EGFR target based *in silico* docking studies. The metal-ligand stoichiometry in the complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) corresponds to 1:2, whereas in case of Pd(II) and Cd(II), 1:1 stoichiometry was observed, wherein the ligand behaves in a bidentate manner towards metals coordinating through azomethine nitrogen atom and the nitrogen of amine group. Based on DFT and spectral studies, octahedral geometry is assigned for Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) complexes, distorted octahedral for Cu(II) complex, tetrahedral for Cd(II) and square-planar geometry for Pd(II) complex. All the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature in DMF. The evaluation of ESR parameters from the ESR spectrum confirms that the M-L bonds are covalent and out of plane π -bonded. From the antimicrobial activity results, it is known that metal complexes have better effect compared to the free ligand indicating that the metals are actually in action. Specifically, Cu(II) complex has shown excellent antimicrobial activity; likewise, Pd(II) complex exhibited a broad spectrum of antibacterial activity, and Ni(II) complex has shown superior antifungal activity compared to Streptomycin and Ketoconazole. Zn(II) complex has shown good antioxidant activity compared to reference drug ascorbic acid. In addition, complexes of Zn(II) and Co(II) have shown potent anti-proliferative activity against IMR-32 ($IC_{50} = 7.81 \pm 0.52, 8.51 \pm 0.12 \mu M$), A549 ($IC_{50} = 6.18 \pm 1.15, 8.27 \pm 0.38 \mu M$) and HepG-2 ($IC_{50} = 15.28 \pm 1.26 \mu M, 16.51 \pm 1.18 \mu M$), respectively. The docking results revealed that complexes Co(II) and Zn(II) exhibited the least binding energies against receptors HER2 and EGFR with their binding energies -7.31 and -6.46 kcal/mol (for Co(II) complex); -8.02 and -7.35 kcal/mol (for Zn(II) complex), respectively compared to Canertinib (HER2), Afatinib (HER2), Lapatinib (EGFR) and Gefitinib (EGFR). From the results, it is clear that the complexes are strongly bound to HER2 and EGFR protein receptors. Interestingly, these compounds have shown most potent anticancer activity and minimum binding energies obtained by docking study.

The results indicate that *in silico* molecular docking studies correlated well with the experimental anti-proliferative activity results.

2-aminonicotinaldehyde, which is structurally comparable to 2-aminobenzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde has been little investigated as a precursor for the synthesis of Schiff bases and their metal complexes. A number of reviews on Schiff base metal complexes derived from salicylaldehyde and 2-aminobenzaldehyde have been reported. 2-aminonicotinaldehyde should form similar Schiff bases and also form complexes with several metal ions. 2-aminonicotinaldehyde containing Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes are well recognized for their use in a variety of biological applications such as antibacterial, antimalarial, antitubercular, antifungal, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anticancer activities.

In particular, cancer is one of the most staggering and death causing diseases in the world which involves abnormal cell proliferation in the body. On the one hand cisplatin and its derivatives, and on the other hand, a large number of metal complexes have been introduced in the treatment of a variety of cancers. However, it was observed that there are several drawbacks regarding the use of complexes, which includes limiting efficiency, clinical usage and side effects. Excitingly, a large number of metal complexes have been evaluated to design the molecules for high selectivity, maximum efficacy and minimum toxicity.

In view of the aforementioned biological importance of the metal complexes and Schiff bases, we present here, novel metal complexes of Co(II), Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pd(II) with Schiff base in a single molecular framework and their potential *in vitro* anticancer, antioxidant, antimicrobial activities and *in silico* studies (DFT and molecular docking).

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Publications from the Thesis

Journal Papers

1. N. kotilingaiah,(2023), Co (II), Ni (II) and Cu (II) metal compounds of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde: Synthesis, crystalline structure, pharmacological assessment, and molecular docking research are all part of the process, *European chemical bulletin*, Volume(12), Issue(4), 6808-6821.
2. N. kotilingaiah and B.M. Praveen, comparative study of binary liquid mixtures containing p-methoxy benzoate acid and amides, *European chemical bulletin*, vol.(12), issue(s16), page no. 3395 – 3407.

Publications Of Patents

1. Dr.N.Kotilingaiah, synthesis of two dimensional inorganic materials for optoelectronics,(2023/1/9), *Indian patent*, Issue (202341047816).